

*Affective Sociomaterialisation: An Inquiry into
Early Childhood Subjectivities within Outdoor
Early Childhood Provision in Scotland, UK.*

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Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Philosophy in collaboration with Early Years Scotland.

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Declaration

I declare that this thesis is entirely my own and has not been previously submitted for another PhD or comparable award.

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Abstract

This doctoral thesis examines the formation of children's subjectivities, related to the metaphysical conditions of being and becoming a subject, within fully outdoor early childhood provision in Scotland. The role of outdoor play provision has been made central in recent years by the Scottish Government as part of the broader expansion of Early Learning and Childcare (Scottish Government, 2017a; Scottish Government, 2017b; Education Scotland, 2019c; Scottish Government, 2020a). This enhanced focus raises questions around how children form their subjectivities in such spaces and how this may differ from what is known about subjectivity within conventional indoor provision. Further, while the existing knowledge base on subjectivity in childhood is derived mainly from the intellectual progress made through the fields of social constructionism (Foucault, 1978), performativity theory (Butler, 2004; 2006; 2011) and developmental psychology (Piaget, 1948; 1957), concerns have been raised regarding the extent to which such frameworks may give primacy to the human, and the logics of humanism, over and above the non-human world (Barad, 2007; Dolphijn and Tuin, 2012; Braidotti, 2013). Such concerns warrant special attention in relation to entirely outdoor environments, where these approaches may underplay the significance of ontological and ontogenetic matters that contribute toward the formation of subjectivity.

This study applies a sociomaterial metaphysical framework to propose an alternative way of understanding how subjectivities come to form in early childhood environments, bringing together Spinozist (2002) monism and insights from process philosophy (Massumi, 2002) in relation to Deleuze and Guattari's (1987) concepts of the assemblage and affect. Methodologically, an ethnographic approach, inspired partly from the postqualitative field of scholarship, is employed to gather data on children's subjectivities at Wood Fire, a fully outdoor early childhood setting.

The findings of this study reveal the novel materiality and relationality of fully outdoor early childhood provision through which subjectivities are in-formed, and also point toward the ways that social and cultural determinacies continue to affectively orientate children's desires in the absence of clearly demarcated material spaces. Thus, these findings demonstrate a more expanded understanding of how we, humans, are produced as individuals in specific encounters through processes of 'affective sociomaterialisation'. Through the presentation of data in textual, visual and cinematic modes, practitioners are encouraged to re-evaluate the role of outdoor provision through a sociomaterial metaphysics that challenges conventional knowledges about how children's subjectivities are formed. Practically, this carries implications for how the materiality of outdoor environments is understood to contribute to the child's sense of self on more expansive terms.

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Preface: on coronavirus

The original purpose of this research project was concerned with finding new ways to understand how stereotypical practices associated with gender and sexuality were produced, and could be challenged, within early childhood. Designed as an ethnographic account, I had intended to spend my time producing data within a single nursery over a month-long period. I was over a year and a half into my PhD and on the cusp of commencing my fieldwork when the coronavirus disease, Covid-19, spread into the UK. As nurseries began to close around April 2020, it was initially thought to be a waiting game as to when I would be able to start my fieldwork. There was much uncertainty surrounding when I could safely enter any setting without posing a risk to children, parents, the staff team, and myself. Understandably, the staff in the setting that I spoke with were hesitant to say when this might be. At this point, then, some creative thought was required. Should I keep waiting and hope that I would be allowed back into the same setting? The projected scenarios on Covid-19 and the lack of a vaccine against this disease at the time meant that it would be unlikely that I could return at any point soon. Could I continue my research without gathering any empirical data? At this point, I had written most of an introduction, two whole literature chapters, and spent a substantial amount of time finalising my methodology chapter ahead of beginning fieldwork. I would have been faced with the task of rewriting large parts of my PhD to justify not gathering empirical data. Because of this, the seemingly most fruitful option was to switch my chosen nursery setting to an entirely outdoor environment.

Shifting to an entirely outdoor setting appeared to be the best course of action for several reasons. Firstly, because of Covid-19 and the heightened risk of airborne transmission within indoor spaces, entirely outdoor environments had the obvious advantage of significantly greater ventilation. Secondly, outdoor nurseries, and specifically the outdoor nursery that I proposed to work with compared to the original indoor nursery, are considerably larger in physical size. This meant that I could distance myself from the children and the staff during pick-up and drop-off times and still gather good quality data (in a technical, audio and video sense). From the initial call-out, I had received expressions of interest from many outdoor settings. However, they were excluded at the time due to location and transport costs. I am therefore grateful for the hardship fund provided by the Doctoral College within my university in alleviating the financial costs to make it possible for me to continue my research.

Though the transition in my fieldwork site was necessary to continue this PhD, it presented a challenge to the original research questions premised on conducting research within a conventional indoor setting. Demarcated spaces for specific kinds of play are commonplace within indoor

nursery settings, with areas such as the ‘home corner’ or the ‘construction area’ often created to facilitate certain kinds of play practices with the aid of particular materials (Davies, 1989; Browne, 2004). For example, the home corner is intended to replicate a conventional Western domestic space within the home, replete with pretend food, dining tables and chairs, and general kitchen apparatus. It represents ‘family life’ and, as such, games where children take on the role of ‘mummies and daddies’ who inevitably look after their babies, cook for each other, and ‘dress-up’ according to the materials available are thoroughly ordinary encounters. This is not a neutral process since the cultural discourse surrounding the family in Western societies is laden with heteronormative and gendered assumptions about *which* children can take up *what* roles. For example, it is the mummy who inevitably looks after the baby and dresses up with pretend makeup, with the daddy acquiescing to her authority on such issues. These roles are almost always aligned with the gender and assigned sex of the child, such that a boy who may attempt to dress up as a mummy would be seen as going against what they *should* be doing. As the existing scholarship has long made clear, this is often policed by both the children and the staff within the setting and, as I had proposed to explore, heavily facilitated by the materials themselves (Browne, 2004; Blaise, 2005a; Gunn, 2008; Hellman and Heikkilä, 2014; Børve and Børve, 2016; Lyttleton-Smith, 2017; Callahan and Nicholas, 2018; Care Inspectorate; Zero Tolerance, 2019; Black Delfin, 2020; Osgood and Mohandas, 2021). This begs the question, what might happen if the delineation of those spaces was removed?

The entirely outdoor setting that I eventually chose for my fieldwork, Wood Fire nursery, is somewhat exemplary of an ‘alter-childhood’ space (Kraftl, 2014). This is a term coined by Kraftl (2014, p. 219) to describe “explicit attempts to imagine, construct, talk about, and control the lifeworlds of children differently from a perceived mainstream ... not as a static category for naming particular discourses, against others (i.e., neoliberalism), but as a cipher for open and, hopefully, productive questioning”. Contra to the image I have described above of conventional settings, at Wood Fire there is no home corner. There is no construction area either, or any kind of delineated area for the children to engage in a certain type of play. The materials in the setting, and the space itself, forced me to think differently from received ideas about nursery environments. This does not mean that heteronormative practices did not occur at all during my visits to the setting, but my ethnographic gaze instead had to shift toward an understanding of children’s identity in a broader sense. I became interested in the coming-to of subjectivity itself, as it continually formed in novel ways through the children’s relation to their material environment (or, through the material environment’s relation to the children). In other words, my focus was not so much on identity as a fixed form, but rather as something always *in-formation* (Manning,

2016). This challenges the logic of identity categories as *a priori*, such as a child being already gendered as a boy or a girl, and instead considers how subjectivities are actively (re)produced through ongoing intra-actions to form identity (Barad, 2007). In this thesis I will assess the extent to which paying attention to these processes matters in unsettling the logics of individualism and anthropocentrism that continue to haunt dominant ways of knowing about subjectivity (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987; Braidotti, 2013).

While there is no shortage of literature examining the benefits of outdoor play for children, there remains a paucity of research concerned with how such environments might enable or constrain the child's capacity to express themselves in ways that might challenge how identity formation is conventionally understood. It would be easy to apply, as I have described above, the knowledge that is already known about indoor settings and conclude that in the absence of these spaces, such practices disappear entirely. However, this frames the question primarily in epistemological terms, overlooking the ontological and ontogenetic nature of how children might come to experience the force of power relations within encounters. For these reasons, in this thesis I develop a sociomaterial framework in order to blur epistemological, ontological, and ontogenetic boundaries and produce a metaphysical framework that would enable identity to be understood as an assemblage of social and material meanings and practices, rather than an overriding structural formation.

The thesis that follows, then, is not what it was initially supposed to be. The ambit has shifted. It has become otherwise. Some aspects of my earlier focus have stayed, for instance my intention to develop and evaluate a process of what I will come to describe as 'affective sociomaterialisation', as well as my intention to focus on spaces where power relations emerge to augment and striate children's identity formation and their sense of self. Other lengthy sections that I had written pertaining directly to heteronormativity will no longer feature. The hope is that they will form part of another piece of writing, another research-assemblage at some point in the future. Overall, I share all of this with you, the reader, in the spirit of honesty, and to convey the messy, wild and, at times, mad nature of doing a PhD. It is not entirely bad though, as Deleuze and Guattari (1983, p. 131) remind us, "madness need not be all breakdown. It may also be a breakthrough". This is the affirmative spirit with which I have managed and, I hope, will resonate through such uncertain times.

1 Chapter One: Introduction

*All terms in **bold text** are hyperlinked (Ctrl + Click) to the Glossary at the end of this thesis, all terms underlined contain a hyperlink to the relevant page (see page 10 for further information).*

1.1 Introduction

This chapter introduces the focus and rationale of my research thesis. I begin by problematising the question of **subjectivity** in early childhood and placing this study within the broader theoretical context concerned with how human subjectivities are formed. I then detail my overarching aims and any potential implications that I foresee arising from this study. In the latter part of this chapter, I consider my role as the researcher and my personal relation to this study before providing some notes on terminology and keywords for clarity. I close this chapter with a detailed summary of the structure and outline of this thesis.

1.2 Situating the problem: children's subjectivity and outdoor environments

The question of how children come to form their subjectivities, as expressed through their play experiences during their formative years, remains a central concern within early childhood studies. Several studies on this subject have argued that children's subjectivities can be both inherently creative and radically expressive (Olsson, 2009; Stockton, 2009; Hargraves, 2020). However, as the existing research also demonstrates, the **developmentalist** and **neoliberal** demands of curriculum and the determinate nature of socialising processes serve as a continual foreclosure of the child's capacity to express themselves indeterminately and to become-otherwise from the norms that can foreclose their potential (Biesta, 2013; Rose, 1999; Fendler, 2001). Ultimately it is these narrow conceptions that frame ideas around the purpose of education and, just as importantly, life itself (Manning, 2016; Manning, 2020). How we, as researchers, might better develop knowledges that may enable an uncoupling of subjectivity from these determinacies, or rather how we might reclaim *subjectivity against subjection*, remains a pressing concern for research inquiry.

That childhood is both an undetermined and creative period is not a radical claim. The fundamental value of allowing children to express themselves free from constraint has long been noted within the founding pedagogical methods of several early childhood theorists. The early writings of Friedrich Froebel (1967), Maria Montessori (1915), and the Reggio Emilia philosophy (Vecchi, 2010), which are often considered to be among the most influential early childhood

approaches within the Western world, all acknowledge the creativity of the young child in play and emphasise this as central to their pedagogies in one way or another. Developments in the natural sciences have enabled researchers to understand children's early experiences, too, where there is now plenty of evidence of greater brain plasticity and neurogenesis in early childhood compared to later life (Jung *et al.*, 2010; Rippon, 2019). Naturally, even in spite of these gains, how exactly cognitive processes relate to creativity is still unclear. Nor, read independently of broader contextual factors, would such information be necessarily useful. However, understood together with developmental theory, there is a case to be made that the formation of subjectivity in children's early years remains indeterminate and open to variation. In my own act of creativity, my reasoning in this thesis as a whole intends to work with and beyond these knowledges. I draw from the broader fields of philosophy and social theory to examine the basic grounds by which subjectivity comes to form in the face of processes of subjection and may be formed-otherwise (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987; Braidotti, 2002; Spinoza, 2002).

The primary purpose of this thesis is to advance a **sociomaterial metaphysics** for examining the formation of children's subjectivity within entirely outdoor childhood provision in Scotland. The role of outdoor play has been made central in recent years by the Scottish Government as part of the broader expansion of Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) provision (Scottish Government, 2017b; Scottish Government, 2017a; Education Scotland, 2019c; Scottish Government, 2020a). It is now seen as a fundamental part of growing up in Scotland. A number of guidance documents have been published to promote the value of the outdoors for children's learning and development (Scottish Government, 2017b; Scottish Government, 2017a; Education Scotland, 2019c; Scottish Government, 2020a). The latest of such guidance documents published in February 2020, 'Out to Play' (Scottish Government, 2020a), lists multiple 'life-enhancing' benefits for children including: greater physical health, improved mental wellbeing and enhanced developmental benefits. This guidance follows an earlier position statement on playing outdoors with over 90 signatories including the Scottish Government, NHS Health Scotland, a number of local authorities, national bodies and leading academics (Inspiring Scotland, 2018). Yet, none of these position statements involve any new ideas. The importance of outdoor play has long been enshrined within the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989). Nor is my intention for highlighting these guidance documents to contest any of the stated benefits of outdoor play. In other words, since at least the late-twentieth century it has been documented that such environments can provide novel experiences for children's play and their development. However, even with all the acknowledged 'life-enhancing' qualities of outdoor learning, questions still remain with regard to exactly how the

material nature of outdoor environments work to shape subjectivities in ways that may conform with, or challenge, the broader social and cultural normativities of any given society.

In this thesis I work from feminist and social justice perspectives concerned with developing ways to understand distributions of **power** in educational **spaces** (Freire, 2005; Braidotti, 2013; Coleman and Ringrose, 2013; Osgood and Robinson, 2019). From this position, it would be an oversight to believe that, in the absence of any fixed, and often heavily **gendered**, ‘home corners’ or ‘construction areas’, unequal power relations might simply disappear in outdoor environments or are no longer relevant. Yet this argument is implicit across all of the various policy and guidance documents where the question of how children come to form their **identity** is rarely present, or there remains an implicit adherence to the logics of developmentalism. As it stands within the academic scholarship, there is a paucity of literature in the Scottish context pertaining to the ways that children develop their identities in fully outdoor learning environments. However, it matters that attention is paid to children’s identity formation and the power relations that constrain capacities in such contexts. This thesis advances the argument that outdoor learning environments are not discrete bubbles distinct from the ‘real’ world and the pull of broader normative social and cultural determinations do not get left at the nursery gates. Indeed, the recent scholarship on **affect** has been salient in revealing the ways that certain power relations, often through habits, tendencies, orientations, and regularities still occur constitutively and in creative ways even in the absence of more explicitly visible normativising practices (Stewart, 2007; Massumi, 2015; Dernikos *et al.*, 2020). These authors argue that attending to how affects are felt in certain moments, often before they are consciously recognised, is crucial to noticing how power relations circulate between children and the material environments that they inhabit. The knowledge gained through an understanding of affect has the potential to extend what is known about how broader social and cultural constructions of identity categories come to fix children in place and determine the boundaries of what is possible.

Thus, my intention for working with affect is not necessarily to contest the notion that outdoor play can be ‘life-enhancing’, I am certain that in many encounters it can be, and I am keen to capture these moments. This will not be all negative critique. Rather, my intention for this thesis is to consider more closely the ways in which broader unequal relations of power within society are reproduced within children’s outdoor play encounters, and to demonstrate the creative affordances that a sociomaterial perspective may provide. Early childhood spaces are political as much as they are for learning to the extent that learning in itself is always-already imbued with political affectations (Rose, 1999; Fendler, 2001; Freire, 2005).

What is known about the politics of subjectivity in childhood is largely derived from the intellectual progress made through a primarily Foucauldian (1978) informed **social constructionist** framework, and Judith Butler's (2004; 2006; 2011) oeuvre, which will be discussed in terms of **performativity** theory. Both approaches build on the critiques of earlier socialisation models which too often produce the child as passive and without meaningful **Agency**, and developmental models which are criticised for providing normative, **neurotypical** and universal standards of human rationality (i.e. Piaget's ages and stages for development) (Prout, 2005; Burman, 2016). Instead, social constructionist and performativity theory approaches argue that power is social, and that children's identity formation is primarily constructed through their social relations (Naughton, 2005; Robinson and Diaz, 2006; Martin, 2011; Moore and Reynolds, 2018; Fleer and Oers, 2018). It is language vis à vis **discourse** that functions as a form of social control and represents reality. Therefore, the primary goal of scholars influenced by Butler, Foucault and similar theorists has been to deconstruct words, phrases and ideas to understand how established discourses regulate certain bodies. In this thesis, I proceed on the basis that both approaches, and that of **developmental psychology**, toward children's identity formation in early childhood which pay attention to language in the constitution of social reality have greatly enhanced understandings of normative identity formations. Yet, I also share the concerns of others (Barad, 2007; Dolphijn and Tuin, 2012; Coleman and Ringrose, 2013; Kirby, 2017; Braidotti, 2019) that a framework that regards identity formation as primarily social or structural has significant **epistemological** implications for how dominant power relations are interpreted and might be challenged.

The productive contributions thus far must be stressed as crucial. However, the argument has been made that any conceptual framework that primarily addresses the social realm inevitably restrains the possibility for resistance against these forms of power to the domain of discursive (human) agency, thus bracketing out the social world from the (**non-** and **more-than-human**) material world that enables it (Barad, 2007; Kirby, 2017). This parsing of nature from culture is widely acknowledged as the defining feature of Rene Descartes' (1985a) dualistic **humanism**, where the mind is perceived as hegemonic to matter and both remain **ontologically** distinct. In Chapter Two, I will consider the extent to which Descartes' philosophy remains axiomatic to contemporary perceptions of subjectivity.

This thesis will instead consider the merit of sociomaterialism as a metaphysical approach that may enable a different focus toward ontological and **ontogenetic** concerns surrounding the nature of subjectivity and identity, less as a monolithic form but rather as 'force' (Manning, 2012). Put differently, the formation of children's identity might be more accurately understood as always **in-****formation** in relation to one's social *and material* environment, as a continual process rather than

an independent ‘form’ alone. This is not to completely discount form, but to resituate it as co-compositional with movement; not only to ask what form *is* but *how it comes to be* in the first place in a more processual and relational sense. Though a relatively nascent field, the research literature is already beginning to demonstrate how such a framework is especially useful for research with children on the cusp of verbal language, where paying attention to material things (a dumper truck, a stick, some mud) and play spaces (a tyre-hill, a climbing frame) may better illustrate the complex flows of power working to shape how bodies become subject to normativising identity formations and, importantly, how they may become-*otherwise* from the felt imperatives to conform (Olsson, 2009; Lenz Taguchi, 2010; Sellers, 2013; Renold and Mellor, 2013; Lyttleton-Smith, 2015; Fournier, 2019).

As I will consider in Chapter Two, in the Western context within which this thesis is situated, the influence of **capitalist** and neoliberal practices in shaping children’s identity formation is unmistakable (Mccafferty, 2010; Giroux, 2014; Ball, 2015; Roberts-Holmes and Lee, 2019; Roberts-Holmes and Moss, 2021). The subject-form is co-constitutive with these processes through varying modes of control (Deleuze, 1992b). More precisely, it is the prefigurative and affective nature of these controls that are my primary concern. For childhood, these controls operate as recursive temporal investments in future feed-back that capitalist hegemonic (and ergo neurotypical, gendered and racialised) modes of subjectification determine (Coleman, 2009; Parisi and Goodman, 2011; Swindle, 2011). One example of this is Lee Edelman’s (2004) concept of ‘reproductive futurism’ and the persistent idealisation of childhood on **heteronormative** terms. Here, hegemonic discursive constructions of an *a priori* heterosexual child enact a temporal narrative of an already anticipated future reality, it is within the idealised family that the image of the child remains central to this compulsory narrative of reproductive futurism. Family and home corner play are ubiquitous in early childhood settings, prefiguring an idealised white, Western, domestic utopia (Taylor and Richardson, 2005; Ericsson, 2012; Sotevik, Hammarén and Hellman, 2019).

The question I seek to address in this thesis, therefore, is in the absence of such spaces, (how) do issues surrounding gender, sexuality and other unequal power relations still (come to) matter? This is to say that, given what is already known about how children’s identity is shaped by the broader determinations, especially within indoor early childhood environments (Blaise, 2005b; Robinson, 2013), it remains necessary to consider how this process works in ‘**alter-childhood**’ (Kraftl, 2014) outdoor play environments, too. Bringing my theoretical proposal together, I argue that such an inquiry might reveal a novel perspective toward childhood in terms of what I will come to describe as ‘**affective sociomaterialisation**’. The intention is that this approach may provide new insights

into the ways that power relations emerge within spaces to foreclose children's capacity to act. The approach I advance here is fundamentally about understanding how the normative social and cultural determinations of identity that can prohibit how humans experience the world come to be in-formed. These are determinations that are predominately perpetuated by historically-present epistemologies of humanism that privilege **individualism**, neurotypicality and perpetuate **anthropocentrism** (Braidotti, 2013).

1.3 Thesis aims

This thesis has three overarching aims:

1. To advance a metaphysics of sociomaterialism toward understanding children's identity formation
2. To examine the potential for outdoor early childhood environments to facilitate thinking otherwise beyond deterministic identity formations.
3. To evaluate how a sociomaterial framework toward understanding children's identity in-formation can assist future learning and teaching.

Regarding my initial aim, in this study I bring the current epistemological knowledges on the formation of children's identity together with what is loosely described as the 'new materialist' wave of scholarship, concerned with the ontological and ontogenetic significance of materials, objects and 'things' (Coole and Frost, 2010; Dolphijn and Tuin, 2012; St. Pierre, Jackson and Mazzei, 2016; Fox and Alldred, 2017). With these, I seek to establish whether a metaphysical framework of 'sociomaterialism' might enable a more creative exploration of children's identity formation. This line of inquiry enables a reassessment of the fundamental metaphysical knowledges that have directed understandings of subjectivity thus far, away from the Cartesian legacy of privileging the individual self as the locus of experience. In this project, I am mobilised by concerns that the privileging of language, discourse and culture has resulted in a failure to theorise the relationship between discursive (linguistic) and non-discursive (material) practices (Barad, 2007). In contrast, the sociomaterial argument that I advance draws from Spinoza's (2002) **monist** (episto-ontological) metaphysics to examine how non-human and human elements come together within the nursery site. I utilise monism in relation to the Deleuzian concept of the **assemblage** to reconceive of the ways onto-epistemological entanglements make matter *matter* (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987; Barad, 2007). I intend to examine the extent to which bodies, human or not, might always be **being** and **becoming** in relation to other bodies (as assemblages) which

in turn affect how the body is (possibly always, already) permeable to the influence of others. Through my account of sociomaterialism, mobilised in part through a **postqualitative** mode of inquiry, I propose that there may be implications for how children's developing identities are understood, including challenges to conventional knowledges on the roles of agency and performativity. Overall, based on what is already known about the ways in which children's identities are continually caught up in broader social determinations of childhood, this thesis places the material alongside the social in an attempt to further understand the workings of how dominant power relations contribute toward deterministic modes of identity. I propose that this constitutes an original approach as I intend to provide a novel conceptual interpretation of sociomaterialism as drawn together from various disparate strands of literature. I further anticipate that the application of my synthesis in the Scottish context should provide new knowledges toward what is already known about childhood and children's identity formation in fully outdoor, alter-childhood environments (Kraftl, 2014).

In relation to aim two, by working at the intersections of research critique *and* **research-creation**, in this thesis I not only aim to better understand dominant power relations that contribute toward determinate modes of identity, but I also aim to think-otherwise as a crucial gesture towards capacities for *resistance* against deterministic identity formations (Grosz, 1999a; Massumi, 2015). This thesis stakes the claim that outdoor play environments that facilitate new knowledges of how children should play, according to the materials, the space and other non-human inhabitants, enable a reconsideration of how these environments come to compose children as individuals. In the absence of more distinctly delineated and typically heavily gender conforming (Davies, 1989; Browne, 2004) spaces, these environments raise questions around *if* and *how* children still come to be determined according to conventional norms. I intend to propose the use of Deleuze and Guattari's (1987) concepts of **'smooth' and 'striated' spaces**. I aim to apply these within a fully outdoor early childhood environment to understand how particular spaces enable, constrain, or allow the creation of new (experimental) subjective formations. The latter of these terms refers to practices of organisation and binding created by sociomaterial demarcations of territory that (re)produce determinate and molar affects. In contrast, smooth spaces, are nomadic, unpredictable and allow for the production of new knowledges to occur. Consequently, in this thesis I intend to bring philosophical thought together with artistic practice to challenge **representationalist** modes of thinking and instead privilege a more experimental form of presentation (Grosz, 2008). Based on my fieldwork, I intend to produce a video montage that might unsettle the persistence of human subjectivity and induce **haptic perception**. Illustrating such occasions of experience is an endeavour toward producing childhoods differently through examining epistemological and

ontological matters in relation. It also aims to bring concepts to life, provoking new knowledges and thinking with theory-as-practice.

Finally, in light of the novelty of the sociomaterial framework that I intend to produce, this thesis also evaluates how such a way of approaching questions about children's identity formation may assist future early childhood practice. My aims are to critically examine how sociomaterialism may disrupt human-centric understandings of childhood to provoke new knowledges of how normativising practices are assembled to order certain behaviours, spaces and objects. My intention for this research is not to offer enclosed prescriptions for practice to be followed, but rather to provoke new knowledges and foreground other ways of knowing from a theoretical paradigm that does not privilege human agency over materiality. This has implications for pedagogical knowledges and how research inquiry might more successfully understand how subjectivities are in-formed and may be in-formed otherwise within early childhood spaces. Alternatively, this project might be conceptualised as a change in the 'minor key' (Manning, 2016). I work through the existing scholarship on social and cultural determinacies to understand how children's capacities come to be foreclosed, and at the same time examine the processes that may unsettle the already-known. Further, I contend that understanding the sociomateriality of childhood might respond to a number of broader questions about our, human, relation to the non-human worlds that we inhabit. The violent tenets of humanism and anthropocentrism remain axiomatic in the present day, perpetuating individualism as well as (false) notions of human mastery over non-human worlds (Ingold, 2000; Braidotti, 2013; Snaza and Weaver, 2014; Singh, 2018). In the Scottish Government's (Education Scotland, 2019b) educational curriculum, these tendencies are built into how children and childhood is understood through, for example, the implicit metaphysics of Piagetian developmental psychology ([see page 37](#)). Yet I intend to propose that sociomaterialism may enable a different way of knowing about how children might already be engaged in different ways of living. How, once the individual child is decentred as the sole unit of agency and consider the materiality of the world, they are already being and becoming in ways that cast a shadow on how we, as adults, currently understand the nature of experience itself. As an auxiliary aim, then, this thesis may provide an opportunity to examine *what children and childhood might be able to teach us*, as adults, as much as we might be able to support them.

1.4 Researcher positionality

The sociomaterial framework that I advance in this thesis implicates a way of situating myself as the sole researcher that aligns with the history of feminist scholarship on positionality (Haraway,

1988; Tuana, 1989; Harding, 2004). As such, I make no claims to the ‘objectivity’ or ‘neutrality’ of my research position. While such claims to these principles may appear sound, the epistemological grounds from which these terms are derived are problematic because they are rooted in a way of knowing that presupposes a (false) relation between the researcher and the object of their inquiry. The implications of this for research inquiry, as Braidotti (2013) writes, have meant that supposedly objective methodologies have overwhelmingly acted in the interests of maintaining universalist criteria of validity from an artificial positioning of the researcher as clearly distinct from their research. While, theoretically, objectivity may seem sound, in reality it is rarely, if ever, possible. If we, as researchers, come to recognise and accept that our thoughts, decisions, and **desires** always shape practices in a way that often elides conscious decision, then to maintain a position of neutrality is a *non sequitur*. Instead, I take the position, that issues of this kind might be more usefully addressed if researchers were to rethink their troublesome commitments to universality and become more *ethically responsible* for the research that we produce (Barad, 2007). This is to say that we, as researchers, need to remain implicated both in what we critique and what we create. My approach therefore follows Barad (2007) in staking the claim that we cannot know the world by studying it at a distance, we know because we are part of its very becoming. This is deeply ethical work that holds me accountable for what gets produced. This thesis is therefore written with the explicit subjective intention of social justice in its widest human and non-human sense, motivated by both feminist (Ahmed, 2014a; Coleman, Page and Palmer, 2019; Osgood and Robinson, 2019), more-than-human (Barad, 2007; Braidotti, 2013), and anti-**colonial** (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987 see Chapter Six) logics.

It also matters to note that my own experience of ‘political depression’ motivates the production of this thesis (Cvetkovich, 2012). As someone who has long been interested in the politics of social justice, both within and outside of the early childhood field, the challenges of the current political climate have long felt, at times, insurmountable. Manning (2020, p. 141) captures this felt sentiment when she writes that “Everything matters, all the time, the body poised to leap, the nervous system on high alert. Enthusiasm, excitement, and then, too often, chaos, or entropy, or inertia ... [Then] Burnout”. Political depression therefore can be said to mark a continual frustration that ongoing efforts toward radical change beyond reformism have thus far been insufficient, and that it continues to be easier to imagine the end of the world than the end of capitalist individualism (Fisher, 2009; Cvetkovich, 2012). In the face of how to respond, I believe with others that new modes of engagement are necessary (Probyn, 2004). By utilising a sociomaterial framework, this PhD aims to effectively widen the scope of analysis to ask *what else* comes to matter when the human as the primary unit of analysis is dislodged. Further, through my engagement with artistic

practice in Chapters Five and Six, my approach also works through ‘politics by other means’ in seeking to elaborate new possibilities of more-than-human being and becoming (Grosz, 2008).

As well as my political outlook, my rationale for an engagement with new ways of exploring practices in early childhood stems from my experience as a former early childhood practitioner. Working within a profession that has historically been rendered ‘women’s work’ (Apple, 1986), I have always wrestled with the issue of normative identities and how they manifest in practice. At the same time, such knowledges have, and continue to, impress upon me. The affective nature of normative practices so often boundary me, a Black male, as an ‘outsider’ against normative figurations of the white, female practitioner. I name this to make clear that I myself am not free from the very logics of identity that I describe throughout this thesis.

1.5 The research

This empirical side of this thesis is drawn from a multi-sensory postqualitative ethnography of a fully outdoor and alternative early childhood setting within Scotland. Wood Fire nursery is a fully outdoor environment for children from two years of age, set on grounds comprised of field, meadow, and woodland areas, with an indoor space, known as a ‘Yurkie’. Wood Fire differs from conventional mainstream provision insofar as the total area for children to play in is roughly 49,000ft² (4,559.66 m²), offering masses of space for the children and far more than a conventional indoor setting could ever provide. Chapters Five and Six, in different ways, will detail my time at Wood Fire in full, where I will consider how the sociomateriality of the children’s play encounter forces us, adults, to reconsider how children come to in-form their senses of self through outdoor environments.

1.6 Glossary and Terminology

It matters what matters we use to think other matters with; it matters what stories we tell to tell other stories with; it matters what knots knot knots, what thoughts think thoughts, what descriptions describe descriptions, what ties tie ties.

(Haraway, 2016, p. 13)

Following Haraway (2016), this thesis takes the position that the language used to describe worlds is not separate from reality, but rather produces it. A Glossary of terms is located at the end of this

thesis ([see here](#)) and referenced in bold text in the first instance of each term's use from Chapter One onwards. Other text underlined also indicates a hyperlink to the referred place for ease of use. The reader is encouraged to use the hyperlink function (Ctrl + click) for each, and, if available, return their first position in the main text. The terms listed in the Glossary relate to the body of scholarship within this thesis and relevant areas of inquiry. Therefore, it is more specialised than a core or general glossary and, unless necessary, does not cover broader terms relating to theory and research. I also extend and clarify some initial terms in further depth here to orient the reader.

1.6.1 Subjectivity and Identity

In this thesis, I focus on both subjectivity and identity. However, my focus will tend toward the former as it relates to the metaphysical conditions of 'being' and 'becoming' a subject. Where I name identity, this is to denote the more legible representation of a subject on terms aligned with social classifications, such as gender or race. Thus, it may be interpreted as consequential from subjectivity. As will become clear in forthcoming chapters, my concern is less about what subjectivity 'is' in terms of giving it an identity, but rather how it works and what that then means through a sociomaterial framework.

1.6.2 Sociomaterialism

The overall body of scholarship that I work with in this thesis might feasibly be referred to in a number of distinct ways with histories that are far from straightforward to trace. Terms such as 'new materialism', the **'posthuman'**, the 'more-than-human' and the 'sociomaterial' are often used to refer to, on the surface, very similar theoretical fields. For Maclure (2017), each might be deemed exemplary of 'catachresis'- perpetually misused and without a stable referent. As she points out, "it would be absurd to say that we are talking about a unified philosophical or methodological field here" (ibid, p. 50). Within this thesis, I have made the decision to avoid the term 'new materialism' where possible. Primarily, this is because I am wary that this apparent 'newness' will not last. I also recognise that many of the ideas presented are only new in the sense that they have recently regained traction in Western academic scholarship. There is a documented history of ideas around agency and materiality in indigenous cultures (Mignolo, 2012), and within certain historical strands of Western philosophy (i.e., Spinoza, Nietzsche).

A more difficult decision has had to be made regarding my usage of the terms 'more-than-human' and 'posthuman' as either distinct or interchangeable that is worth some discussion here. More-than-human is a phrase usually attributed to Whatmore (2002) within the field of human geographies and has generally retained its meaning as expressive of an inherent relationality between non-human and human worlds (which I explore further in Chapter Three). Notably,

Whatmore introduces this term to challenge perceived limitations with Donna Haraway's (1991) argument for 'posthumanism' in the figure of the cyborg. For Whatmore (2002, p.160), Haraway is unconvincing in establishing the precise nature of how human and non-humans relate to each other insofar as her notion of the cyborg ontologically presupposes individual beings which then come together in hybrid, cyborg, form.

Haraway (2008, p. 17) has since come to distance herself from the posthuman label, stating that she "never wanted to be posthuman, or posthumanist, any more than [she] wanted to be postfeminist". Yet she is still widely associated with the use of this term (Åsberg and Braidotti, 2018, p. 7; Braidotti and Hlavajova, 2018, p. 95), and has further articulated her interpretation of relationality following Karen Barad's (2007) notion of **intra-action**. Barad (2003) also speaks of a '**posthuman performativity**'. Further, for many authors (Taguchi, 2012; Walker, 2014; Sheldon, 2016; Murrin and Bozalek, 2019), although not all (Hein, 2016), Barad's conceptual framework can be read productively with the metaphysical framework of Deleuze and Guattari (1987) ([see page 59](#) for a discussion of this). This is notable because Whatmore's attempted resolution to the perceived limitations of Haraway's original position is a turn to Deleuze and Guattari's concepts of affect and becoming. Therefore, it can be said that while more-than-human and posthuman are initially presented as distinct, Haraway's recent articulation through Barad indicates a theoretical resonance between both *vis à vis* Deleuze and Guattari.

Given the entangled lineages of these terms, one may be sympathetic to a lack of distinction in usage within the literature. An additional consideration is that, for one who is unacquainted with this research field, in wider culture the notion of the 'posthuman' is often conflated with the 'transhumanism', which itself refers to scientific and technological developments that attempt to *enhance* the human (rather than, fundamentally, question what human is) (Åsberg and Braidotti, 2018). To avoid this unhelpful crossover, where possible I will use more-than-human. However, it will not be my primary term. My intention is to develop a 'sociomaterial' proposal and speak in terms of 'affective sociomaterialisation' to indicate an epistemic association with other dominant theoretical frameworks used in early childhood. For instance, whereas it is common to say that 'childhood is a social construct', this thesis advances the argument that childhood might rather be constructed socially *and materially*. Whereas childhood is often understood through processes of socialisation, I argue that it be understood in terms of *affective sociomaterialisation*. The term sociomaterial also is uncuffed from any latent initial association with the human as *a priori*. As I will come to examine, it is through the social (in terms of epistemology) and the material (through processes of ontogenesis) that the subject, or the human, then emerges, in contrast to the position that there is the human from which we then become 'more-than' or 'post-'. Further,

sociomaterialism is already used within the educational research field where I am partially situated (Kervin, Comber and Woods, 2017; Postma, 2012; Henderson, 2015; Fenwick, Edwards and Sawchuk, 2011). However, I avoid the hyphen between the two terms to indicate the entanglement of both relations together. Finally, my preference for the term sociomaterialism should be interpreted as an indication that I am not interested in staying faithful to a singular theorist. My preference is to work against strict impersonations of the canonised versions of philosophy in the interests of proposing an exploratory conceptual framework that best aligns with my intended object of inquiry. As I will discuss further in Chapter Three, I intend to utilise an approach of ‘conceptual pickpocketing’ (Braidotti, 2002) as a means of bringing different knowledges together as part of my sociomaterial proposal for understanding subjectivities.

1.6.3 ‘Early Childhood’, ‘ELC’, and ‘educator’

In this thesis I will use ‘Early Learning and Childcare’ (ELC) to refer to all research and professional practice with nursery settings in Scotland that offer education and childcare to children up to school age. These include family centres, nursery schools, nursery classes attached to primary schools, and childminders. ELC settings can be operated by local authorities, private businesses, or the voluntary sector. More generally, I will broadly use the phrase ‘early childhood’, as a shorthand for Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC), for all formal services outside the child’s home that provide care and education for children from birth to school age.

Secondly, while a number of titles are used to describe those who work within early childhood, I have settled on ‘practitioner’ as an imperfect term. Browne (2004) has been especially critical of the term practitioner, arguing that it implies that work with young children is essentially routine and mechanical. I question whether this is an issue of the term itself, or rather to do with how early childhood is perceived compared to other professions. The prestige attributed to the health sciences as a profession, for instance, means that ‘medical practitioner’ is a commonly accepted term. Browne’s preference is ‘educator’ insofar as she believes that it relates more closely to the underlying purpose of early childhood. This is a term I have used myself elsewhere (Tembo, 2020a). However, my position has since shifted. In privileging the educative nature of early childhood, I am cautious that this precludes the value of ‘care’ with young children. Secondly, I would argue now that education being the core purpose of early childhood professionals is not a universal truth. One could easily understand it as the adult’s role to *facilitate* the child’s experiences, as much as it is to educate them. I recognise that practitioner contains neither a nod to education nor care, nor facilitation, but it does gesture toward the ‘doingness’ of the role and is the most commonly used term. Nor is there anything to say that practitioner could not relate to education

and care. Perhaps the vagaries of the term are a strength in terms of refusing limitations. For these reasons, I will stay with practitioner as my term of choice.¹

Finally, there is a serious playfulness with my language at times throughout this thesis. I make use of footnotes throughout my writing. This is partly following the style of other writers as evidence of *overflow*, and, with Massumi (1992, p. 9), partly as evidence of “how hard it is to keep a text in departure from taking leave of itself”. One might argue that footnotes can disrupt the flow of the argument by drawing attention away from the main text. I sympathise with this view, though the reader is under no obligation to read them. This thesis operates perfectly well without footnotes. I share Sword’s (2012, p. 140) sentiment that footnotes offer me, the writer, an “unmoved corner of grass where [I] can let [my] proverbial hair down and run wild”. Needless to say, the most salient points will remain well within the main body of my writing. Elsewhere, I pluralise words to both agitate any notion of a singular monolithic mode of thought and signal dynamism and multiplicity, and there are certain words that I have deliberately unlearned through the process of writing this thesis. Overall, these minor idiosyncrasies are a means of inducing a bit of life into the text, of bringing the text to life.

1.7 Thesis summary

This thesis follows a traditional structure where I begin by examining states of knowledge to underpin and situate this research study. Following this introductory chapter, in Chapter Two I pay attention to how the child’s subjectivity is understood within the Scottish curriculum. After an overview of the national context, I examine how subjectivity might currently be understood in relation to the influence of neoliberal thought and developmentalism within curriculum. This section is then underpinned by an evaluation of conventional approaches toward children’s subjectivities, turning to the principal frameworks of social constructionism, performativity theory, and Piagetian developmental psychology to illustrate the existing knowledge base surrounding identity formation. This evaluation will be considered in light of the scholarship on materiality with a view to assessing the merit of these approaches for entirely outdoor environments. I close Chapter Two by exploring implications on the basis of the existing literature for my research study.

¹ I also reject recent calls from a prominent private ECEC provider that the title of nursery ‘teacher’ should be adopted (Learner, 2017). Primarily, this is because teaching is a distinct career from ECEC and as such any conflation between the two is unhelpful. Secondly those working in ECEC are not paid anywhere near the same, referring to one’s staff team as nursery teachers, but only paying them according to first part of that title is a contradiction.

In Chapter Three, I respond to the questions that emerged from my examination of the literature in Chapter Two by advancing a sociomaterial approach toward understanding children's identity formation. I begin by introducing the metaphysics of Baruch Spinoza (2002) as a means to unsettle and complicate knowledges that foreground a predominantly Cartesian way of experiencing the world. I turn to Barad's (2003) conception of 'posthuman performativity', building on Spinoza's monism, to explain an alternative conception of agency, before introducing the roles of assemblages and affect. I will seek to examine how both are crucial to the aims of my thesis insofar as they enable a further departure point away from the conventional models of subjectivity in line with my sociomaterial proposal. I will demonstrate how assemblages mobilise more-than-human performativities that become stabilised (or not) through affects, where the more recognisable the latter are, the more affective they become. The latter parts of this chapter consider implications for space and time, where I evaluate capacities for resistance enabled by this approach in terms of privileging an openness to both the production of novelty and the not-yet-known. I end by drawing all of these threads together and examine what sociomaterialism *does* for reconfiguring subjectivity in response to the approaches outlined in Chapter Two.

In Chapter Four, I translate the argument for sociomaterialism in line with my research aims for this thesis. I begin with research design, including how I negotiated access to a nursery setting and how I managed the ethics process for gaining consent from parents, carers, and the children themselves. The second part of this chapter places my proposal alongside the tenets of traditional qualitative research, considering necessary departure points given my ontological commitments that partially situate this study with the 'postqualitative turn' (Lather and St. Pierre, 2013; St.Pierre, 2017; Koro-Ljungberg *et al.*, 2019). I introduce my approach toward a multi-sensory inquiry with a focus on the use of video as well as written field notes. I conclude Chapter Four with a final section on 'what's coming next', where I examine the role of textual, visual and cinematic present of ethnographic data through artistic practice. This section also describes my rationale for the production of a montage video through experimental film techniques (de Freitas, 2015).

In Chapter Five, I present Wood Fire nursery through a sociomaterial ethnography. I begin by introducing the setting and detailing distinctions from mainstream provision in terms of the space itself and the approach toward age-banding and daily routines. I also name the non-human inhabitants of this space that produced ethics of care in the children before detailing my processes of '**tuning in**' to Wood Fire through a sociomaterial sensibility. This chapter contains still imagery re-presented on more creative terms, which I then take further in Chapter Six where I introduce the video data. Chapter Six is the point that the reader is encouraged to view the video data,

following which an exposition is provided that details the techniques I draw on to experiment with cinematic presentation.

In Chapter Seven I present my concluding thoughts on the thesis I have undertaken in light of my fieldwork. This concluding chapter offers an initial recap of the thesis before I revisit my aims and discuss the extent to which they have been met. I also provide a section on implications of this study and consider some constraints. In the final part of this chapter, I look forward with regards to the direction that the ideas in the thesis may take in the future.

2 Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The purpose of Chapter Two is firstly to contextualise the research by introducing the Scottish context in which this study is positioned. I begin by situating early childhood in Scotland, providing contextual analysis and highlighting several key tensions in the implementation of a Curriculum for Excellence (CfE) (Education Scotland, 2019b). Secondly, my aims within this chapter are to explore the influence of neoliberalism within this national context. I intend to examine the extent to which neoliberal practices have contributed toward the hegemony of developmentalist logic, appending value (simply what is valued by the logic of the curriculum) to various modes of measurability, affecting how the child's subjectivity is conceived as a result. I then broaden my critique toward the socially determining processes of gender and sexuality. I consider the extent to which the CfE has been able to address inequalities on the basis of these social and cultural determinacies and, again, the implications of this for the child's subjectivity. In the following section I review the existing theoretical frameworks for understanding subjectivities. Namely, social constructionism, performativity theory and developmental psychology, each of which I shall evaluate in light of the more recent theoretical turn to materiality. I will consider how this area of scholarship may enable researchers to unsettle fundamental issues of individualism and anthropocentrism that, as I will examine, haunt the contemporary dominant perspectives. I end this chapter with several problematisations that will be explored in Chapter Three.

2.2 The early childhood landscape in Scotland

Following devolution powers introduced in 1998, early childhood, more commonly known as Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) in Scotland, is integrated in terms of overall ministerial responsibility, but with different sub-departments for education and for childcare services (OECD, 2015). While Scotland has devolved responsibility for the provision of ELC, some welfare and tax provisions, including child tax credits, child benefit, and maternity allowance, remain under control of the UK Government and UK Parliament. In the decade after devolution, Scotland moved from a centre-left coalition to a minority Scottish National Party (SNP) Government until 2011, when the SNP Government became the first majority government in this period for another decade. In 2021, since the party finished one seat short of a majority during the Scottish Parliament election, the SNP formed a power-sharing coalition with the Scottish Greens based upon an informal cooperation and confidence and supply agreement (Scottish Government and Scottish Green Party, 2021). While the SNP is typically perceived as a left-wing party, this difference is often exaggerated across public discourse (Curtice, Hudson and Montagu, 2020). They are arguably

much closer to the centre-left with reports showing that there is only a slight tendency for Scotland to be to the left on issues of social equality and redistribution (Keating, 2017; Cohen *et al.*, 2018). Though, as Massesti's (2018) analysis, based on party manifestos and interviews with party elected representatives, demonstrates, they have explicitly engaged with left-wing-populist narratives on anti-austerity at various points in the past decade, for instance during election periods and as part of their independence referendum campaign.

At the time of writing, it is too early to determine what sort of effect the Scottish Greens will have on Scottish politics and the ELC context in particular. While their election manifesto (Scottish Greens, 2021) was more far-reaching in ambition than the SNP's, insofar as it named intentions to end P1-S3 Scottish National Standardised Assessments, raise the school starting age to seven and introduce a kindergarten stage for three- to six-year-olds, it seems that few, if any of these promises have been kept through their agreement with the SNP. The absence of any mention of the ELC profession within the *Draft Shared Policy Programme* (Scottish Government and Scottish Green Party, 2021) is perhaps an early indication of the level of influence that they may have on such matters.

A number of strategies have been put forward since devolution by the Scottish Government for the ELC sector. The 'New Community Schools initiative' in 1998 sought to develop a multi-agency approach toward the development of 'full service' community schools (Scottish Executive, 1999). It was intended to provide a wider range of services from children's earliest years and deliver a more integrated approach towards early childhood with practitioners, teachers, social workers, community education workers and health professionals all forming a cohesive service. However, limited by decisions at a UK level, this failed to materialise and was subsequently replaced by plans for the CfE in 2004 (Cohen, 2013). Several factors led to the creation of this curriculum, notably a lack of cohesion and consistency across the previous curriculum and the contradictory ways in which it was being implemented across local authorities (Priestley, 2016). The CfE was implemented after several years of consultation in 2010 and covers children from three to eighteen years old. Central to the philosophy of the CfE is an orientation toward all children becoming 'successful learners', 'confident individuals', 'responsible citizens', and 'effective contributors'. These make up the "four capacities" of the curriculum, which I shall return to later on ([see page 26](#)) (Education Scotland, 2019b)

Whether the Scottish Government have achieved the intended level of cohesion and consistency is a contested point. While the CfE was generally viewed in positive regard at the time of its implementation, scholars have been quick to note concerns. Priestley and Humes (2010), for

instance, call into question the underlying philosophy of the curriculum. They argue that, in the way that the CfE is structured through outcomes organised into sequential levels, a resulting incoherence occurs through both epistemological and pragmatic contradictions. The CfE is found to lack any conceptual clarity when framed through curriculum analysis. Consequently, there are “tensions between convergent and divergent modes of learning, between teleological and open-ended conceptions of education, which may be unhelpful to the process of enactment in the classroom” (Priestley and Humes, 2010, p. 358).

Another key issue that has been raised is the parsing of ‘childcare’ particularly for under three-year-old children that is predominantly provided by the private sector, and preschool education for children from three years old that is primarily delivered by local authorities (Naumann *et al.*, 2013; Muth, 2018). The case for formally aligning childcare and preschool education has been made consistently as far back as 1974, when a report from the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 1974, p. i) concluded that:

It has become increasingly obvious from a variety of sources that it is no longer desirable, at a policy level, to maintain any degree of separation between planning for full day care and planning for pre-primary education.

Yet, there was initially no curriculum for children below three years *per se*. A separate document entitled *Pre-Birth to Three: Positive Outcomes for Scotland's Children and Families* (Learning and Teaching Scotland, 2010b) provided the guidance for those working with younger children. In an attempt to remedy this separation, the Scottish Government have published *Building the Ambition*, in 2014, and now an updated version of *Realising the Ambition*, in 2020. Both contain guidance for ELC practitioners who work with children from birth to five years old and set out how interactions and experiences can be delivered within caring and nurturing environments. In the period of little more than ten years, then, there have been three different guidance documents published for the early childhood profession while the core experiences and outcomes and benchmarks in a CfE Early Level (Education Scotland, 2017) have remained the same. While there is plainly a need to revisit guidance in light of new research, arguably the pace of change within the Scottish policy context is indicative of a lack of longer-term foresight which may be more beneficial in providing consistency for the profession. The Scottish Government (2012, p. 33) themselves have admitted to the challenges in trying to achieve greater cohesion, arguing that whilst they aspire for high-quality, flexible and integrated early learning, they do not have “all the levers” to achieve these goals.

Today, there remain several salient debates around ELC provision in Scotland.² In 2016, the Scottish Government (2016a) published their *Blueprint for 2020*, proposing to extend free early education from 600 hours to 1140 hours for all three- and four-year-olds and eligible two-year-olds. Funded provision, where costs are covered by the government, is available to all three- and four-year olds and eligible two-year olds. The latest statistics show that 98% of three- and four-year old children are registered to attend an ELC setting.³ The blueprint further outlines their strategy for increasing the size of the profession and improving qualifications. For comparison, this is already in place in England although restricted to children of working parents. On the surface, the Scottish Government's proposals to extend free early education appear progressive. Research has consistently advocated the value of high-quality ELC to enhance all-round development in children through extended provision (Siraj-Blatchford *et al.*, 2002). However, it should again be questioned whether this is early enough. McLean, Naumann and Koslowski's (2017) definition of the 'split system' is relevant here, where little publicly provided childcare is available for children between birth and three years old (childcare), and a more extensive system of public provision is available from three-years-old to school entry (early education). The *Blueprint for 2020* therefore appears indicative of a continued failure to integrate ELC provision for parents with children from birth to three years old, where the rigidity of institutional care still falls short of what is needed by parents in paid employment (Scottish Government Social Research, 2018). A related concern is the number of graduates working in the ELC profession, with the extension of provision requiring almost twice as many practitioners. The Blueprint pragmatically states that "an extra 435 graduates [will be] working directly with children will be in place by 2018". This goal was not achieved since the *Summary Statistics for Schools in Scotland* (National Statistics and Scottish Government, 2018) report showed an increase of just 229 graduates working in ELC with degrees relevant to early childhood, other than teachers. At the time of writing, the most recent data reveal that the number of *graduates* has increased further, however the number of FTE qualified *teachers* has decreased to 729 in 2020, down from 821 in 2018, and 921 in 2017 (National Statistics and Scottish Government, 2020). While a full analysis is outside the scope of this thesis, it cannot be in the interests of the Scottish Government to have decreasing numbers of teaching staff during a period of planned expansion.

² It is worth at least acknowledging the recent OCED review (2021) of a CfE here, if only justify its absence in my analysis. The omission of any scrutiny with regard to the early level beyond contextual information is disappointing and perhaps a reflection of OECD's priorities than the actual quality of this phase of education in Scotland.

³ Children in Scotland start school when they are aged between four and-a-half years old and five and- a-half years old, though deferral is possible subject to approval by the local education authority.

Finally, it is also concerning to read the Scottish Government's (2017a) proposals for 'creating a more diverse ELC workforce' where their consultation argues for improved pay and conditions to attract more men into the profession. It is suggested that by increasing the proportion of outdoor learning opportunities, more men will be drawn to working in early childhood:

Recruiting more males to the workforce will, in time, provide a virtuous cycle where boys will have more male role models influencing them in the early years and therefore will view a career in ELC more positively in the future. Our consultation suggests that improved pay and conditions in the sector will help to attract more men into careers in ELC and increasing the proportion of outdoor learning opportunities should do likewise.

(Scottish Government, 2017a, p. 15)

This claim is problematic for several reasons. Firstly, suggesting men will only come into the profession when pay and conditions increase is dismissive of the 96% of women in the profession who have historically had to deal with low income and poor working conditions (Roberts-Holmes and Moss, 2021, p. 81). The implicit suggestion within this consultation is that men require better conditions to work. The most recent research shows that, while those in the public sector ELC settings do receive the living wage, the majority of staff within private settings (around 80%) do not (Wane, 2019).⁴ A sounder logic would be that both pay and conditions need to be improved irrespective of engaging more men in early childhood, not because of them. Secondly, equating 'outdoor play' with men's involvement is an essentialist position on gender roles. The assumption is posited that all men should enjoy outdoor, and by extension physical, play. This re-enforces a rationalist and essentialist view of the gender completely free from the reality of men's experiences. When gender roles are perceived in this way, as natural, differences between groups are seen as justified and left unchallenged. The wider implications of this are that any arising inequalities are then seen as both inevitable and unavoidable. Hence, the openings for a more gender diverse pedagogy (Warin, 2018), and advocacy for *more men of all kinds* (Tembo, 2021b) in early childhood, beyond reductive conceptions, have been missed.

it is required that settings who adopt the 1140 hours model of provision will have to pay staff the Scottish Living Wage, which is 78p per hour more than the national minimum wage. This remains several thousand pounds less than entry level teachers, pointing toward wider issues with regard to the overall status of the profession that are outside the scope of this thesis.

2.3 Producing neoliberal subjects

Having outlined and explored some tensions within the Scottish Government's policy context, this section now aims to consider how children's identity is both understood and constructed within this context. Central to my forthcoming argument is a principal issue that I thus far have omitted in my initial contextualisation. That is, the unmistakable influence of neoliberal thought that has come to permeate all aspects of education over the past several decades (McCafferty, 2010; Giroux, 2014; Ball, 2015; Roberts-Holmes and Lee, 2019; Roberts-Holmes and Moss, 2021). I begin this section by considering the historical roots of neoliberalism, where I outline how economic rationales for education remain in place today as the norm in the CfE. From here, I examine the contradictory ways in which equalities are recognised as shaping how the child develops their sense of self and conclude on how well the Scottish Government is truly meeting their ambition for the country to be 'the best place for children to grow up' (The Scottish Government, 2018).

Early childhood environments and educational contexts as a whole have long been, and continue to be, closely entangled with the dominant social and cultural ideologies within any given society (Rose, 1999; Wolf, 2002). These institutions represent the consolidation of strategies of power through curriculum, policy, and other forms of control. Yet, romanticised notions of childhood as non-political sites continue to frame public discussions on how such environments are perceived within society (Robinson, 2013; Tsaliki, 2016). On this view, politics have no place in the nursery. This sentiment was expressed recently by a government Education Select Committee Chair MP in a Sunday Telegraph newspaper article on the topic of whether nursery practitioners should be allowed to speak with children about racial prejudice and discrimination (Hope, 2021). This article was one of many published around the same period that sought to spark controversy over not how, but whether or not children should be taught to be aware of equalities and their own identity characteristics (Mail on Sunday, 2021; Nachiappan, 2021). It came in light of new non-statutory guidance on how to promote inclusion and diversity in early childhood provision (Early Years Coalition, 2021). The Sunday Telegraph article in particular featured an interesting comment from Robert Halfon MP, the Chair of the House of Commons Education Select Committee:

This is just unacceptable. This dogma and doctrine is totally out of place... The whole purpose of children learning is to learn, not for some kind of political Soviet indoctrination session.

(Halfon, in Hope, 2021, para 15)

Halfon's comment initially reveals the reductive framing of equalities within the early childhood field, where the discursive framing continually prohibits any meaningful discussion beyond antagonistic tropes. This relates to the wider 'moral panics' (Smith, 2003; Rodwell, 2018) that have re-emerged in public discourse around the role of equality in education, primarily framed through the binary perspectives of 'left-wing' versus 'common sense' ideas about what children should be taught and made aware of. A second example of this would be the recent backlash over the inclusion of No Outsiders lessons (Moffat, 2017), part of a programme in the English curriculum which aims to teach children about characteristics protected by the Equality Act (including sexual orientation) (Parveen, 2019a; Parveen, 2019b). The accusation that practitioners are 'indoctrinating' their students has already been levelled at university lecturers (Turner, 2017) and school teachers (Forrest, 2020). In this context, one should not be surprised to witness this allegation levelled at early childhood practitioners. While there is little to no evidence in favour of this claim, Robert Halfon MP's sleight of hand in parsing 'learning' from 'politics' overlooks the fundamental knowledge that, from a social justice perspective, political motivations are already embedded into the foundations of learning practices (Freire, 2005). In positioning learning as neutral from politics, a majoritarian viewpoint is revealed which acts in the interests of maintaining the *status quo*. As I shall examine now, when one traces back to the historical purpose of education as it initially became entangled with the processes of capitalist expansion, the overlapping histories of education with politics are lucid.

Historically in the West, the theoretical purpose of education can be traced back to the early modernisation and human capital agenda of the 1960s and 1970s (Benavot, 1992; Rose, 1999; Wolf, 2002). As Benavot (1992) outlines in his analysis of the relation between education and economic growth during this period, the role of formal schooling was seen as crucial in developing the requisite skills and knowledge necessary for participation in the labour market. Greater provision of education was perceived as beneficial to national interests surrounding productivity and economic growth underpinned by increasing value being placed upon the alleged ideals of competition and individualism. It was the decline in popularity of Keynesian economics and the subsequent neo-liberal policies implemented by Margaret Thatcher which set the foundations in the British context.⁵ When the then Prime Minister took office, her stay was swiftly followed by a neoliberal agenda including tax cuts for the middle and upper economic classes, the dismantling of the welfare state, as well as deregulation and privatisation of public companies (Hall, 2011;

⁵ As Shilliam (2020, p. 2018) points out, Thatcher's political programme emerged within a much broader history enveloping racial and imperialist logics. The contribution of seemingly populist figures such as Enoch Powell, who gave the infamous "river of blood" speech, were in fact closely entangled with the underlying logics of the economic neoliberal project.

Connell and Dados, 2014). Schools in England were financially incentivised to opt out of Local Educational Authority involvement and several acts were introduced to provide parents/carers with greater choice as to where their child could attend (Evans, 1997; Fry, 2008). British society became intrinsically related to the now classical concept of ‘the market’ and ideas of ‘equal exchange’, according to *economic value*. Yet the notions of equal exchange and fair market value were long ago identified by Marx as one of the foundational myths of capitalism (Marx, Engels and Hobsbawm, 1998), nor was there any evidence during this period to show that increased educational provision promoted greater economic growth (Wolf, 2002). Wolf’s (2002) analysis is particularly salient as she identifies that the established belief in a direct relationship between the amount of educational provision within a society and its future growth rate is both incorrect and naïve. Yet as future analyses have since demonstrated, the epistemological belief that people can be seen in relation to their labour market value continues to hold considerable power in the twenty-first century (Lazzarato and Jordan, 2012; Massumi, 2018).

As Rose (1999) identifies, the relation between increasing intelligence tests for children during this period and the broader government agenda of maximising an individual’s social utility became intractable. Measurable attainment became the norm. In the early childhood context, these shifts amounted to the increasing influence of developmental psychology and the associated notion of the ‘developmental norm’. Particular behaviours and abilities deemed characteristic and distinctive of different age levels were defined and organised into scales with specifications of the ages as a means of codifying difference. As a result, “norms of posture and locomotion; of vocabulary, comprehension, and conversation; of personal habits, initiative, independence, and play could now be deployed in evaluation and diagnosis” (Rose, 1999, p. 152). Importantly, at this point there is a transition in how neoliberalism can be understood from merely an economic logic toward a more insidious order of reason in the production of subjectivity: as part of a ‘society of control’ (Deleuze, 1992b). Deleuze (1992b) established this term to signify a move past Michel Foucault’s (1995) theorisation of ‘disciplinary societies’ which remains an influential text for analysing how power works in society. In Foucault’s (1995) analysis, disciplinary societies constitute the period between from Industrial Revolution through to the end of the second world war, whereas Deleuze’s (1992b) paper on ‘societies of control’ examines how power relations have shifted from that period until the end of the twentieth century and would continue into the twenty-first. Fendler (2001, p. 137) summarises the distinctions between each according to three distinct aspects:

first, both discipline and control societies are characterized by the self-monitoring gaze; but in a control society the monitoring is more frequent and continuous ... Second, standards in a disciplinary society tend to be fairly centralized and long-lasting; however,

standards in a control society are more heterogeneous and quickly changing. Finally, a disciplinary society afforded the promise of closure or completion of a project; however, a control society offers no possibility of closure or completion.

Contemporary scholars have endorsed much of Deleuze's foresight in the thirty years since his article was published, pointing to the ways in which neoliberal politics extend the effects of power beyond closed spaces into all aspects of life (Parisi and Goodman, 2011; Brusseau, 2020; Thompson, 2020). This occurs primarily through modes of quantification that append difference to value according to economic logic. Subjectification, then, is less an outcome of strict disciplinary forces but rather a continuous process of control according to varying methods across one's lifetime, with little possibility of closure or completion (Fendler, 2001).

Many authors are also in harmony on the point that there have been salient global implications from the dominance of developmentalism (Wynter, 1996; Braidotti, 2013; Burman, 2016). Namely through its hegemonic status as fact, rather than as a historically specific mode of thought. From a Black studies perspective, Sylvia Wynter (1996) illustrates how the emergence of the logic of 'development' from the West has come to orient subjects in more and less equal ways at a global level. Development, perceived as an objective and merely denotive term, is in fact a historically-present legacy rooted in the Renaissance (and, subsequently, the Enlightenment) period of 'humanism' that served to legitimise colonial conquest. One classic historical example of this is the Renaissance image of the Vitruvian Man (Braidotti, 2013). Strengthening Wynter's contention, Braidotti (2013, p. 13) writes:

Leonardo da Vinci's Vitruvian Man (can be understood as) an ideal of bodily perfection which, in keeping with the classical dictum *mens sana in corpore sano* (trans: a rational mind in a healthy body), doubles up as a set of mental, discursive and spiritual values. Together they uphold a specific view of what is 'human' about humanity ... That iconic image is the emblem of Humanism as a doctrine that combines the biological, discursive and moral expansion of human capabilities into an idea of teleologically ordained, rational progress.

The surrounding epistemics of humanism, then, enabled a reference point from which the West could make universalist claims to rationality, effectively subordinating African countries as *underdeveloped*, as lacking, to maintain the political and economic interests of the West as 'developed' (Wynter, 1996). In the contemporary moment, the ideal 'normal' child and the logics of development remain obstinate. Curricula conceptions in the West, especially within early childhood, have become even more interlaced with the now near unfathomable processes of capital (McCafferty, 2010; Giroux, 2014; Priestley and Biesta, 2014; Roberts-Holmes and Moss,

2021). Increasing measurement of children’s developmental progress, often clouded within a discourse of ‘school-readiness’ have been identified as the Trojan horse by which the child continues to be valued according to normative models of development (Biesta, 2013; Lupton and Williamson, 2017; Bradbury, 2018; Apple, 2019).

The Scottish Government’s educational policy agenda, with expectations for children to become ‘successful’ learners; ‘confident’ individuals; ‘responsible’ citizens; and ‘effective’ contributors through their engagement with the curriculum, is perhaps an exemplary case in this regard. Outcomes for children in a CfE are specified through teaching content in the form of ‘Experiences and Outcomes’ and ‘Benchmarks’ (Education Scotland, 2017). The former sets out statements for practitioners about what learners need to know and be able to do to achieve a level across the curriculum areas (i.e., I know that being active is a healthy way to be.), whereas benchmarks are intended for the practitioner to know how to support them (i.e., ‘demonstrates different ways of being active, for example, energetic play’). As stated by Education Scotland (2017, p. 2), their purpose is to “make clear what learners need to know and be able to do to progress through the levels, and to support consistency in teachers' and other practitioners' professional judgements”. In this sense, a CfE curriculum is not particularly exceptional in comparison to other national curricular approaches across Europe and remains committed to a teleological pedagogy of childhood (Priestley and Humes, 2010). Through an outcomes-based approach, there is an expectation for children to become ‘successful’ learners; ‘confident’ individuals; ‘responsible’ citizens; and ‘effective’ contributors through their engagement with the curriculum. One might argue that early childhood has thus far remained distinct from these outcomes, however this claim perpetuates early childhood as an apolitical space and is easily dismissed when the relation between the early level and the broader intentions of the CfE is articulated in *Realising the Ambition* (2020, p.68, bold in original):

There are strong connections in this guidance about **respect, working with families** and the **importance of relationships**. These in turn link to the four capacities of Curriculum for Excellence so that children can become **confident individuals, effective contributors, successful learners, and responsible citizens**.

Through a discursive analytic, these generic statements of intent are regulatory functions that prefigure children as future workers, feeding into a broader narrative that has increasingly been built into curriculum theory across many contemporary capitalist societies in the West (Priestley and Biesta, 2014). Mechanisms such as testing, regulatory inspection, monitoring, audit, measurement (often of ‘productivity’ or via ‘performance indicators’), and comparative league

tables have all become integral features of education systems (Rose, 1999; Fendler, 2001; Biesta, 2013). The Scottish Government's implementation of standardised literacy and number testing for 7-year-olds in 2015, despite clear opposition on the basis that testing applies undue pressure on the child, is heavily reflective of this trend (BBC News, 2016; The Scotsman, 2018; Upstart, 2019). As Fendler (2001, p. 129, my emphasis) writes:

Curricular objectives serve as the mode of subjectification that constructs a flexible and responsive educated subject. When this mode of subjectification is put together with the educative substance of desire and the power relations of governmentality, then *the educated subject is one who freely disciplines the innermost aspects of the self* to comply with the developmental objectives of society in order to be educated.

Fendler's argument speaks to the crux of the issue — the integration of neoliberal thought into educational spaces, including within early childhood provision, has created a particular mode of subjectivity: the child positioned as *lack*. That is, lacking something and in need of subjectification. This is a fundamental feature of developmentalist discourses whereby institutions do all they can do to “tame children's desires; to predict, control, supervise, and evaluate them to predefined standards (Olsson, 2009, p. 141)”. Predetermined goals and standards, such as those in the CfE, therefore have a controlling function. They view the child as lacking the correct experiences and outcomes necessary to develop through schooling. Arguably, in the most recent *Realising the Ambition* (Education Scotland, 2020:23) document, there is a recognition that “development is not a race or an endurance contest”, acknowledging that children are not a homogenous group. Yet the guidance continues to privilege a linear model of progression for each individual child. In other words, the logic of development is still understood to matter *within* each child, if not between all children. This is also visible in their aesthetic use of the arrow to represent a clear causal trajectory of development which, as both Scholnick (2000) and Overton (1994) identify, has historically emphasised a precise form of development that privileges masculinist notions of order, sequence, progress, and irreversibility. Overall, the privileging of developmentalist, neoliberal truths is inherently problematic because it acts to foreclose alternative explanations and ideas about how children make sense of their worlds. As Pires (2014, p. 3) analogises:

[S]tating of a child that she is normal has for the adult the same function as a diagnosis, in that it inscribes the child within a certain set of parameters or standards according to which the child is supposed to behave, at once “eliminating” the unpredictable, as well as diminishing the possibility for dis-order.

What Pires articulates here is the epistemological foreclosure of potential and the habituation of particular modes of being (and becoming) as valued above others through standards of ‘normal’ development. Specified ways of what children ‘need to know’ (such as how to be ‘responsible’) and be ‘able to do’ (such as the ability ‘contribute effectively’ toward society) frame ideas of ‘what counts’ in education and in life as a whole, and also inform understandings of ourselves and the lifeworlds that we encounter. Noticing how ‘what counts’ is governed in the CfE through experiences and outcomes, and through the imperative for children to ‘achieve’ certain levels of development, enables a further critique of the curriculum’s disciplinary orientation (Manning, 2016). That is, the ‘neurotypical’ tendency that provide the grounds for this logic. Neurotypicality names “a central but generally unspoken identity politics, (which) frames our idea of which lives are worth living, and which lives are worth saving ... Neurotypicality tells us what is in our best interests, and we tend to accept it wholesale” (Manning, 2016, pp. 3-4). Insofar as educational curriculum shapes children’s identity formation, it does so in a way that excludes difference and radical expression.

2.4 Producing social subjects

It is against the neoliberal, and *ergo* neurotypical tendencies, of education in Scotland that I can now further examine implications for childhood and a wider range of aspects of the child’s social subjectivity. Recognising that, contra Robert Halfon MP’s earlier claim, learning practices are already caught up in political agendas through non-neutral, developmentalist conceptions of child development, my analysis now shifts in focus from the curriculum as the sole determinate factor of childhood subjectivities toward the related role of culture as shaping how children are able to be and become-otherwise. For Lugones (2007, p. 187) such issues are two sides of the same coin, constitutive of “the modern/colonial gender system”, whereby the overarching logic of classification (as developed or undeveloped subjects, as gendered and sexed subjects) reigns supreme. The forces of capital go hand in hand with the colonial and the neoliberal with the normative. This shift resonates with the broader logic of a Deleuzian (1992b) control society where the logics of neoliberalism now effect all forms of social production, not simply within a delineated space of enclosure.

This section will take as its case the Scottish Government’s latest interventions into challenging the normativity of heterosexuality and the gender binary, occurring both through the role of censorship and through a number of evident discursive contradictions throughout policy

guidance.⁶ I focus on these documents because thus far their ambit of inquiry has failed to consider the foreclosure of children's potential beyond gender and, to a much lesser extent, sexuality. For example, there remains little explicit naming of the effects of racism in determining children's capacities within the early childhood context, where attention has predominantly tended toward addressing this issue in schools or as subsumed within a set of eight wellbeing indicators, referred to as SHANARRI, within the Getting it right for every child (GIRFEC) approach (Scottish Government, 2021). My interest, as will become more evident in later chapters, is in all determinacies, or determinacy *per se*, that can limit the child's potential to be and become—otherwise from the fixity of identity.

To first examine how fixed social models of children's development have an effect on children's subjectivities in a CfE, Lee Edelman's (2004) concept of 'reproductive futurism' can be employed as a heuristic to understand how policy and curricula preserve a privileging of heteronormativity through shaping heterosexuality as desirable over non-heterosexual identities. Heteronormativity is a concept rooted in feminist and Q/queer theory used to critique the hegemonic status of heterosexual identity as a taken for granted, 'natural', and unquestionable norm and, thus, perpetuates inequality against LGBTQ+ people (Warner, 1993; Rich, 1993; Katz, 1995). It is an ongoing colonial logic (McClintock, 1995; Oyewumi, 1997; Nokizaru, 2015). In educational spaces, heteronormativity is visible both explicitly through homophobic name-calling or verbal and physical harassment of students who deviate from normatively gendered forms of sexuality. It also effects these environments in more subtle ways through any range of practices that position heterosexuality as more intelligible, desirable, and legitimate. In early childhood spaces specifically, this includes: how girls are subject to Westernised beauty standards in ways that boys are not (Blaise, 2005a); subtly homophobic attitudes by practitioners towards children when they display any behaviour that does not align with their assigned sex (Paechter, 2007:66; Soteyvik, Hammarén and Hellman, 2019), and the general routinisation of heterosexual romance as the norm in play activities and resources (Robinson, 2005; Gunn, 2008; DePalma and Atkinson, 2009; Gunn, 2011). Reproductive futurism names the recursive logic of political thought in epistemologically framing the terms of debate at the expense of certain bodies over others.

Within the Scottish curriculum, outcomes pertaining to how children learn about gender and sexuality are addressed within the curriculum section 'sexual health and sexuality' within the Health

⁶ I take the position that children are not born *as a priori* gendered or sexed subjects, but rather are prefigured or determined into these roles (Katz, 1995; Oyewumi, 1997; Mukherjee, 2016). This is not to deny children agency but rather to acknowledge that insofar as children perform their own gendered subjectivity, they do so within an already-present recursive system of order.

and Wellbeing (Personal and Social Education) area. Though as far as the benchmarks intend to relate to sexual health *and* sexualities, the former dominates the latter. My object of inquiry here is not on an emphasis on learning the correct names of body parts in reproductive terms. Rather it is, as others have identified (Robinson, 2005; Gunn, 2008), an *absence* of any explicit mention of gender and sexuality that reinforces the normativity of heterosexual identity. This then enacts a temporality of an already anticipated future; it is within the idealised nuclear family that the image of the child remains central to this compulsory narrative of reproductive futurism. That is, the heterosexual child figured as innocent yet constantly under siege, as if queerness marks a threat to the sacred image of the child producing a logic whereby “the sacralization of the Child thus necessitates the sacrifice of the queer” (Edelman, 2004, p. 28). As Robinson (2013, pp. 23, emphasis in original) argues, a smoothing over of the ways in which children experience and learn about gender and sexuality leaves them in a state of ignorance surrounding this topic and in fact perpetuates heteronormativity:

Censorship is significantly linked to Western ideals of childhood innocence and its intersection with the discourse of child development, constituting children as too young to deal emotionally and cognitively with concepts fundamental to narratives of struggle, survival and procreation. There is a prevailing perception that children should be sheltered from this knowledge for as long as possible in order to avoid any stress or trauma that might be associated with *premature* access to this information.

Reproductive futurism, through heteronormativity, perpetuates discrimination against children who deviate from idealised heterosexuality. To put this another way, the discursive smoothing over of knowledge relating to gender and sexualities operates as part of what has been identified as the ‘hidden curriculum’ in educational contexts (Kelly, 2004). Acknowledging the hidden curriculum, along with other salient conceptual heuristics, allows for a recognition of the ways in which fixed social models of children’s development influence children’s subjectivities.

Research demonstrates that a failure to address heteronormativity only perpetuates inequality against non-heterosexual children (Lough Dennell, Anderson and McDonnell, 2017). At the time of writing, the existing data reveal that in Scotland, 71% of LGBT young people experienced bullying in school on the grounds of their sexual orientation (Lough Dennell, Anderson and McDonnell, 2017). This is a rise from 69% in 2012 and 60% in 2007, and while the percentage of LGBT young people who think that Scotland is a good place to live has risen over the last decade, essentially the same amount believe that homophobia remains a problem for Scotland. In England and Wales, a report revealed that homophobic and transphobic hate crimes have more than doubled over the

past five years (Marsh, Mohdin and McIntyre, 2019). The latest hate crime statistics from the Crown Office & Procurator Fiscal Service (2019) reveal that the number of charges reported with an aggravation of prejudice relating to sexual orientation rose to 1,176 between 2018-19, 5% higher than in 2017-18. Once again, apart from a fall in 2014-15, the number of charges has increased consistently year on year since the legislation was introduced. There are caveats with the sample size, as with much quantitative data in general. Yet these caveats must be balanced against the difficulties of gathering data from minoritised people in the first place, where issues relating to inequalities are often under-reported or subsumed into broader categories of prejudice or discrimination (Pezzella, Fetzer and Keller, 2019; Lantz and Myers, 2020). Therefore, at a time where educational inequalities continue to exist, persist and may even be worsening, it is possible to argue that a continued failure to challenge heteronormativity, through an absence of recognising how children come to form their gendered and sexual subjectivities, will only perpetuate inequality and continue to privilege heterosexuality as the normative identity.

Outside a CfE, several guidance documents have been published with the intention of supporting children's gender identity, as well as challenging determinate norms and stereotypes. Closely related to heteronormativity, I interpret the process of gendering to be another instance whereby the child's subjectivity becomes socially determined according to prefigured, historically situated, norms (Colebrook, 2004; Lugones, 2007). In *Realising the Ambition* (2020: p. 41), it is explained that:

Children receive and absorb gender-stereotyped messages about what they can and cannot do according to their sex from a very early age ... These stereotypical views can shape their attitudes to relationships, participation in the world of work and affect their wellbeing.

This statement is supported by guidance documents such as *Improving Gender Balance* (Skills Development Scotland, 2019) and *Gender Equal Play* (2019), in addition to local authority initiatives promoting the *Gender Friendly Nursery* (2018). As well as these, the end of 2018 saw the Scottish Government announce plans to embed LGBTI inclusive education across their curriculum. The report put forward to the Scottish ministers by the LGBTI Inclusive Education Working Group, in conjunction with the Time for Inclusive Education (TIE) campaign, lays out 33 detailed recommendations to improve the educational experiences of LGBTI children and young people in Scotland. While on one hand the recognition of gender through these guidance documents should be welcomed, they are arguably more indicative of the fragmented nature of implementing a focus on equalities related to identity into ELC provision. More importantly, while these policies and guidance documents have been lauded, a close analytic reading suggests limitations in clarity and ultimate goals. My critique of these policies illustrates a salient concern; that projects fighting

for gender equality, while progressive to an extent, remain limited as far as elements of the language employed potentially de-radicalises what, in the broader context, feminism and social justice work is for. There is a concern that in seeking to challenge gender inequality, these policies may end up reproducing binary conceptions of gender and ultimately doing little to contribute toward true equality.

Firstly, with the *Improving Gender Balance* (Skills Development Scotland, 2019) guidance, ‘balance’ is employed as the operative goal for gender in educational contexts. However, the use of this term within the document is problematic. Etymologically, balance derives from bi-, which translates as ‘two’. ‘Gender balance’ therefore assumes a binary distinction where male and female roles remain distinct from each other, based on essentialist biological differences, a notion of complementarity, and pertaining to traditional nuclear familial roles (Warin, 2018). In other words, it maintains a heteronormative conception of childhood as separable into a homogenous binary, boys and girls, where achieving a balance is the end goal. In the *Gender Friendly Nursery* evaluation report (Heywood, 2018, p. 6), the role of male practitioners is uncritically linked to specifically boy’s development. The report initially states:

[the ECEC settings] were able to recognise the benefits of having males in the nursery environment. Some nurseries had experience of male students having their placement in the nursery and saw first-hand the impact this had on children.

The claim is further evidenced with feedback from a staff member who took part in the course, who writes “It was fantastic and you could see the boys that weren’t very expressive before and didn’t interact, come out of their shell and be a wee bit more comfortable” (*ibid*, p. 7). Again, while seemingly progressive, this is in fact again an essentialist understanding of gender which assumes that men are necessary to support the development of boys, and that boys in particular need male role models. This subjectifies women as lacking whatever is perceived as needed to support boys and presumes gender to be a fixed, monolithic and determinate identification which remains stable throughout one’s life (Butler, 1988; Butler, 2004). This, again, posits a determinate subjectivity with little room for diversity beyond the binary.

Even granting the perceived progress made with these policies, it remains salient to note that these policies are situated within a narrative of promoting gender equality and LGBTQ+ inclusivity, therefore doing little to challenge the more fundamental and compulsory nature of heteronormativity and reproductive futurism itself. The most recent *Gender Equal Play* guidance (Care Inspectorate; Zero Tolerance, 2019) is the best illustration of this and represents something of an opportunity lost. For instance, the terms ‘gender balance’, ‘gender equal’, ‘gender diverse’

and ‘gender neutral’ are used at various points entirely indiscriminately, with little further consideration on the implications of this. In Appendix Three of the document, there is an exemplar of a ‘gender equality policy’ from a Family Learning Centre in Glasgow. One of the statements reads that “All resources reflect a gender balance and are gender neutral”, indicating a lack of understanding as to what these terms actually mean: it suggests a discursive contradiction for a resource to reflect both balance *and* neutrality at the same time.

Another major theoretical issue is the omission of any meaningful discussion on children who may *already* be challenging the gender binary. Across all of the guidance documents I have discussed thus far, the epistemological framework in which the child is understood is that of an *a priori* gendered subject, such that the very possibility of any child trans-ing the gender binary is unintelligible. For instance, in *Gender Equal Play* (Care Inspectorate; Zero Tolerance, 2019), in the 53-page document there is one single mention of transgender children, who are rendered invisible within an already binary linguistic framework where the terms ‘boys’ and ‘girls’ are maintained in the traditional view. The absence of the trans child reveals the discursive limits of thought within the Scottish political context as inarticulable within the gender binary. Thus, these children are, as Gill-Peterson (2018, p. vii) makes plain, often “left to fend for themselves in a culture that suffers from being unable to imagine children with a richly expressive sense of who they are”. The inherent creativity of the child’s subjective self is therefore appended to a way of knowing that forecloses any possibility for trans children to thrive.

The purpose of this section has been to review and evaluate the ways in which the child’s subjectivity is shaped according to the Scottish Government’s interventions against heteronormativity and the gender binary. This matters because, as others have argued, the liberation of children who are deemed as failing to meet the heteronormative and gender standards placed upon them would unsettle the determinacies placed upon all children (Halberstam, 2018; Fournier, 2019; Faye, 2021). Yet, despite attempts to promote LGBTQ+ inclusive practice, my analysis has demonstrated how discourses of heteronormativity, in more and less explicit forms, continue to prefigure non-heterosexual identities as unintelligible through boundaries of censorship. Further, I have outlined tensions in the fragmented nature of implementation as visible through a number of contradictions in the language used throughout these guidance documents. For instance, through problematic beliefs on gender balance that do little to disrupt normative subjectivities within the gender binary. Therefore, my review indicates that the current efforts made by the Scottish Government to mitigate against prescriptive social and cultural determinacies are, at present, weak. This casts light on what might be done to understand how these identities come to form and, importantly, how they might be contested. In the next section, I review the

existing theoretical frameworks for understanding subjectivities and evaluate these in light of the more recent theoretical turn to materiality.

2.5 A review of theoretical frameworks for understanding subjectivities

The focus of the sections that I have explored thus far pose questions not only about which kind of theoretical framework might be employed to further understand how children come to form their identities in the Scottish context, but also how children's identities might be formed otherwise from the determinacies I have examined. To this end, different theories exist in the literature regarding the ways in which children's identities are formed. Predominantly, however, the question of subjectivity has been approached from the perspectives of social constructionism (Foucault, 1978; Foucault, 1980a; Foucault, 1980b), Judith Butler's (1993; 2004; 2006) performativity theory, and developmental psychology (Piaget, 1948; Piaget, 1957). On the former two, it is worth noting that there is little agreement on whether either Foucault or Butler linguistically advocate a theory of social *constructionism* or social *constructivism*. Some authors have referred to these terms as interchangeable (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p. 23; Rau, Elliker and Coetzee, 2018, p. 298). Some have referred to Butler as a constructionist (Weinstein and Colebrook, 2017, p. 78), and Foucault as a constructivist (Hirtle, 1996), whereas others have made the opposition association between the two (Coleman, 2009). Having reviewed these, I find Coleman's (2009, p.205) explanation most convincing insofar as she argues that:

While [Foucauldian] social constructionism understands bodies as constructed by the unequal power relations of sex and gender, Butler argues that bodies are materialised into intelligible subjects as sex and gender as *effects* of power. For social constructionists, bodies are constructed by sex and gender, but can be understood as in some way *prior* to sex and gender while, for Butler, bodies are only intelligible *through* sex and gender

Having said this, it must also be taken into account that constructivism is a term that for many educational scholars, including myself, is more readily attributed to the works of Lev Vygotsky and Jean Piaget (Smidt, 2006; File, Mueller and Wisneski, 2011). For these reasons, I will follow others (Barad, 2012a; Taylor, 2016a; Pitts-Taylor, 2016a) in referring to Butler's framework as 'performativity theory'. The intention in this section is therefore to outline the key distinct tenets of social constructionism and performativity theory and examine any resemblances or differences in their approach. From here I shall address the role of developmental psychology before assessing all three approaches in light of the emergent, materialist-orientated, scholarship. Since there is a vast amount of literature on the founding theorists of each approach, my attention in this section will focus primarily on the *interpretations* of these theories within the early childhood field as they

are understood and applied today. Jean Piaget, for instance, is said to have published more than more than 50 books and 500 papers across his lifetime. A full analysis of these texts would be well outside the capacity of this study and would not necessarily reflect how his theories are applied in the contemporary early childhood field. Overall, the purpose will be to establish justification for my own forthcoming research proposal with regards to how subjectivity might be reinterpreted and challenged on the basis of the existing scholarship.

2.5.1 *Social constructionism*

Michel Foucault's (1978; 1980a; 1980b) social constructionist approach examined how power circulated through society in the form of constructed discourses in the second part of the twentieth century. Foucault (1978) defines power as essentially self-reproducing and constitutive of norms and disciplinary subjects. Writing against the notion of the subject as an interiority, most notably in the psychoanalytic model for understanding the non-conscious espoused by Freud (1962; 2010), Foucault instead positioned the subject as a dynamic *exteriority*. That is, as Braidotti (1991, p. 61) explains, the subject constituted by:

the structures of the organisms, the bodily roots of the self; the insistence of language; the conditioning of the social order; the whole accumulated stock of human knowledge... it is this set of complex structures that constitutes the very heart of Foucault's notion of 'discourse' meant as one of the fundamental structures of the subject.

Discourses, then, are "not merely "groups of signs" but practices that systematically form the objects of which they speak" (Foucault, 2002, p. 54). As Weedon (1987, p. 108) further explains, they are "ways of constituting knowledge, together with the social practices, forms of subjectivity and power relations which inhere in such knowledges and the relations between them". Our gender or sexual identities, for instance, are not fixed, or given. Rather, they are best understood as an effect of power in relation to the person and their social world. Certain relations, structures and processes therefore produce positions of power within the world that can force, constrain, shape, as well as coerce and potentiate individual action. In this sense, to refer to a person as 'heterosexual' itself produces an often-unacknowledged discursive power relation that works to structure reality. Viewing society as constantly disciplined through discursive practices allows for an understanding of the power mechanisms within such practices, reconceptualising power itself as an unstable and dispersed phenomenon, rather than a singular, centrally located, force.

Importantly, according to Foucault, if identity formation is constructed by power relations, rather than fixed in nature, this opens up the possibility to question to what extent it can be changed. "Discourse transmits and produces power; it reinforces it but it also undermines and exposes it,

renders it fragile and makes it possible to thwart it” (Foucault, 1978, p. 101). This insight, and Foucault’s broader epistemological approach toward subjectivity has informed a plethora of research within the early childhood studies field (Naughton, 2005; Robinson and Diaz, 2006; Martin, 2011; Moore and Reynolds, 2018; Flear and Oers, 2018). Writing in relation to children’s (sexual) identities, Kerry Robinson (2013, p. 87) offers a lucid conceptual argument for social constructionism:

[F]rom an early age, children have a strong sense of desire, wish to act on that desire, and are actively engaged in constructing their sexual subjectivities... Young children try to critically make sense of and sort through the bits and pieces of information they receive about sexuality. Children actively engage in making meanings about sexuality in their early lives based on this limited information (which is often misinformation, stereotypes or myths). They receive this information from families, peers, television, the Internet and through their daily experiences, especially of observing others – older children, young people or adults, and pets and other animals.

I cite at length here since Robinson’s argument, that children are actively engaged in their own meaning making, makes a number of important claims. Firstly, it is an epistemic claim to the primacy of human agency, for it is the *children* who have a strong sense of desire. This is a key point that I will return to at the end of this chapter. Robinson also makes the claim that children are constructed *by* the workings of power: that they are socially inscribed within a power structure that overlays unequal discourses of power relations. This argument is possible on the premise that power is social, and children are constructed through social discourses. It is primarily language that functions as a form of social control and constructs reality, therefore the primary goal of social constructionist scholarship has been to deconstruct words, phrases and ideas for the purposes of understanding how normative discourses, such as sexuality and gender, are constitutive of certain identities (Foucault, 2004).

2.5.2 *Performativity theory*

Whereas in a social constructionist approach, bodies are understood as constructed *by* the workings of power, Judith Butler’s (2004) performativity theory treats bodies not as constructed but *materialised through* power. This can be read as an attempt to reinstate the *matter* of bodies, not as a passive things onto which gender is mapped, but rather as themselves socially constructed. In her own words on the materiality of sex, Butler (2004, p. 94) questions:

If sex is experienced by us within a cultural matrix of meanings, if it comes to have its significance and meaning in reference to a wider social world, then can we separate the

experience of “sex” from its social meanings, including the way in which power functions throughout those meanings?

Butler proposed the ‘heterosexual matrix’ as a conceptual framework to consider sex itself as constructed and materialised through time. This happens through what they are most well regarded for, her conceptualisation of ‘gender performativity’ (Butler, 1993). Performativity does not simply mean a performance of gender in a superfluous sense but refers to “the reiterative and citational practice by which discourse produces the effects that it names” (ibid, p. 2). Here, performances of the self are bounded discursive practices that are consistently repeated through primarily speech acts, rather than being a universal condition of one’s identity. In this sense, Butler’s theory is theoretically aligned with that of Foucault, however distinguishable insofar as she seeks to materialise matter. This distinction allows Butler to posit gender as something that is ‘done’ *through* certain power relations. The heterosexual matrix is also intelligible through normatively gendered performances, with those people, including children, existing outside the matrix working as threatening ‘spectres’ of failed gender. Perhaps central to Butler’s (2004) conception is the claim that epistemology can stand in for ontology, a second crucial point that I will explore in further depth toward the end of this chapter (and in Chapter Three). As the application of both social constructionism and performativity theory into early childhood reveals, children’s subjectivities are socially produced according to particular meanings, beliefs, and rules about how they should be and who they can become. For instance, how ‘proper’ girls or boys should behave with respect to the determinate norms of compulsory heterosexuality and the gender binary (Blaise, 2005b; Robinson, 2005; Folgero, 2008; Gunn, 2011; Ericsson, 2012; Robinson, 2013; Gansen, 2017). Much of this knowledge underpins the contemporary policy guidance that I discussed in the previous section and has proved valuable in enabling an understanding of how determinate forms of identity might be refused. However, it has also been identified that these perspectives also privilege a particular perspective on agency that may limit capacities for resistance against subjectification, another point I will return to (Barad, 2007).

2.5.3 *Piagetian developmental psychology*

Earlier on in this chapter, in the section on ‘producing neoliberal subjects’, I examined how proponents of developmental psychology produced standards of measurable attainment as part of the broader trend toward developmentalism in early childhood. Though, as Burman (2016) identifies, it would be incorrect to interpret this as solely a historical issue, for developmental psychology, informed through the insights of Piaget, continues to hold considerable sway over the ways in which the formation of children’s identity is understood today. The influence of this perspective often works as a taken-for-granted expectation that invisibly shapes certain ideas about

children and childhood (Burman, 2016). Since I have already outlined a critique of developmentalism, this section will explore a second, though not unrelated, core theme of this perspective: the key roles ascribed to individual cognition and the individual self in shaping subjectivity.

The focus on cognitive development in the field of developmental psychology may be understood as concerned with individual development in terms of neurological and chemical processes within the human central nervous system, composed primarily of the brain (Watson and Coulter, 2008). The individual as the point of reference relates to a wider disposition among many, although not all, proponents of developmental psychology to taper social phenomena (as is the focus in social constructionist and performativity theory perspectives) to individual properties or attributes of the mind (Piaget, 1970; Walkerdine, 1998; Walkerdine, 2015; Burman, 2016; Shaffer *et al.*, 2020). This is expressed most clearly in the position taken by psychologist Jean Piaget (1971), whose insights into development have been foundational to dominant perspectives on ‘child-centredness’. On the broad influence of Piaget across various disciplines, Burman (2016, p. 235) suggests that “few nurses, social workers, counsellors or teachers (as well as psychologists) will complete their training without learning about Piaget’s stage model of cognitive development” One might reasonably add early childhood practitioners to this list, given the way in which he is regularly labelled as a ‘pioneer’ in leading early childhood media (David, 2006; Martin, 2021) and also due to the axiomatic maxim of ‘ages and stages’ of childhood development across various curriculum models (File, Mueller and Wisneski, 2011; The Scottish Government, 2014; Cameron and Moss, 2020, p. 108).

Piaget, originally a biologist, proposed that children’s knowledge passes through a series of stages which causes them to think and reason in particular ways at different ages from birth. His theory of genetic epistemology privileges a logic of ‘continuous construction’:

For the genetic epistemologist, knowledge results from continuous construction, since in each act of understanding, some degree of invention is involved; in development, the passage from one stage to the next is always characterised by the formation of new structures which did not exist before, either in the external world or in the subject’s mind.

(Piaget, 1970, p. 77)

His theory of the self, then, posits that a continuous process occurs within the individual throughout their formative years. Piaget (1948; 1957) argues in his early writings that from birth babies are ‘egocentric’ not because they consider themselves the centre of the world but because he believed that they were not aware of the differences between themselves and the rest of the

world. As Kesselring and Müller (2011) suggest, this argument has been largely overlooked by scholars who are dismissive of Piaget's theoretical position on the basis of extending a Cartesian worldview of a binary distinction between the internal self and the outer world. Piaget's conception here actually posits an initial *adualism* which was informed by his interests in autistic thought processes. However, he ultimately believed that babies would eventually develop beyond this stage toward 'logical or scientific' thought as their intelligence grew (Harris, 1993; Burman, 2016, p. 191). Burman (2016) further explains how Piaget considered that during this egocentric stage the child is essentially asocial insofar as they were not yet adapted to a communicative context. This critique was levelled most strongly by Lev Vygotsky (2012) who, in contrast, saw individual development as fundamentally mediated by social and cultural interactions, although still at the level of the human.

There are several criticisms that can be levelled against Piaget's mode of development. Firstly, his epistemic distinction between autistic and rational thought is problematic. That he saw autistic thought as a primitive phase from which all children would grow out of, as a phase separate from 'reality' aligns with a heavily neurotypical and ableist perception of human development whereby the logic of rationality takes precedence over alternative modes of thought (Campbell, 2009; Manning, 2020). Secondly, Piaget's reductive presentation of autistic people as asocial also warrants concern. In Yergeau's (2010) paper on representations of autism in academic writing, they point to a conflation within relevant scholarship between egocentrism and autism on the basis of neurological differences, while failing to account for the *social* norms that perpetuate that difference. The connection between autism and a developmental incapacity to engage in social relations, usually assessed through verbal speech, is therefore a neurotypical trope that assumes a particular way of being human. Yet Piaget conflates a lack of social reciprocity with autism and therefore pathologises it as such. Finally, as touched on above, Piaget's theory was premised on an implicitly individualised idea about children's knowledge as residing within the individual child, which was then actualised between children and their environment (Huf and Kluge, 2021). Hence, this evaluation of Piagetian developmental psychology reveals certain limitations in adopting this perspective for understanding the formation of subjectivity. However, there is a plausibly more salient concern underlining *all three approaches* I have explored that I will now examine.

2.6 A critique of theoretical frameworks for understanding subjectivities

While social constructionism, performativity theory and developmental psychology have all contributed in different ways toward questioning how the child comes to form their sense of self, all three do so on the basis of foregrounding *epistemological* concerns and give primacy to the human over and above the non-human world. This is visible in the earlier quote shared by Robinson

(2013), through Butler's (2004) claim that epistemology can stand in for ontology and finally through the emphasis given to individual cognition in developmental psychology (Piaget, 1970). In recent years, however, there has been a resurgence of scholarship seeking to understand how ontological, non-human, forces may shape the ways in which subjectivity is understood (Fox and Alldred, 2017; Dolphijn and Tuin, 2012; Barad, 2007; Braidotti, 2013). For these writers, the argument that subjectivity is primarily social or located within the human body alone has significant implications for how resistance might be possible against determinate ways of being. This is because, it is argued, these perspectives remain rooted within a Cartesian worldview and the philosophy of 'humanism' (Braidotti, 2013). My critique now shifts toward the dominant strand running through Western philosophical thought, in particular the writing of René Descartes (1985a; 1985b), who continued a mode of reasoning traceable back to Aristotle and Plato, that I argue remains present in current conceptions of subjectivity within early childhood through these three perspectives.

The formation of the individual subject is most clearly attributed to the philosophical position outlined by Descartes (1985a; 1985b), an Enlightenment era philosopher situated within a philosophy of humanism during a period when the reigning influence of the Church was in decline (Whitehead, 1948). Replacing Christian God, Descartes' theory of knowledge positions the thinking human self as the authoriser of experience. Precisely, it is the mind which is posited as more important than, and in control of, the body. Thus, goes the oft-cited maxim: 'I think therefore I am' (originally, "I am thinking, therefore I exist" (Descartes, 1985a, p. 127)). It is the human individual who is granted ontological privilege in experiences, such that experiences are *given* to human subjects who act from a foundational ground. One on view, Descartes' position may be read as serving in the interests of maintaining theological fidelities through a belief in free will. As Goudriaan (2016) explains, his beliefs on the relation between philosophy and theology as separate disciplines were contradictory, expressing both a belief in their separation while also acknowledging that a complete distinction was perhaps impossible. In this sense, Descartes can be said to have developed philosophical theology that seeks to prove the existence of God on metaphysical terms. Nevertheless, Descartes metaphysics has salient consequences for how the human relation to the non-human world has since been understood. As Gatens (2009, p. 30) explains, "if mind is superior to matter, and if - as [Descartes'] theory of knowledge demands - there is nothing mind like in the material world, that world becomes inferior to the mind that knows it". There are two implications here. Firstly, an ontological dualism is consequently established between mind and body, as well as nature and culture. Secondly, Descartes' epistemological claim to the *cogito* and the production of knowledge as emergent through an

internal monologue with one's own mind is a rationale rooted in solipsism (Rorty, 1979). This is the position that it is only the self that exists and that all that a person knows is the content of one's mind, such that the subject is essential to being and knowledge. As a result, Descartes' philosophy implies that any reality that would either be anterior or posterior to human beings is an impossibility.

As Whitehead (1948) quips, if a philosophical outlook is judged on popularity, then it is certain that no other theory has ever come close since any person first sought to understand the nature of human experience. St.Pierre (2020) argues that Descartes' position has come to represent an imperceptible truth across the humanities field of scholarship. It would, additionally, be a significant mistake to ignore the wider social context in which this metaphysical approach emanated. In his text on the structure of knowledge in the West, Grosfoguel (2013) deploys the term 'epistemic privilege' to consider the hegemony of philosophical thought as it has emerged out of several key historical moments during the long 16th century (the two hundred years between 1450-1600). These include the genocides and epistemicides of the Jewish and Muslim populations through the conquest of Al-Andalus (now Andalucía); of the indigenous peoples in the Americas by Christopher Columbus; of African people who were then forcibly brought to America as part of slavery; and finally of Indo-European women during this period who were considered 'witches' (Federici, 2004). Grosfoguel (2013, p. 86) argues that these events produced the epistemic circumstances meaning that in the 17th century when Descartes first expressed the phrase 'I think therefore I am', the "I" could not possibly have been "an African, an indigenous person, a Muslim, a Jew nor a woman (Western or non-Western)". None of these subjects were considered within the deeply colonial framework of Descartes logic, thus perpetuating the hegemonic status of Western philosophy.

It must also be noted that the anthropocentric separation of nature from culture is not a universal way of knowing. Mignolo (2012) points to the fact that the indigenous peoples of Aymaras and Quechuas in South America made no distinction between nature and culture prior to colonial revolution during the long 16th century. They saw themselves *in* it, not separated *from* it, such that 'culture was nature, and nature was (and is) culture'. However, in the wake of the colonial rule, Western Christians sought to establish their control over knowledge about nature by disregarding any knowledges that ran counter to their own understanding. The subsequent Industrial Revolution (only possible because of colonialism) redefined nature to refer to the physical non-human world to the extent that nature became a "repository of objectified, neutralized, and largely inert materiality that existed for the fulfilment of the economic goals of the "masters" of the materials" (Mignolo, 2012, p. 13).

As Descartes relates to the question of subjectivity, while social constructionism, performativity theory and developmental psychology models do not entirely disavow the body or the material world, the primacy given to discourse, human performativity and cognition effectively subordinates non-human objects and material into second place (Alaimo and Hekman, 2008; Pitts-Taylor, 2016b; Fox and Alldred, 2019). These approaches remain popular; however an increasing body of scholarship is turning the 'new materialisms' to unsettle the dominant epistemological and ontological paradigms underpinning previous research (Barad, 2007; Dolphijn and Tuin, 2012; Braidotti, 2013). This body of scholarship, it is argued, represents novel ways of contributing new knowledges to a field where an epistemic privileging of the social sciences has arguably restricted power's productivity to the domain of culture, overlooking an understanding of the *material* nature of power as relational (Barad, 2007). This has implications for how subjectivity may be fundamentally re-interpreted and represents an effort to address build upon the poststructuralist privileging of culture through resituating ontological and ontogenetic concerns.

Indeed, in the Scottish context in which this study is situated, a focus on materiality may prove generative given the increasing attention that has been paid toward non-human environments across various policy texts in the past several years, discussed next. More broadly, in the period during which this thesis is written, children's relationship to the educational spaces that they inhabit has become a primary site of concern both within public and academic discourse. As others have noted, Covid-19 has cast a shadow over the ways in which humans encounter and move within spaces and has further highlighted the significance of non-human material environments in everyday human lives (Chen, 2021). This next section will address the outdoor play context with a view to examining how a focus on materiality in the formation of identity might enable new knowledges on the formation of subjectivity within the early childhood field.

2.7 Outdoor Play

While long integrated into early childhood provision across several countries in Europe, the movement toward an emphasis on the value of outdoor play in Scotland has only emerged in the past decade and is underpinned by a number of factors. This includes ideas about children's access to ELC provision, children's wellbeing, and children's health. From an economic perspective, the prominence accorded to outdoor play reflects the Scottish Government's ambitions to extend their childcare offer in light of the increasing free ELC entitlement. In their own words, it is "cost-effective in meeting the expansion of funded childcare" (Scottish Government, 2020a, p. 6). Fundamentally, then, encouraging the use of outdoor environments might be said to be about

increasing the capacity of the physical space available to meet the increasing demand. In addition, the economic case for outdoor play relates to influence of neoliberal thought on the CfE in this context, it is perhaps unsurprising that outdoor play continues to be interpreted in line with a neoliberalising model for education. For instance, when it is written that “(Outdoor) experiences, from early years to adulthood, will help our children and young people to enter *education, employment or training with transferable skills required to meet the opportunities and challenges of a rapidly changing world*” (Learning and Teaching Scotland, 2010a, p. 22). Yet it is entirely unclear how this is the case.

The Scottish Government does not make the economic arguments central to their case for outdoor play. The wider public anxieties around the status of childhood itself, coming against the backdrop of claims that digital technologies are ‘eroding children’s ability to think, learn and behave’ appear to have provided the perfect Trojan horse for the Scottish Government to implement their proposed expansion. Such claims are central to Sue Palmer’s (2015) argument in her book entitled: *Toxic Childhood: How The Modern World Is Damaging Our Children And What We Can Do About It*. Palmer’s book, which has been widely celebrated within the media and is noted as an ‘influential’ text in the Care Inspectorate’s decision to make outdoor play an integral part of their ELC expansion (Mathias, 2018), best reflects the broader cultural anxieties of the current moment:

One major side effect of the technological revolution has been, for many children, the replacement of age-old play activities (running, climbing, pretending, making, sharing) with a solitary, sedentary screen-based lifestyle. This is an alarming development. TV, computer games and the Internet have many merits, and our lives would be much the poorer without them, but they aren’t a substitute for real life – and if children are to develop healthily in mind and body, neither are they a substitute for real play.

(Palmer, 2015, p. 49)

While Palmer’s overall argument tends toward a necessarily complicated and balanced case for outdoor play against the effects of the modern world, at times her distinction between digital technologies and the ‘real world’ inevitably portrays a romantic, ‘good old days’, vision of outdoor play environments as free from cultural influence. A discursive slippage is also visible between the terms ‘outdoors’ and ‘natural’. Yet, as the fields of feminist Science and Technology Studies long ago revealed, what counts as the ‘real world’ is always-already a politically laden claim (Haraway, 1990). As I will consider in further depth in Chapter Three, there is an emergent body of scholarship suggesting that not only is such a distinction incorrect, insofar as nature and culture is already co-constitutive and entangled, but that to maintain this separation is in fact undesirable (Haraway, 1990; Barad, 2003; Kirby, 2017). Nevertheless, as noted in the Care Inspectorate’s

rationale for expansion (Mathias, 2018), Palmer's case for greater outdoor play provision has been taken seriously. These concerns, along with the opportunities that outdoor play could provide in terms of greater space (and therefore greater capacity for children), and the numerous 'life-enhancing' benefits for children that such environments can provide, have all contributed toward the Scottish Government integrating outdoor play as central to their commitment for childhood.

The enhanced policy focus on outdoor play environments in Scotland, then, necessitates a need to examine how children might come to form their identities within these spaces. This is further complicated since, as Kraftl (2013) notes, such settings tend to hold particular values that directly contradict the neoliberalising tendencies of conventional nursery environments. These values may be visible through an explicit pedagogical approach toward the non-human environment or an emphasis on wider ecological concerns. Therefore for research inquiry into subjectivities, while scholars writing through social constructionist and performativity theory perspectives might attribute agency primarily to the individual child, there is an argument that this underplays the significance of the material environment and perpetuates a human-centric perspective of the world (Hultman and Taguchi, 2010). This position is in fact already evident within *Realising the Ambition* (2020:15), where the primacy of the human over the non-human world is visible in their second aspect of development:

We often talk about the environment in terms of physical spaces, but the key part of the environment for children is the human, social environment of positive nurturing interactions.

That this pedagogical focus on the environment pays less attention to a discussion of physical spaces in favour of the 'human, social environment' is an implicit sleight rooted in a Cartesian metaphysical presumption. The material environment is treated as subordinate to children who are deemed as the masters of their environment. Elsewhere within the document, there is a little consistency regarding the purpose of materials, such as in these two statements:

Materials should be open ended to develop children's creativity.

(*Ibid*:50)

As pedagogical leaders we should know the purpose and possibilities of the materials we provide outdoors and indoors.

(*Ibid*:54)

In these above lines, there is a direct contradiction in the expectation that practitioners provide open-ended materials at the same time as having to know their purpose and possibilities. Elsewhere, it is written that:

It is good to know that the children are enjoying playing with the mud kitchen, but it is much more useful to notice the extent to which a child is curiously and creatively exploring how textures change when materials are mixed together.

(*Ibid:* 66)

If children are curious about how textures change when materials are mixed together, then practitioners will be able to provide new materials and sensitive adult support to enable children to find out more about *how materials behave*.

(*Ibid:* 67, my emphasis)

The initial statement above applies a developmentalist logic to the use of mud kitchens in children's play, disregarding their autotelic pleasure (It is good to know that the children are enjoying playing with the mud kitchen) in favour of mastery (it is much more useful to notice the extent to which a child is curiously and creatively exploring how textures change when materials are mixed together), thus foreclosing organic creativity in favour of specified knowledges. In the final statement, the very notion that materials 'behave' again asserts an anthropocentric worldview where we, humans, are in control of the world around us. The overall approach toward materiality is therefore one that establishes a binary between humans and their non-human world in much the same way as the social constructionist, performativity theory and developmental psychology perspectives.

Yet, contra *Realising the Ambition* (2020), scholarship on materiality is now beginning to re-evaluate the philosophical commitments underlying the existing research into how children come to form their identities (Lenz Taguchi, 2010; Renold and Mellor, 2013; Rautio, 2014; Lyttleton-Smith, 2015; Osgood and Robinson, 2019; MacRae, 2020). On this view, the Cartesian legacy of viewing the material world and the individual self as disjunctive overlooks the complicated relational and ontogenetic entanglements happening between them. Instead, the 'new materialist' wave challenges this conception and posits an approach that challenges the logics of the child (as an 'individual') and their relation to the material environment (as one that maintains a position of anthropocentric humanism). For instance, Lyttleton-Smith's (2017) research adopts this perspective within a conventional nursery setting to examine how the materiality of the

environment itself is productive and contributory toward gender norms among boys and girls. Contrasting the home corner and small world areas, she writes that:

The home corner and the small world were two of the most-used areas of the classroom and were significantly different in terms of their spatial and material features ... The small world was effectively a public space. It was visible from most areas of the classroom, its lack of furniture creating a spacious open area with nothing to hide behind ... (in contrast) the enclave of the home corner ensured that one was much less likely to be disturbed by other children or regulated by teachers than in other areas of the class-room ... the result of this was that violent conflicts tended to occur more in the home corner.

(Lyttleton-Smith, 2017, pp. 7-8)

Rather than a sole focus on the children, Lyttleton-Smith's analysis demonstrates how the materials and spaces themselves are policed in distinct ways that can be (re)productive of particular gendered behaviours. This points toward an argument for agency as less individualised than in conventional perspectives and more relationally distributed within social *and* material encounters. Other studies have produced similar findings (Lenz Taguchi, 2010; Renold and Mellor, 2013; Rautio, 2014; Osgood and Robinson, 2019; MacRae, 2020), demonstrating the value of an emphasis on materiality in shaping subjectivities. Though how children come to form their identities in relation to the material environment, when that environment is stripped of any conventional 'home corner' or 'construction area', raises questions about whether and how broader social identities might shape children's subjectivities in the same way. Furthermore, this line of inquiry may have implications for how human subjectivity can be understood within the conditions of the Anthropocene in challenging human exceptionalism and producing more ethical subjectivities that unsettle received notions of mastery (Kraftl, Taylor and Pacini-Ketchabaw, 2020; Ingold, 2000).

Within specifically outdoor environments, research is beginning to demonstrate how children's relation to their material environment might illustrate different ways of knowing about subjectivity where the individual is dislodged as the sole agential actor (Kraftl, 2014; McPhie and Clarke, 2015; Jarvis, Kraftl and Dickie, 2017; Taylor, 2017; Vladimirova, 2021). These are informed theoretically from various different strands of scholarship including the human geographies (Massey, 2005), feminist Science and Technology Studies (Haraway, 1987; Haraway, 1988), and quantum physics (Barad, 2007). These studies suggest that, given the often novel and unique nature of these spaces, reconsidering subjectivity with a materialist focus may prove to be a fruitful avenue of inquiry in entirely outdoor environments. However thus far few studies have considered whether, and if so how, socially determinate forms of identity might be produced in entirely outdoor environments

in the absence of clearly coded spaces. Certainly, no research on these terms has taken place within the Scottish ELC context, indicating a gap in the knowledge base that compels further inquiry.

2.8 Closing

In line with my research aims, this chapter has begun to demonstrate how children's identities are continually determined according to norms that shape who they may be and who they may become. Exploring how these might be challenged, I have considered the dominant theoretical perspectives within the literature that enable a further understanding around how children come to form their identities in more and less equal ways. My review has demonstrated limitations within each in perpetuating anthropocentric and Cartesian ways of knowing. Questions therefore arise as to how it might be possible to challenge the underlying ways of thinking that have enabled these humanist constructions of subjectivity, and what it might look like to take seriously the idea that human agency cannot be considered as separate from materiality. I have identified how a concomitant focus on the non-human, material, world may prove generative in expanding the ambit of inquiry beyond anthropocentrism. In the Scottish context, where an increasing emphasis has been placed on outdoor play spaces, there remains a need to consider how children come to form their subjectivities within these often highly unique material environments. Chapter Three examines how children's subjectivities might understand from a more ontological line of inquiry and the implications of such an approach for challenging conventional understandings of agency.

3 Chapter Three: Producing a sociomaterial framework for understanding subjectivities

3.1 Introduction

Questions about the material nature of discursive practices seem to hang in the air like the persistent smile of the Cheshire cat.

(Barad, 2007, p. 64)

Building on the justification for this research informed by the literature identified within Chapter Two, in this chapter I look forward toward developing a sociomaterial proposal for understanding how children might alternatively come to form their identities. I examine how I may go about challenging the underlying modes of thought that have enabled the distinctly humanist constructions of subjectivity in line with materialist-oriented scholarship that I have initially identified. This is not, however, to entirely reject the merit of previous perspectives. This is an *unsettling* of things. It is not a complete dismissal. I recognise that approaches toward how children's identities are in-formed in early childhood spaces that maintain a Cartesian logic have significantly enhanced knowledges about the formation of children's subjectivities. As discussed, many of these studies have made clear that children are socialised to understand rules, beliefs, meanings, and specific codes of conduct associated with determinate modes of being *and* becoming. For instance, how 'proper' girls or boys should behave with respect to the determinate norms of compulsory heterosexuality and the gender binary (Blaise, 2005b; Robinson, 2005; Folgero, 2008; Gunn, 2011; Ericsson, 2012; Robinson, 2013; Gansen, 2017). These knowledges remain essential for the project of dismantling and refusing determinate forms of identity. Yet the lingering smile of the Cheshire cat, as the above epigram suggests, remains firmly in place.

This chapter deals with the metaphysical framework for the sociomaterial approach I intend to advance informed from my argument in Chapter Two. My approach toward sociomaterialism concerns itself with the nature of human and non-human existence and, in a wider sense, how research inquiry might understand what constitutes the experience of *life itself*. I examine how it may figure as a way of contributing new knowledges to a field where a privileging of epistemological concerns within the social sciences has restrained the potential for change against operations of power to the domain of culture, therefore overlooking an understanding of its

material and thoroughly relational nature (Barad, 2007). The (re)turn to the material represents an effort to address the shortcomings of, and build upon, the Cartesian legacy of prioritising epistemology through resituating ontological and ontogenetic concerns. My preference here is to use the less common ‘ontogenetic’ as well as ‘ontology’. The latter term works on the assumption of a concrete category of being, whereas speaking in terms of genesis, from which the adjectival ‘genetic’ is etymologically coined, gestures more accurately toward movement and process (Massumi, 2002; Manning, 2006). This has salient implications for how subjectivity is understood that I will explore throughout this chapter.

3.1.1 *Conceptual pickpocketing and notes on terminology*

The sociomaterial turn, as I have discussed in the introductory chapter ([see page 11](#) where I share my justification for the term ‘sociomaterial’), is by no means a coherent field of study. It is a field that has been prefaced as “theoretically dense and ontologically impossible to operationalise” (Allen, 2018, p. 5) and “mind-numbingly diverse” (Fox and Alldred, 2017, p. 4). This sheer discordance of thought within this field has been levelled as a barrier to engagement, and I sympathise with this view when I consider the difficulties in the very naming of this return. However, I certainly do not share the view that this precludes any engagement with sociomaterialism *per se*. In my view this is a necessary complication of things. In her exegesis of Gilles Deleuze’s legacy, Braidotti (2002, p. 66) introduces the term “conceptual pickpocketing” to understand how Deleuze, an important early theorist within this field, “preached and practiced conceptual insurrection against the theoretical fathers” in a kind of “loving disrespect” that sought to work against rigid imitations of the canonised versions of philosophy. Unconcerned with meticulously following a singular theorist, Braidotti (2002) details how Deleuze engaged in the art of bricolage to bring together sources and actively think through the intellectual challenges they propose. Ringrose and Renold (2019, p. 6) take a similar approach in their passage on citational practices by eschewing simply following “‘masters’ and ‘key concepts’ models of phallic dissemination, field-defining, and territorialisation”. Their use of phallic is employed to refer to the Freudian processes of oedipalisation as a form of repression that constrains desire to the paternal, familial, and therefore all too familiar, domain (Lorraine, 2010). My use of conceptual pocketing echoes this line of thought and is also akin to the scholarship on **diffractive** inquiry that emerged over the years (Barad, 2007). This approach is not intended to diminish the individual nuances of each of these writers, and certainly not to avoid conceptual difficulty. Rather, the emphasis is on finding resonance between them, seeing what works, and entangling key tendencies. Affirmatively, then, I take up this technique of conceptual pickpocketing to work with, through,

across, and sometimes against sociomaterial, poststructural, and phenomenological thought as I assemble my proposal for understanding children's identity formation in early childhood.

At first glance, this admittedly feels distant from the previous chapter where I dealt in more empirical terms, however these initial conceptualisations are necessary to provide the basis for later analytic work. I will introduce several key terms relevant to my study, namely: Spinozist monism, assemblages, and affect. I consider how sociomaterialism resituates identity in-formation in line with epistemological and ontogenetic concerns. I end this chapter by considering the implications of sociomaterialism for my intended research aims.

A final note on terminology within this chapter in addition to that which I have discussed in Chapter One: as far as I am putting forward a sociomaterial proposal, it should follow that I stick to the language of materiality and matter to describe the human relation to non-human elements of experience. In some instances, and particularly in the first part of this chapter, I will stick to this rule. My primary concern, however, is that 'matter', in the sense of the noun, not the verb 'to matter', is rarely employed in everyday usage to refer to the non-human, and certainly not in early childhood contexts. As the chapter progresses, I will shift my use of terminology to that of 'things', a term I believe to be much more common and applicable. This is also the preferred term of Bennett's (2010, p. xvi) writing, who writes of 'thing-power', which "gestures toward the strange ability of ordinary, man-made items to exceed their status as objects and to manifest traces of independence or aliveness, constituting the outside of our own experience". Finally, in some cases, I may not distinguish between non-human and human at all. My rationale here is that there will be instances where a distinction between the human and the non-human is simply unnecessary. In these instances, I shall use the term 'more-than-human'.

3.2 Introducing a Spinozist metaphysics

Turning to the underlying metaphysical perspectives that inform theories on subjectivity, this section considers how it might be possible to overcome the limitations of a Cartesian worldview. I introduce and evaluate a Spinozist metaphysics as to how it informs my broader sociomaterial proposal for understanding children's identity formation.

Following the motivation within scholarship to unsettle humanist thought, research on sociomaterialism first challenges the perceived nature/culture and matter/mind binaries (Gatens, 2000; Kirby, 2017). This is a shift away from conventional ways of understanding the world, namely the **transcendent** Cartesian belief that humans exist in a hierarchical relationship, above

all matter, including animals, plants, and objects. As I discussed toward the end of the previous chapter, contemporary interpretations of this view posit the active thinking human self (the *cogito*) as more important than, and in control of, the passive body and wider environment. However, underwriting this paradigm are a number of implicit presuppositions about what counts as human in the first place, implicating power dynamics around claims to rationality, subjectivity and agency that continue to affect how humans perceive the relation between minds and bodies, as well as nature and culture.⁷ From a sociomaterial position, the dualistic nature of Descartes' metaphysics that has led to this parsing of nature and culture is considered to be a fundamental oversight insofar as it perpetuates notions of human mastery over the non-human world (Kirby, 2017). The Cartesian view perpetuates anthropocentrism given that it diminishes the basic significance of recognising that, globally, human beings have always, and continue to, depend on material relations to make culturally specific lives possible (Barad, 2007; Alaimo and Hekman, 2008; Coole and Frost, 2010). Against this, scholars writing in the vein of a sociomaterial approach shift the focus away from "Man" as the measure of all things toward more relational kinds of subjectivity (Deleuze, 1988; Dolphijn and Tuin, 2012; Braidotti, 2013). Sociomaterialism moves toward a monist metaphysics theorised by Baruch Spinoza (2002), a Dutch philosopher of Jewish and Portuguese ancestry in the seventeenth century whose contributions against Cartesian logic remain crucial today.

It is worth noting at the outset that criticism has been levelled against the mobilisation of Spinoza's thought for an overreliance on secondary and tertiary sources rather than an engagement with his works on their own terms (Robinson and Kutner, 2018). In response, I will refer to *Ethics*, which is widely regarded as Spinoza's *magnum opus*, directly where possible. Yet I also believe that there is good reason to engage with secondary texts given the complexities of the historical era in which Spinoza wrote. Further, many of these writings, far from revising his original position, can be said to strengthen the clarity of his metaphysics. Deleuze (1992a; 1988) and Deleuze and Guattari's (1983) interpretations are a case in point insofar as they both foreground Spinoza's writings on monism and 'affect' (see page 63) and situate him on more political and contemporary terms. For example, in *Anti-Oedipus* where Deleuze and Guattari (1983, p. 28) write that the most fundamental problem of political philosophy is in fact the one that Spinoza foresaw with exceptional clarity. That is, the question of how human desire is shaped. Deleuze and Guattari explicate the political

⁷ Though the birth of humanism is typically considered pre-Socratic, for instance with Protagoras's maxim that 'man is the measure of all things' it would be unfair to say this was primarily a Western practice. Morgan (2016), for instance, points out that certain humanistic ideas were central to many ancient Confucian, Theravada Buddhist, and Taoist traditions that turned away from the compulsory authority of the supernatural, and instead posited human beings as the primary source of spiritual understanding and value

nature of this question in relation to wider social repression, questioning the Cartesian logics that have led people to become ignorant of the (affective) forces that shape conscious thought. Whereas, as discussed, Descartes' position would advance a theory of mind, Spinoza disavowed the binary nature of this logic on the basis that humans cannot separate thinking about the mind from thinking about the body. In his view, neither reason nor emotion emerges solely from the individual thinking mind, as the implications of such an idea have resulted in a false consciousness leaving us ignorant of how we perceive and interpret the body. Therefore, in contrast with Descartes, Spinoza (2002, p. 281) believed that "mental decision on the one hand, and the appetite and physical state of the body on the other hand, are simultaneous in nature".

Positing the body as simultaneous with the mind has vital implications for how agency is understood. There is a move away from the *cogito* and a transcendental mode of thought, toward an ontological foundation of **immanence** whereby priority is given to neither the mind nor the body, neither nature nor culture. Nor are they considered binary. In a later proposition it is possible to comprehend how Spinoza (2002, p. 284, original emphasis) conceives of these as inextricable from each other:

Whatsoever increases or diminishes, assists or checks, the power of activity of our body, the idea of the said thing increases or diminishes, assists or checks the power of thought of our mind.

What Spinoza posits here is that external forces within the environment can directly affect human bodies, which therefore directly affect the mind, as the two are simultaneous in nature. This brings us to the *monist* aspect of Spinoza's view which challenges anthropocentrism and therefore implicates how humans perceive the role of matter in experience. Rather than an understanding of matter as being inert, passive, and in need of human agency to do anything, matter is now understood as having the capacity to enable, constrain and mediate the body and mind to differing degrees. Thus, contra Descartes, Spinoza actively *increases* the significance of the knowledge that human beings have always, and continue to, depend on material relations to make culturally specific lives possible.

Contemporary scholars have found significant value in Spinoza's ontological position (Gatens, 1995; Braidotti, 2006; Dolphijn and Tuin, 2012). Braidotti (2006, pp. 40-41), for instance, advances her argument for dislocating the human as the centre of experience on the grounds of a monist metaphysics that essentially dissolves the individual subject into a broader web of non-human elements. Similarly, in Grosz's (1994) account of sexed subjectivities, Spinoza's monism is utilised to trouble the perceived individual immediacy of self-consciousness and advance a more holistic conception of the self. Applying Spinoza's thought and the liveliness of matter in the early

childhood context has several further implications. Firstly, it means no longer considering the (active) child, the (active) practitioner, the (passive) nursery environment, and the (dumb) material resources as hierarchical and discrete entities. Materials and things often found in early childhood spaces, such as paint, a climbing frame, a princess dress, or a football, can be treated as active and participatory as far as they ask questions of us (humans), produce ideas and invite processes of curiosity (Jones *et al.*, 2011; Rautio, 2014; Pacini-Ketchabaw, Kind and Kocher, 2017; Hargraves, 2020). This challenges a predominantly cognitive-oriented and humanist understanding of how curricula should function in relation to the child, such as that in the current Scottish CfE (Education Scotland, 2019a). For instance, as I noted in Chapter Two, in *Realising the Ambition* (Education Scotland, 2020a), while there is some recognition of the open-ended possibilities of materials, there is a much stronger emphasis on ‘mastery’ (Plumwood, 1994). This is visible through the expectation for practitioners to know in advance “the purpose and possibilities of the materials” (Education Scotland, 2020, p. 54) and then support children to understand how they “behave” (*ibid*, p. 67). For outdoor play materials in particular, the guidance privileges predefined properties, such as “how the wind blows, the features of natural materials, exploring the textures, weight and size of items such as stones, twigs and plants” (*ibid*, p. 76). On this view, it is only the human who is granted any relevance within play encounters as a transcendental subject concerned with the disciplinisation, labelling, manipulation and control over matter.

Lenz Taguchi’s (2010) study is a good illustration of how a monist metaphysics can be used to resituate material ontogenetics in learning practices. Situated in the Swedish context, Lenz Taguchi follows an onto-epistemological framework to highlight the tensions in viewing the learner and the material world as separate. For her, as in sociomaterial thought, this view positions the outside world as passive and without agency, where learning is something that takes place only within the individual learner’s mind, represented through language and discourse. In contrast, what she, inspired by Karen Barad (2007), terms an ‘intra-active pedagogy’, underpinned by an onto-epistemological approach, re-establishes learning as the production of intra-actions taking place within the always-ongoing process of non-human and human relations (Lenz Taguchi, 2010). For them, *Intra*-action is distinct from *interaction* insofar as the latter is based on the premise that things can be separated out as discrete entities for analysis. *Intra*-action, instead, is pure relationality. It is immanent relationality whereby humans do not hold a monopoly on which things generate meaning.

Rather than an exclusive focus on the (transcendent) learner, an intra-active pedagogy considers the whole of the learning event, the environment, and the agentic qualities of things that interact with the learner. This has political implications given that it overcomes the humanism of Descartes

metaphysics and challenges how the pedagogy of play practices might be conceived. It also enables a move beyond the well-rehearsed theory/practice divide. An intra-active pedagogy blurs these distinctions and repositions the material environment in relation to discursive meanings (Lenz Taguchi, 2010).

3.2.1 *Distinctions from previous frameworks*

Practically, a useful distinction from previous frameworks has been made by Masumi in the translators forward to Deleuze and Guattari's (1987) *A Thousand Plateaus*, in terms of '**State philosophy**' and '**nomad thought**'. State philosophy can be explained as a mode of research inquiry that relates to the creation and affirmation of statements, theory testing and building, through the production of unified laws. It is not insignificant to note here that, at least since the early modern period, universities have always sought to service the needs of government (Bhambra, Gebrial and Nişancioğlu, 2018; Gopal, 2021), so has curriculum (Apple, 2019). Research is top-heavy, starting from *a priori* abstractions and then conducting research with established classifications. State philosophy is understood as seeking to categorise, define and understand things relative to what is considered normal (Braidotti, 2011). It is therefore a process of stratification, where matters are explained by their resemblance to existing things or the extent to which they fit within existing categories; the purpose being to lay the foundations for future understanding. However, the problem with this typological thinking, and the crucial point to be drawn from this distinction, lies in its acceptance of 'difference': when we seek to categorise (and represent), we can only conceive of difference in terms of opposition between already stabilised, and zombified, entities (DeLanda, 2002).

Given the cul-de-sac presented by these major forms of sociological thought, many have argued that there is a need to engage in the productive nature of nomad thought to queer these boundaries and move beyond processes that have sought to segment and categorise the social (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987; Manning, 2016). While State philosophy seeks to represent the world through overarching top-down theory, nomad thought is instead concerned with following the processual flow of events as they unfold, beyond human experience, (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987). There is greater attention toward ontogenetic multiplicity, process and relations such that no singular thing in the social world is considered to exist in isolation. This is, again, a direct challenge to Cartesian logic and aligns with Spinoza's monism. Rather than beginning with established classifications, whereby the body corresponds to a particular site and therefore comes to be defined by that position, a monist perspective effectively relocates the politics of 'difference' (simply how we discriminate between beings and essences) prior to the typological scheme, effectively overcoming the fixity of "zombie concepts" that have tended to dominate models of thought in social sciences

research, especially those concerned with power relations (Massumi, 2019, p. 502). This is not, however, to position State philosophy as entirely static. As Manning (2016, p. 1) explains:

[N]either the minor nor the major [state philosophy] is fixed in advance. The major is a structural tendency that organizes itself according to predetermined definitions of value. The minor is a force that courses through it, unmooring its structural integrity, problematizing its normative standards.

This process of transformation is central to a sociomaterial approach toward subjectivities, not in terms of moving into a different form but rather of constantly processual, constantly transforming relations (Coleman, 2009). For Hickey-Moody and Rasmussen (2009, p. 43), humans do not begin as fixed subjects who then have to know a fixed world because the self is always transforming according to its relations. It is more accurate to say that “there is experience and *from* this experience we form an image of ourselves as distinct subjects”. The central contention here is that engagements with the nomadic and minor into majoritarian modes of thought have the potential to develop more critical interventions into the ways in which scholarship might understand children’s subjectivities in-formation in the present and how they can be challenged.

This metaphysics introduced thus far can be understood in broader terms as rooted in **process philosophy**, concerned with understanding the world as an ongoing process in continual transformation (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987; Grosz, 1999a; Dolphijn and Tuin, 2013; Coleman, 2009). The ‘present’ is conceptually understood as what is happening ‘now’. That is, as the point which separates the past from *what it was*, and into the future *toward which it is moving*. In this sense, the present itself is never fixed. Deleuze and Guattari (1987) address this by speaking of ‘becomings’ of the present, rather than being of the past. The past is not inaccessible, it is co-existent with the present as potential (or tendency, as Bergson (2001) would have it). Braidotti (2002: p. 99) also makes this point when she considers that “temporally speaking, a body is a portion of living memory that endures by undergoing constant internal modifications following the encounter with other bodies and forces ... (this) lies at the heart of Deleuze’s vision of subjectivity”. I return to this point on temporality toward the end of the chapter ([see page 73](#)). For current purposes, however, it is sufficient to outline that an engagement with a Spinozist metaphysics and minor thought is a manoeuvre away from process of signification, coding, and representation, toward a focus on the emergence of movement where passage precedes construction. Processually, the actual experience of life itself means that we humans never stop becoming. Thus, thinking in terms of becomings entails a crucial shift in conventional thinking about subjectivity as it allows for a consideration of the not-yet-known.

3.3 Towards a sociomaterial agency

Following my earlier assertion that this sociomaterial proposal is not a complete departure from previous models of thought, in this section I consider how Judith Butler's (1988; 1993; 2006) performativity framework may be resituated and expanded upon within a sociomaterial metaphysics to understand agency in a more-than-human sense.

As discussed in Chapter Two, for Butler (1993), who is perhaps one of the most influential scholars on gender and identity in the contemporary Western world, performativity does not simply mean a performance of identities in a superfluous sense. Rather, it refers to “the reiterative and citational practice by which discourse produces the effects that it names” (Butler, 1993, p. 2). Their argument follows that form of masculinity, femininity, and performances of the self are practices that are consistently repeated (primarily through discursive speech acts), rather than being a universal condition of one's identity. Gender, then, and the performance of identity, can be understood as something that we humans *do* as a constructed performance in which we act, although do not have complete agency in, insofar as we all operate within strong cultural discourses of what it is to be a ‘boy or a ‘girl’ or a ‘man’ or a ‘woman’. For Butler, these discourses are routinely repeated, so they feel “real”, as if these discourses were who we are. Yet in repeating them we also sustain the gender norms. In a classic sense, Butler (2006, p. xv) can be said to be describing processes of ‘habituation’, where performativity serves as “a repetition and a ritual, which achieves its effects through its naturalization in the context of a body, understood, in part, as a culturally sustained temporal duration”.

Butler's theoretical framework does grant the insistent reality of bodies, yet many have outlined that their argument around performativity is one in which the *human*, agentic repetition of gender performance animates the body and signifies biological sex (Kirby, 2002; Dolphijn and Tuin, 2012). This is a strong claim with significant consequences, though there are a number of occasions where Butler states this. In *Bodies That Matter*, for instance, Butler writes that there can be no outside to signification for “every effort to refer to materiality takes place through a signifying process which, in its phenomenality, is already material” (Butler, 2011, p. 78). Similarly, in a later text, *Undoing Gender*, Butler admits “Every time I try to write about the body, the writing ends up being about language. This is not because I think that the body is reducible to language; it is not. Language emerges from the body, constituting an emission of sorts” (Butler, 2004, p. 198).

It is also worth revisiting the sex/gender distinction advanced by Butler. For the purposes of my broader argument this can be understood as a distinction between ontology (of the human body)

and epistemology (the knowledges used to know about the body). Butler's theory of performativity enables a distinction that posits gender as a social performance, enacted on to biological sex. Across much of feminist and queer scholarship during this period, this was deemed necessary in avoiding biological reductionism (Clough, 2004). However, considering this in sociomaterial terms, it is possible to comprehend how, in committing to a concept of performativity in which gender defines sex, materiality in a broader sense (but for Butler, specifically the body) is necessarily *subject to* discourse. Butler ultimately remains limited to a dialectical scheme of already established gender roles, echoing the function of a State Philosophy (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987). As Dolphijn and Tuin (2012, p. 143) put it:

Butler restricts herself to an oversimplified idea of language which refuses to see how the politics active in sex and gender build upon a series of statements and states of things that have always already been intrinsically entwined with one another and that are always in processes of morphogenesis corresponding to one another.

As others have noted, too, the limitations of Butler's performativity theory lie in not recognising the dynamism of matter sufficiently and therefore disregarding or even dissolving material bodies into discourse or language, thus restricting any possibility for resistance against determinate forms of being and becoming-otherwise from the domain of discourse (Braidotti, 1994; Cheah, 1996; Kirby, 2002; Barad, 2007). Finally, while Butler's formulation of habituation can be understood as a conventional interpretation located 'within the context of the body', through a sociomaterial perspective it becomes clear that the 'body' that Butler describes is implicitly human.

There is a further argument to be made that Deleuze and Guattari (1987) foresaw the limitations of Butler's argument before she had even made it. In the opening sections of *A Thousand Plateaus*, Deleuze and Guattari (1987) introduce two different figurations of writing: that of the 'tree or root' and that of the 'rhizome'. Logically aligned with their wider exposition around State philosophy and minor or nomad thought, the authors are critical of linguistic models that presuppose only a particular form of discourse. This is not to infer that these models are too abstract, but rather that they are not abstract enough (1987, p. 6) that they fail to encompass a diversity of ways of knowing about the world, or "other dimensions and other registers" (*ibid*, p. 8). The figuration of the tree in this case is intended to speak to the rooted fixity and stasis of signification and representation, whereas the rhizome privileges open connection untethered from typological thought.

Returning to Butler, to lessen the merit of engaging with epistemology over ontological matters in binary terms, however, is not to disregard performativity entirely. Rather, as Hickey-Moody and

Rasmussen (2009) propose, there is a case for reading Butler with Deleuze and sociomaterialism productively together in spite of their distinct ontological frameworks. In fact, it might be their very incompatibility that makes such a productive reading: “if they were already the same, why would we need both of them?” (Hickey-Moody and Rasmussen, 2009, p. 46). Seeking to accommodate material concerns alongside the social, Barad (2003) has instead proposed a ‘posthuman performativity’ to extend subjectivity and agency beyond the human toward the world itself. Drawing from insights in the field of quantum physics, Barad restates a case for matter and meaning without giving *a priori* primacy to either. She proposed that “all bodies, not merely ‘human’ bodies, come to matter through the world’s iterative intra-activity - its performativity” (Barad 2003, p. 823). In a similar, albeit much more contemporary vein than Spinoza originally theorised, the practical implications of this proposal are that agency is distributed through intra-active social *and* material relations, through rhizomatic ‘assemblages’ (which I discuss next). As I wrote at the outset of this chapter, agency has long been thought of as a defining characteristic of the human species where humans are considered to be the exclusive producers of the social world. However, in the sociomaterial mode of thought:

Agency is not held, it is not a property of persons or things; rather, agency is an enactment, a matter of possibilities for reconfiguring entanglements. So agency is not about choice in any liberal humanist sense; rather, it is about the possibilities and accountability entailed in reconfiguring material-discursive apparatuses of bodily production, including the boundary articulations and exclusions that are marked by those practices.

(Kleinman and Barad, 2012, p. 54)

In my initial readings on the role of agency, I was anxious. My feelings were akin to those expressed by Olsson (2009, p. xx1) early in her text: “To do away with the subject! Doesn’t that sound dangerous for our field of early childhood education?”. As a former early childhood practitioner myself, I am all too familiar with the aphorisms for a ‘child-centred’ approach (Education Scotland, 2020a, p. 15), keeping the child ‘at the heart’ of best practice (Education Scotland, 2020a, p. 38), and the pressure to always include the ‘child’s voice’ (Education Scotland, 2020a, p. 109) that populate early childhood curriculum frameworks. Yet it is salient that thinking in more-than-human terms does not remove the child at all. This is not an erasure. Agency is distributed, relational, more-than- or posthuman, rather than individualised. A sociomaterial performativity overcomes the limitations of purely humanist thought, moving instead in line with my sociomaterial proposal around overcoming any binary separation between epistemology and ontology. On these terms, a monist metaphysics that aligns with the philosophy of process

diminishes the significance of any distinction between epistemological knowledges and ontogenetic forces. Thus, actively enlarging the scope of inquiry into subjectivity beyond the humanist domain and its related concerns about the ‘individual’.

3.3.1 *Between Barad and Deleuze*

My use of Barad, and her conception of posthuman performativity, in relation to Deleuze, and my forthcoming exploring of his concepts of the assemblage and affect, is worth some attention at this point, not least since it has been argued by Hein (2016) that their respective positions are fundamentally incompatible with each other. The crux of Hein’s (2016, p. 6) argument is that while Deleuze’s philosophy is one of immanence, “Barad’s is a philosophy of identity and remains within the sphere of transcendence”. This claim is made on the basis that Barad’s framework necessitates that agency can only be understood *through* intra-action, which itself can be understood as an identity in the Aristotelian sense, whereas Deleuze’s philosophy operates at a prior level of ‘pure difference’ as that which remains undetermined prior to any fixed form. Ultimately, Hein (2017, p. 7) concludes that:

As far as combining the work of Deleuze and Barad in the same qualitative study, ontologically, their philosophies are incommensurable, and mixing or blending them is likely to result in ontological/theoretical incoherence.

Hein’s argument is initially convincing in drawing attention to the difference in emphasis that each author gives to ontology and ontogenesis. However, it sits in stark contrast to many authors who have found a number of resonances between these authors (Taguchi, 2012; Walker, 2014; Sheldon, 2016). One direct response to Hein has been put forward by Murriss and Bozalek (2019), who are essentially critical of Hein’s critique (even though, as they themselves acknowledge, Hein writes that his paper is *not* a critique) on the basis that his analysis is too oppositional, leaving no room for a more affirmative reading of the two. Rather, they argue, a more diffractive form of inquiry is necessary to build “new insights and attentively and carefully read for differences that matter in their fine details” (Murriss and Bozalek, 2019, p. 11). Such an approach echoes my own exposition of conceptual pickpocketing and further justifies my own decision for bringing these two authors together as part of my sociomaterial proposal. However, there is a further argument to be made against Hein that foregrounding the immanent nature of Deleuze’s philosophy underplays its relation to Deleuze’s broader conceptual metaphysics, and specifically the role of assemblages that shape human desire. In other words, to only focus on immanence ignores how Deleuze more practically understood this in relation to the assemblage, which I turn to now.

3.4 Assemblages

Having thus far considered Spinoza's metaphysics and attendant implications for materiality and agency, I now gather these strands through to the role of the 'assemblage'. Assemblages have become an important part of sociomaterialism in recent years to perform several key manoeuvres. Namely these are: to move away from thinking of power in terms of structural formations (the grid, State philosophy); to disrupt an understanding of subjectivity as unified and static (from beings to becomings); and finally, to engage in a more relational approach toward agency between non-human and human relations in encounters (from Cartesian humanism to Spinozist monism). Yet, while the term is used regularly throughout Deleuze and Guattari's work (1987; 1994), it is often thought that at no point did they formalise assemblages as a theory *per se*. DeLanda (2006, p. 3), for instance, remarks that the few pages dedicated to assemblage throughout Deleuze's work hardly amount to a "fully-fledged theory". There is some truth in this, yet conversely, I recognise it as possible to read their lack of formalization as a deliberate move, since to talk of assemblage 'theory' suggests an abstraction, an idea, and therefore a representation. As Guattari (2011) writes, assemblages operate on the same level of subjectivities rather than acting as a universal meta-language. In his own words:

There is no general assemblage that overhangs all of them, every time we encounter a universal enunciation, it will be necessary to determine the particular nature of its enunciative assemblage and analyse the operation of power that leads it to lay claim to such a universality.

(Guattari, 2011, p. 12)

In any case, part of the initial confusion in understanding this term lies in the translation of assemblage from the French word *agencement*, which first appears in *A Thousand Plateaus* (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987) to replace the previously used term 'desiring-machines' (Deleuze and Guattari, 1983). The translation has proved problematic because the English word 'assemblage' does not mean the same thing as the French word *agencement*. While the English definition of an assemblage is a gathering of things together into unities, the French *agencement* is an arrangement or layout of heterogeneous elements. Nail (2017) outlines a notable consequence of this distinction. Namely, assemblage in the original French translation was a term created as an alternative logic to that of the English unities, though because there is no equivalent English definition of *agencement*, assemblages are falsely taken to be unities and therefore the intended meaning is lost in translation. A unity is defined by the intrinsic relations that various parts have to one another in a whole. An example of this would be the human body:

Each organ performs a function in the service of reproducing its relations with the other parts and ultimately the harmony of the whole organism. A heart separated from a body does not survive as a “heart” since the function of a heart is to circulate blood through a body. Similarly, the organism does not survive without a heart, since it is the nature of the organism to have a heart.

(Nail, 2017, p. 23)

As I have analysed elsewhere (Tembo, 2020b), as each element relies on each other to be unity, any deviation from their internal relations ceases the unity entirely and becomes a mechanism defined only by their external relations. In contrast, an assemblage as it was intended by Deleuze and Guattari (1987) is comprised of *heterogeneous* elements coming together in a *non-homogenous grouping*. While unities do not allow for change without abolishing themselves in the process (for example, the human body does not survive without a heart), assemblages are more like machines, defined solely by their external relations of composition, mixture, and aggregation. To this end, they are open-ended systems. More nomadic than State-like. More rhizomatic than the logic of the tree. This is what Deleuze and Guattari (1987) are referring to when they talk of a **‘Body Without Organs’** (BwO) insofar as a body does not automatically designate a human body but is rather an assemblage of relations (what they also call a “disjunctive synthesis”) always in flux on a plane of immanence. This is perhaps better understood as an ‘un-organised body’. Here, I find a Rube Goldberg machine most instructive for thinking through Deleuze’s interpretation of assemblage, made up of incongruous parts in *ad hoc*, shifting relations of widely varying degrees of efficiency and probability. Rube Goldberg machines are deliberately complex things that ultimately perform a simple task or tasks. As Shores (2010, para 3) explains:

What we note from the machines is how comically unrelated are the conjoined parts. They are more like disjunctions than conjunctions, but they are mechanical, because they affect one another; or we might say the resulting transformations are always implied yet never coherent. What we see is the production of differences on the basis of differences.

While this is a simplified illustration of how assemblages work, the *ad hoc* nature is usefully elaborated to underpin their open-ended, or non-totalisable, status. In his review of ‘post-social assemblages and collectivities’, Oswell (2013) introduces the assemblage in relation to Foucault’s (1980b) concept of the *dispositif*, a French term that originates in the verb *disposer*, to arrange or to place. This has been identified as a central term within his writings that has since been translated into ‘apparatus’ in a number of subsequent texts. Foucault (1980, p. 194) himself explained this term as a “thoroughly heterogeneous ensemble consisting of discourses, institutions, architectural

forms, regulatory decisions, laws, administrative measures, scientific statements, philosophical , moral and philanthropic propositions ... the apparatus itself is the system of relations that can be established between these elements". While there are similarities between this and the Deleuzian assemblage, Oswell's (2013, p.73, emphasis mine) review is noteworthy in its omission of the role of *desire* within the latter, and in his claim that "*perhaps more so for Foucault*, the organisation of materialities is intimately tied to the actualisation of power". Such a claim is striking insofar as he risks depoliticising the assemblage which, rather than having a weaker concern with power, arguably formulates a more expansive and nuanced approach that recognises the role of power *per* desire. Whereas Foucault saw apparatus of power as primary and constitutive of norms and disciplinary subjects, Deleuze (1992c; 1997) and Deleuze and Guattari (1987) resituate power within the assemblage as a consequence of desire, which for them has ontological priority. This is important because it resituates the capacity for resistance not in response *to* power, but prior to the sedimentation of it. Their aim here was to subvert the already-constituted and locate flows of desire between bodies as the starting point. On this basis, following the distinction that I made earlier in building my sociomaterial proposal between interaction and intra-action, it is salient to consider how my interpretation of assemblages is made in the same vein. There is not a pre-existing world and then assemblages where individual components interact with each other, rather assemblages *produce* and are *constitutive of* worlds through intra-action (Barad, 2007). No anterior significance is given to either the human or the non-human, both emerge through each other in events or encounters to produce us as individual subjects, insofar as individual subjectivity is recognised as the axiomatic state of being. On this basis, it is possible to argue that assemblages have an ontogenetic status of their own, "a being *of* the middle" (Massumi, 2002, p. 70, emphasis in original) rather than a "middling being" (*ibid.*). This enables the potential for subjectivities to be conceptualised outside the typological scheme of the already-constituted, mobilising the force of the minor that I have discussed above.

In the early childhood context, assemblages shift analysis beyond the individual child toward the human and non-human intra-actions produced through certain events. Bradley *et al.* (2012), for example, usefully illustrate how the sociomateriality of nursery mealtimes with its heterogeneous composition of 'baby-highchair-floorspace-adult-food-desires to eat-hygiene' all produce more-than-human performativities. For these authors, "the children have agency, but so do the highchairs and bottles. They deflect, make possible, refuse what people and other things can, want or intend to do. They 'addle and rearrange' thoughts, trajectories, actions and perceptions" (Bradley *et al.*, 2012, p. 146). Therefore, as a conceptual frame, in this example assemblages provide a way of understanding how certain human and material bodies come together to enable or

constrain certain relations, thus challenging a traditional conception of subjectivity as solely located within the individual.

Assemblages also work temporally to disrupt linear ideas of cause-and-effect. For example, in the case of gender and sexuality, cause-and-effect logics can often work to position children as victims of ‘inappropriate’ messages from wider society about what it means to be feminine, masculine, or (hetero)sexual (Coleman, 2009). The solution to challenging normative gender and sexualities in this way is to assume a future that can be determined by measurable actions in the present, thus carrying with it a “promise that a process engaging with the same conditions twice can generate an event that looks like the event that it generated the first time” (Manning, Massumi and Brunner, 2019, p. 281). However, if one thinks instead in terms of assemblages, and recognises the often messy ways in which discourse and matter come together in any event, a linear cause-and-effect way of thinking significantly limits the capacities for understanding how practices are *becoming* in processes of formation: “you will find that no event can be mapped in advances” (*ibid.*). Things do always become again, but always in different ways. To this end, it is no longer possible to conceive of a macro level of structural power outside of what actually happens within the contingency of assemblages. As Manning (2016, p. 3) writes:

By making everything an event, by emphasizing that there is nothing outside of or beyond the event, the aim is to create an account of experience that requires no omnipresence.

The often unstable, immanent, and non-totalisable nature of assemblages might provide insight into how more creative subjectivities can emerge in certain interactions. If repetition occurs through assemblages, but in new ways each time, then it is therefore the motor of *difference* (Deleuze and Patton, 1994). Vitaly, what stabilises some assemblages more than others are the capacities of these relations to affect or be affected, which I turn to next.

3.5 Affect

In this section I examine the role of affect as an ontogenetic force that mobilises subjectivities, through assemblages, in encounters. I consider the ubiquity of affect and distinctions from human emotion. I then shift my analysis toward an understanding how affects come to be saturated with power relations informed by the relevant literature.

While it is well noted by nearly all who come across ‘affect’ that there is no single definition of the term, the affective turn can be said to be broadly unified behind the idea that power relations such as gender or race cannot be thought of as externally imposed structures, nor conceived of as static,

atemporal formations (Swindle, 2011; Massumi, 2015; Simpson and Brigstocke, 2019). The recent interest in affect perhaps runs conterminously with the rise in theory fatigue, the declining influence of both social constructionist and performativity theory frameworks, and the felt lassitude within the contemporary political moment (Cvetkovich, 2012). As Probyn (2004, p. 24), a formative writer on affect, admits, “I have been drawn to theories of affect precisely because they seem to offer a way out of the relentless reiteration of abstract notions that goes under the name of ‘theory’”. I also suspect that the take-up of affect within primarily feminist scholarship is salient here, given that affect also challenges the masculinist rationality of Cartesian logics. I understand affect as central to a sociomaterial proposal given the need to complicate conventional interpretations of subjectivity. As others have come to identify (Jones *et al.*, 2011; Pires, 2014; Huuki and Renold, 2015; Curti, 2016; Hickey-Moody and Willcox, 2020; Ingulfsvann, Moe and Engelsrud, 2020), the use of affect seems particularly generative when put to work in early childhood.

In the simplest terms, affect can be understood as one’s felt capacity to act in any encounter, as a way of talking about “‘where we might be able to go and what we might be able to do’ in every present situation” (Massumi, 2015, p. 3). The emphasis on feeling is significant here, since a reading of subjectivity through affect posits that human bodies are not only known through schemas of conscious perception, in the mind, but are rather prehended adjacently to what Massumi (2002, p. 60) terms as the body’s “visceral sensibility”. Massumi’s conception of this term, which I also discuss in another paper Tembo (2021), signals a debt to the physiological sciences and the function of the enteric nervous system that responds to visceral as well as proprioceptive and kinaesthetic sensations. More colloquially, these are often known as one’s ‘gut feelings’:

Visceral sensibility immediately registers excitations gathered by the five “exteroceptive” senses even before they are fully processed in the brain ... it anticipates the translation of the sight or sound or touch perception into something recognizable associated with an identifiable object ... it registers intensity.

Massumi (2002, p. 60)

Understanding affect enables the possibility to consider how humans respond and register sensations prior to conscious recognition. This line of thought suggests that we come to experience and perceive the world through the felt viscosity of encounters of “smell, sweat, flushes of heat, dilation of pupils, [and] the impulses [that] bodies pick up from each other” (Puar, 2017, p. 190), as much as conscious and cognitive thought. Through feelings as much as thinkings, or through perceptions as much as conceptions. This points toward an inherent complicity between humans

and their non-human environments, enabling a broader understanding of how we, humans, continually enact subjectivities in heterogeneous assemblages of non-human and human relations. To use a mundane example from Colebrook (2002, p.38), we can imagine when we watch a scene in a film and our hearts begin to race, our eyes flinch and we might begin to sweat: “Before [we] even think or conceptualise there is an element of response that is prior to any decision”. To pay attention to the nascency of affect, then, enables a step back to focus on the emergence of movements, where “passage precedes construction” and affects therefore precede the rush to representation (Massumi, 2002, p. 8). Because of this, it is important to think of affect as not another ‘theory’ but rather a way of understanding the metaphysical experience of life itself in the same manner as the monist metaphysics that I outlined above. We, humans, are continually caught up in the midst of affects. The most compelling argument for this is made by Massumi in an interview with Manning and Brunner (2019, p. 277) and is worth citing at length:

The gesture of encapsulating it in an ‘affective turn’, as opposed to the preceding ‘linguistic turn’ or any other sort of turn, assumes that affect is a thing, something that can be separated from other things, like you would put a fork on one side of your plate and the spoon on the other, and then position yourself polemically according to whether you think it’s better to scoop or stab your food. It’s a bit Swiftian, like arguing about which end of the egg to open. When you define affect as Spinoza does, as an ability to affect or be affected, it’s clear that it’s a dimension of all activity, whether we see fit to categorize that activity as subjective or objective. It is just as obvious that there is an affective dimension to language. Affect is already on the plate, whatever your preferred intellectual diet, and it lends itself to many kinds of utensils.

What Massumi aims to emphasise here is the ubiquity of affect as an alternative to conventional humanist modes of knowing and feeling, whether it is recognised or not. It is for this reason that I avoid using the term ‘affect theory’ when speaking about affects, since as many others have pointed out, ‘theory’ is suggestive of an abstraction (Guattari and Genosko, 1996; Wyatt, 2019). Affect implicates the pre-conscious, or backgrounded, nature of experience, of which people consciously feel the effects.

There has been plenty of discussion within the literature about the strict-or-not relationship between affect and emotion (Massumi, 2002; Ahmed, 2014a; Åhäll, 2018; Shouse, 2005). While I take the position that there is a useful distinction to made, I recognise it as also true that both terms frequently fade in and out of coherence with one another. As a crude distinction, emotions can be said to refer to conscious thoughts and subjective processes about how individuals feel.

Emotions *follow* affect as felt and thus represent the subjective, or culturally coded, feeling of affect, as “affect plus an awareness of that affect” (Manning, 2006, p. xxi). Because of this, affect is therefore ontologically prior to emotion (and, in fact, all forms of conscious self-reflection) and underpins a pre-personal relationality beyond any one individual, so that conscious feelings (informed by wider social and cultural knowledges) are always inflected with the affects that we, humans, experience. So, for example, naming a feeling as ‘joyful’ or ‘happy’ is a retrospective knowledge applied onto felt affects that make that affect culturally legible (Ahmed, 2014). Although, while conventionally emotions are felt as solely emergent from oneself, such as ‘I feel happy or sad’, this can often overlook the relationality between humans and their non-human environments. Ultimately, as Ahmed (2014a) has written, in everyday reality there is a great deal of slippage between affect and emotion such that a distinction is not always necessary.

3.5.1 *Applying affect*

For research inquiry into the ways that power relations might shape subjectivities, it is argued that working with affect enables a move beyond the level of discourse without dismissing it entirely (Massumi, 2002; Clough and Willse, 2011). This is because it allows research inquiry to account for the *processual* nature of how desires are shaped to produce certain power relations (for example, gender, heteronormativity) and identity in-formation, rather than starting with a presumption of their already embedded nature in social structures. Necessarily, these processes can assemble into regularities (or practices), however this places power structures as consequential effects of affective encounters, rather than already-existing formations (Massumi, 2002). This relationship remains a crucial one, though, as Massumi (2002, p. 8) explains in the same passage:

Gender, race, and sexual orientation also emerge and back-form their reality. Passage precedes construction. But construction does effectively back-form its reality. Grids happen. So social and cultural determinations feed back into the process from which they arose. Indeterminacy and determination, change and freeze framing, go together. They are inseparable and always actually coincide while remaining disjunctive.

Consequentially, this understanding emphasises movement and implicates questions of ontogenetic forces: how particular affects connect thoughts together with bodies and things, in particular spaces, and what capacities they enable (augment) or constrain (diminish) going forward (Spinoza, 2002). Affect might be deemed inherently political in this sense, habitually saturated within assemblages by power formations (Massumi, 2015). Affect entails a move toward the situated nature of certain actions, where the potential affective force of particular spaces based upon social and cultural tendencies is how they enable or constrain certain movements. Affects

are also constitutive of becomings, thus, challenging the notion of already-existing subjects and identities in the world.

As an example of this relationality and constraint, Ash and Gallacher (2015) discuss a water play table within an early childhood environment. Developmentally the water table can be said to provide an understanding of maths and science by allowing young children to explore the physical properties of water. If, however, close attention is paid to the affective *relationship* in encounters between the children, the water, the plastic tray and the various objects placed there to facilitate water play, then the water play does not simply yield knowledge represented in the sum of different sensory experiences but rather shapes the capacities of children, water and playthings to act and to respond to the situation at hand (Ash and Gallacher, 2015). This matters because capacities shape subjectivities concerning how individuals are able to act in any given encounter.

Indeed, crucially with this, it is possible to assemble an argument for understanding the human subject not as a pre-constituted discursive formation as in the social constructionist model, but instead as an assemblage of affects: Identity itself as an effect of affect. As Ahmed (2014a) argues, partially borrowing from a Marxian critique of capital, the more recognisable social and cultural determinations are, the more habitual that they feel, the more affective they then become. An important illustration of this would be Swindle's (2011) paper examining the social and cultural construction of "Girl" as affect. Swindle draws attention to the myriad ways that Girl is assembled as a signifier in Western capitalist societies through a number of affective orientations. She writes:

The affect, girl, circulates with/among objects, including signifiers, giving materiality to certain collectives of bodies (most often though not necessarily young feminine bodies), rendering them girls, and sticking to certain objects and people to create girl culture ... girl is the affect that sticks to certain bodies mattering them by creating the surfaces, boundaries, and relations that seem to delimit them, the affect that animates girlhood, and that is felt *as* girl, though not only *by* girls.

(Swindle, 2011, para 9)

Paying attention to affect is useful here as it gets at the immanent and tendential experience of becoming, rather than being, a Girl, thus troubling static conceptions of identity formation. In other words, researchers are then able to ask what the determination of girl *does* in terms of affecting the capacity of one to act freely. Further, recalling the function of assemblages where bodies are not known prior to their relation (Massumi, 2002; Barad, 2007), it becomes possible to understand how a binary distinction between where human bodies end and where non-human

objects and signifiers begin can no longer be maintained. Many things have now changed. It is the affective relationality of these human and non-human things that enact boundaries and direct the passages towards which bodies may become.

My review of affect here relates back to, and allows me to extend upon, some aspects of the previous chapter where I examined the foreclosure of subjectivity according to contemporary capitalist and neoliberal societies. Aligned with the increased scholarship within this field, a number of authors (Clough and Willse, 2011; Parisi and Goodman, 2011; Beckman, 2018; Massumi, 2018) have since come to utilise affect to better understand capitalist modes of subjection beyond social constructionist approaches at the level of the human. These authors posit that normative discursive practices, including within curricula and policy, feed-back an affective resonance toward particular modes of being as part of the broader subsumption of life under capitalism. Power is now not only the actual exercise of force, but additionally operates tendentially at an affective level insofar as it shapes desire (Massumi, 2015). This can be understood as a form of what Parisi and Goodman (2011) describe as ‘mnemonic control’, which is partly informed by Deleuze’s (1992b) paper on societies of control, whereby investments in future feed-back are a constitutive feature of Western capitalist societies. In their own words, mnemonic control, through facets of contemporary branding culture, “describes the harnessed microactivation of what a body can do, within the domain of demarcated, and relatively predetermined, possibility” (Parisi and Goodman, 2011, p. 173). This is an investment in future feed-back which operates as a habitual mode of control. It also denotes the transition from power relations as repressive or disciplinary toward an understanding of their prefigurative, “sub or just conscious” (Anderson, 2014, p. 26) function. The production of certain social identities, then, is less *of* individual selves but rather constituted *through* assemblages. Take, for example, sexuality. Rather than a disciplinary knowledge of sexuality as repressive over individuals, an understanding of mnemonic control points toward how sexual identities are oriented according to affective desires, or orientations. On the affective nature of sexual orientation, Ahmed (2014a, p. 145) writes:

Sexual orientation involves bodies that leak into worlds; it involves a way of orientating the body towards and away from others, which affects how one can enter different kinds of social spaces (which presumes certain bodies, certain directions, certain ways of loving and living), even if it does not lead bodies to the same places. To make a simple but important point: *orientations affect what it is that bodies can do.*

Extending this point, Ahmed (2014a, p. 166n) includes a promising footnote which aligns closely to a broader sociomaterial perspective by speculating on the role of non-human things that

compose subjectivities: She proposes an approach toward sexual orientation which “rethink[s] the place of the object in sexual desire, attending to how bodily directions ‘towards’ some objects and not others affects how bodies inhabit spaces, and how spaces inhabit bodies”. As numerous scholars have long identified (Warner, 1993; Ward and Schneider, 2009; Johnson, 2012; Nguyen, 2021), it is an orientation toward heterosexuality that remains the privileged social identity in contemporary Western cultures as a taken for granted, ‘natural’, and unquestionable norm. Normative heterosexuality is granted legitimacy in a myriad of ways through the repetition of socio-legal (Johnson, 2012; Howard, 2013), institutional (Peterson, 2013; Searle, 2019) cultural (Chambers, 2003; Ward and Schneider, 2009), temporal (Ahmed, 2006) interpersonal (Krebbekx, 2018), and material practices that socially exclude or marginalise non-heterosexual bodies and orient heterosexuality and the gender binary as the majoritarian framework. Elsewhere, I have explored how whiteness and racialised affects are produced within particular social and material assemblages (Tembo, 2020b; Tembo, 2021a). Overall, investments in future feed-back and the often affective nature of capitalist social and cultural determinations demonstrate the way in which normative forms of subjectivity habitually impose on individuals.

Finally, for research inquiry and analysis, the deployment of affect affords the ability to go beyond solely what is said by any one individual person (and what can then be mapped onto discourse), toward a more ontogenetic consideration of the ways that forms of desire are materially felt and lived between bodies in assemblages. This is to say that affect exceeds language. As Deleuze (1988, p. 19) writes:

When a body “encounters” another body, or an idea another idea, it happens that the two relations sometimes combine to form a more powerful whole, and sometimes one decomposes the other, destroying the cohesion of its parts ... we experience *joy* when a body encounters ours and enters into compositions with it, and *sadness* when, on the contrary a body or an idea threaten our own coherence.

In the early childhood context specifically, thinking in terms of affect also works to disrupt the linearity of developmentalist approaches to children’s learning, and provides a means to think otherwise beyond individualistic approaches toward the child. By way of illustration, in their paper on element affects, Rooney (2018) describes the ways in which particular weather conditions affect children’s experiences of walking and of place, as a part of broader effort to consider how children might come to experiences the scales of human-induced climate change. Adopting a similar approach, Nxumalo and Villanueva (2019) turn to ‘Educator-Child-Creek Encounters’ in their research on decolonial pedagogies to understand the affective relationalities that emerge out of

children's play with their environment. For them, mobilising affect at a time of wider precarity with regards to the ecological climate is a necessarily ethical gesture away from human-centred practices rooted in notions of mastery and extraction. Also attentive to the atmospheric elements that comprise an assemblage, Gallagher's paper (2016, p. 43) extends a conventional humanistic analysis to consider sounds as affect: as "an oscillating difference, an intensity that moves bodies, a vibration physically pushing and pulling their material fabric". In early childhood spaces, it is then possible to consider the **sonic geographies** (Kanngieser, 2012) of noises produced by children, whether that be laughs, tears, screams, or roars, that affect them and may be conducive toward particular subjectivities.

In sum, bringing together affect with assemblages as part of my broader sociomaterial proposal for understanding children's subjectivities serves a central purpose for my research. That is, these knowledges extend the ambit beyond a primarily socially humanist perspective about how experience is produced, toward what I believe might be coined a process of 'affective sociomaterialisation'. On this view, identities are not anterior to one's contextual surrounds but are rather continually produced ontogenetically according to the body's visceral sensibility, often at a "sub or just conscious" level (Anderson, 2014, p. 26) level. These are stabilised through habitual social and cultural determinations that orient desire in particular ways and material things that augment and diminish capacities in any given encounter.

3.6 Implications for space and time

In this section, I examine the extent to which my proposed application of assemblages and affect has implications for how space and time are interpreted within a sociomaterial framework. In Kraftl's (2019, p. 03 parentheses mine) recent paper, the claim is made that "there are strikingly few studies that explicitly articulate children's and young people's geographies [the social] and architectural geographies [the material] together". Drawing from the field of human geography, Kraftl further argues that neutralist perspectives toward space, as no more than a *tabula rasa*, have tended to dominate traditional Cartesian accounts of childhood and children's play. However, outside the early childhood field, critical considerations of space have long been a central concern to a number of sociomaterial theorists in recent years concerned with challenging static conceptions of the term (Massey, 2005; Fenwick, Edwards and Sawchuk, 2011). Doreen Massey (2005), a foundational writer on space, proposed that space is conceived not as a fixed container, but rather as the product of always-in-process relations. For her, recognising the relational nature of space as actively assembling certain meanings, social and material, works against logics of

independency and anteriority. Spaces should therefore be understood as produced through intra-actions that can augment or diminish certain capacities, and therefore as productive of subjectivities.

That spaces shape how subjectivity is produced is not that radical of a claim when one considers the function of large architectural spaces such as football stadiums, shopping centres, offices, and art galleries that are all designed to facilitate and orient certain modes of being (such as ‘football fan’ a ‘retail consumer’ or an ‘office worker’). In an educational context, paying attention to how spaces produce subjectivities enables an understanding of how certain norms become regularised. For Fenwick, Edwards and Sawchuk (2011, p. 129), a focus on spatiality can allow for an understanding of how spaces are constituted in ways that:

[E]nable or inhibit learning, create inequities or exclusions, [or] open or limit possibilities for new practices and knowledges ... Spatial theories raise questions about what knowledge counts, where and how it emerges in different time-spaces, (and) how subjectivities are negotiated through movement and locations.

Such an understanding of space is therefore implicitly processual and deeply contributory toward how humans, come to perceive themselves in the world. Writing in a similar vein, Manning (2020) considers the affective crossing of ‘thresholds’ that exist and are felt before conscious perception, especially for those whom the space was not intentioned for. In such spaces where language and a particular way of being is often presupposed, some cross the threshold more easily than others (Manning 2020). Proceeding on this basis that spaces are not neutral, the manipulation of spaces can be considered in explicitly political terms. Deleuze and Guattari (1987) introduce the concepts of ‘smooth’ and ‘striated’ spaces to further understand the relation that we, humans and non-humans, have with the spatial world. The former refers to practices of organisation and binding created by sociomaterial demarcations of territory. As Deleuze and Guattari (1987, p. 385) argue, “one of the fundamental tasks of the State is to striate the space over which it reigns”. As an example, Hickey-Moody (2019) uses the concept of striated spaces to think through how teenage boys affect and are affected by gender. It is the determining norms placed upon those sex-marked male that continually re-mobilise certain tendencies of masculinity in present moments. She writes how “striations running across boy’s lives mark out territories they want to enter, to own, to change, to avoid, and at times they set perimeters against which they want to rebel” (Hickey-Moody, 2019, p. 15). Thus foreclosing, and sometimes augmenting, a person’s subjective capacity to be and become-otherwise from cultural dominant forms of identity.

Smooth spaces, in contrast, are nomadic, unpredictable and allow for the production of new knowledges. However, this is not intended to set up a binary formation, neither are fixed in place. Instead, “smooth space is constantly being translated, transversed into a striated space (and) striated space is constantly being reversed, returned to a smooth space” (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987, p. 474). As such, this again points to the ways in which identity is not *a priori*, but rather produced through desiring movements where certain affective forces work to enable or constrain the everyday. As an example, in their study on how children are ‘doing gender’ in the nursery, Renold and Mellor (2013) map out the effects of where gender becomes stratified. While the data generated were similar to classic ethnographic participant observation particular attention is paid to the complexities of affect and the movement of bodies through space. In one encounter, the authors share an extract between two pre-school age children, Tyler and Sophie, during a routine play encounter:

Tyler: (getting up) You stay here.

Sophie gets up.

Tyler: (pointing to where Sophie was sitting) No. You stay there.

Sophie sits back down.

Tyler: (looking into the camera, not at Sophie) Sorry, I have to go.

(He then leaves the giant’s castle.)

A typical poststructuralist analysis may primarily focus on what these children say (or do not say) in this encounter, however an ontogenetic framework privileges *what they do* (or what capacities this assemblage produces). This is possible through attending to the bodily movements across space through video and audio recording technologies. As the authors go on to discuss:

[O]ur ethnographic gaze became increasingly focused on how Sophie’s body was almost always in the shadow of her ‘best friend’ Tyler ... we located footage after footage of Sophie’s increasing incapacity to act, to move, or to speak without Tyler in close proximity. We began to see how this transsubjectivity was rendering Sophie’s body vulnerable and open to invasion and territorialisation.

(Renold and Mellor, 2013, p. 33)

While Sophie might appear to move freely, her agency (becoming) is caught up in gendered and heteronormative power relations around the nursery, thus striating her movement. This striation

effectively limits her capacity as a result of the affective forces at play, illustrating the permeability of some bodies to others as a result of the power relations involved. Overall, for my own sociomaterial proposal, this section has demonstrated the value of paying attention to the ways in which spatial factors contribute toward the formation of subjectivities.

With regard to temporality, one of the strongest limitations of poststructuralist research has been the tendency to fix things in place, address states of rest (beings), and then interpret motion as the secondary linkage between these states (Massumi, 2002). This constitutes a form of retrospective analysis, a looking back in time, where the past is understood as determinant of the future and being is put before becoming. However, the focus on becomings that I have discussed throughout this chapter serves as a disruption to a linear understanding of successions and instants. Becomings obey no chronological law, because they cannot be thought of within conventional logics of progress or development. As Bordeleau (2019) remarks, a metaphysics premised on *affective* involvements in the world's becoming is intrinsically related to an imminent futurity beyond chronological, toward non-linear, times. With Manning (in Manning, Massumi and Brunner, 2019, p. 276), this focus on the immanent can be understood as a kind of “event-time” which, again, seeks to unsettle the cumbersome logics of omnipresence:

Event-time emphasizes time's affective force, in the event. This affective force is laden with both pastness and futurity, but in a way that is singularly active in the now of experience.

What a sociomaterial proposal does then, is emphasize the nonlinearity of events and how things come to matter. Within any event, such as children coming together to play in the home corner or the construction area in the nursery, there is a fusing of the past and future that constitutes the present, not as we are (being), but as we are becoming. It is this present that determines what of the past carries forward into the future as potential (again, though becomings). Importantly, the capture of potential is the *sine qua non*, the essential condition and operation of power. “*what was* is a powerful lure” (Manning, 2016, pp. 117, emphasis in original). Paying attention to the emergent conditions of capture through the repetition of habitual affects is crucial if researchers are to better understand the sociomaterial relations that assemble to consequently striate determinate identity formation. If it is remembered too, that smooth and striated spaces operate on a continuum, this may open up potential for ‘lines of flight’ away from conditions of capture, Deleuze and Guattari (1987) outline that there is no determination of ourselves that does not at the same time create zones of *indetermination*. This is a key point that Massumi (2015, p. 58) picks up on:

Even in the most controlled political situation, there's a surplus of unacted-out potential that is collectively felt. If cued into, it can remodulate the situation. As Deleuze and Guattari liked to say, there is no ideology and never was. What they mean by that is no situation is ever fully predetermined by ideological structures or codings.

On this view, the ability to think otherwise and induce the untimely, is a gesture towards capacities for resistance against the determinacy of the already-known. Such a move unsettles the received wisdom of causality as linear and signals toward the production of novelty. For the issue of subjectivity, Deleuze's argument on determination and indetermination signals a need to remain open to subjectivities beyond the human as an "imposed image that imprison[s] us, the most racist of all images" (Colebrook, 2002:66). This is hence why Deleuze and Guattari (1987) privilege the BwO, discussed within the section on assemblages, as an indeterminate and more-than-human subjective form.

3.7 Closing

Responding to the issues raised in Chapter Two, this chapter has sought to develop a sociomaterial proposal for understanding the nature of children's subjectivity. I have argued that the information of the child's subjectivity is not an *a priori* epistemic social construct that is performed primarily through them alone as the sole agentic unit, over and above non-human materialities and the wider environment. Rather, the implications of my sociomaterial proposal posit that the 'child' is continually produced through social and material, natural and cultural, assemblages in events that affectively augment or diminish their capacities to act. In short, this might be termed as the process of 'affective sociomaterialisation'. Identity itself might therefore be reconsidered beyond the individual alone and instead as an assemblage of social and material meanings and practices, rather than an overriding structural formation. Agency is no longer attributable to any single person (nor, technically, is affect either). It is distributed through epistemological and ontogenetic knowledges as a 'posthuman performativity' (Barad, 2003), or a more-than-human form of Butler's original performativity framework. Thus, this enlarges the scope for research inquiry beyond the discursive (linguistic) domain. Notably, while Butler's formulation of habituation can be understood as a conventional interpretation located 'within the context of the body', through a sociomaterial perspective it becomes clear that the 'body' that Butler describes is implicitly human. With affective sociomaterialisation, the body is understood in a more-than-human, more expansive, sense. Thus 'habituation' can no longer be seen to take place primarily within the human body but may be usefully perceived as a co-compositional with the social and material milieu in

which one inhabits. This troubles static individualist categories of the self and foregrounds questions of power insofar as the determinate nature of dominant social and cultural affects can habituate us, humans, in certain ways, more or less equally.

For research inquiry, then, by paying attention to assemblages it is possible to understand how broader social and cultural determinacies are socially and materially felt and lived through the relationality of bodies. How certain signifiers and concepts, such as those relating to gender, do not pre-exist bodies in a temporal sense, but rather are involved in the *constitution* of them so that bodies become organised in socially and culturally recognisable ways, and may become organised-otherwise. Therefore, a sociomaterial metaphysics enables me, as the researcher, to straddle the boundaries between critique and creativity. It matters that we examine the coming-to of subjectivities in ways that extend beyond a focus on the child alone and also understand how the dominant determinacies that are produced can be challenged. It matters, too, that researchers notice how children might liberate desire in ways that are productive of difference outside the realm of the already-known.

In closing, I argue that my proposal toward affective sociomaterialisation may provide some concrete answers to Barad's lingering Cheshire cat, the epitaph that I opened this chapter with. That is, answers *to the material nature of discursive practices* which may inform new knowledges about the production of subjectivity beyond humancentric and individualist perspectives. An explicit focus on ontogenetic matters may also prove generative within outdoor environments where the unique material and spatial affordances might be productive, or not, of subjectivities that challenge determinate ways of being. In the next chapter I assemble a methodological proposal toward exploring how one might conduct research on the basis of the theoretical inquiry I have outlined thus far.

4 Chapter Four: Toward a sociomaterial methodological inquiry for exploring children's subjectivities

4.1 Introduction

The shift from viewing the world as a set of stable fixed entities toward a more entangled, processual and relational understanding presents both opportunities and challenges for qualitative research inquiry. The purpose of this chapter is to build on the theoretical proposals put forward in Chapter Three and assemble a sociomaterial inquiry for exploring children's subjectivities in practice. As a reminder, the three research aims that guide this study are:

1. To advance a metaphysics of sociomaterialism toward understanding children's identity formation
2. To examine the potential for outdoor early childhood environments to facilitate thinking otherwise beyond deterministic identity formations.
3. To evaluate how a sociomaterial framework toward understanding children's identity information can assist future learning and teaching.

I begin this chapter by detailing my research design. This section includes a discussion of my decision to adopt an ethnographic mode of inquiry, and also details coronavirus-related issues surrounding access to the nursery setting that I eventually chose for my fieldwork. Since a full sociomaterial ethnographic account of my time within this setting will be detailed in the following two chapters, here I will focus primarily on the processes of gaining consent and ethical approval. In the middle section of the chapter, I discuss how I have assembled my sociomaterial inquiry in terms of methodology. This part begins by locating this particular sociomaterial research assemblage where I consider implications for thinking about researcher subjectivity and objectivity, extending on my brief coverage in the introductory chapter. I introduce the 'postqualitative turn' (Lather and St. Pierre, 2013; St. Pierre, 2019) and consider distinctions from more traditional forms of qualitative research methodology that I myself have been trained in and continue to wrestle with. I then introduce video technologies as a technique alongside a traditional research diary. The final part of this chapter introduces what is to come in Chapters Five and Six, specifically in terms of how I intend to present the data I have gathered through differing act of research-creation.

4.2 Research design

4.2.1 *On ethnography*

Within the early childhood research field, qualitative ethnography is widely recognised as a particularly useful approach for gathering data with children as a means to become embedded within, and gain closer proximity to, their lifeworlds (Farrell, Kagan and Tisdall, 2016; Christensen and James, 2017; Dennis and Huf, 2020). Since the focus of this study is on children's subjectivities within outdoor environments, I therefore believe that ethnography would be an entirely appropriate strategy for gathering data with the children. There is, however, a question of how traditional ethnography may be interpreted within a sociomaterial framework. As Tuck and McKenzie (2015) comment, the term ethnography literally means 'the study of culture', which implicitly implies a separation from the study of nature (and the natural sciences, more generally). Conventionally, traditional ethnography is understood as a practice with *human* participants (Miller and Brewer, 2003). Yet, my sociomaterial proposal troubles this perception since, as Chapters Five and Six will demonstrate, I am keen to foreground the role of the material world in the information of children's subjectivities. It might therefore be concluded that ethnography appears a clumsy fit within sociomaterial research methodologies and related attempts to reassert the inseparability of culture and nature within a monist ontology. However, as Fox and Alldred (2015) note in their review of sociomaterial research, ethnography still broadly remains the favoured methodology of choice. Given my sociomaterial commitment, this project does not fit neatly into traditional ethnography, yet across the literature there is plenty of precedent for a study of this kind to remain ethnographically inspired. For instance, I could feasibly turn to any one from 'sociomaterialist ethnography' (Schadler, 2017), 'diffractive ethnography' (Gullion, 2018), 'sociomaterial ethnography' (Niemimaa, 2014), 'ethnographic multi-sensory mapping' (Renold and Mellor, 2013), or 'posthumanist institutional ethnography' (Taylor and Fairchild, 2020). There are similarities between all of these and, in any case, for those unfamiliar with sociomaterial inquiry, retaining this term provides a semblance of association. Therefore, I will retain my use of ethnography as yet another act of conceptual pickpocketing (Braidotti, 2002) as I assemble my sociomaterial inquiry.

4.2.2 *Negotiating access to a nursery setting*

This research project was originally designed in partnership with Early Years Scotland (2021), a third-sector membership and service-delivery organisation. This enabled the opportunity to access potential nursery sites through their membership base as part of my sampling strategy. Since this study was intended to be ethnographic in nature, a single nursery setting in the vein of a 'case study' approach would have been appropriate in light of the period of time that I had planned to

spend at the setting (Creswell, 2013; Buscatto, 2018). A case study approach enables the researcher to gather in-depth qualitative data within a single bounded system (a nursery setting) and go into greater detail than if they were to cover multiple cases (Creswell, 2013). My intention had been to spend four to six weeks “hang(ing)-out” (Rosaldo, in Geertz, 1998) at a single setting, which I believed would provide ample opportunity to generate sufficient data. Therefore, I make no explicit claims to the generalisability of this study across more than one setting. Rather, the intention was to study an *example* which carries value in own its right (Massumi, 2002; Gale, 2018, pp. 168-169).

The process of selecting a nursery setting was underway prior to the coronavirus pandemic at beginning of 2020. The initial invitation to take part in this study was sent through Early Years Scotland to private nursery settings; out of school care settings; individual practitioners (who would then pass the information on to their workplace); and voluntary ELC settings. Each was invited to express interest via email response, following which I would reply on the basis of certain criteria: location, access and the material environment itself. Regarding the location of the setting and the distance that I would have to travel each day, I was keen to avoid settings where I might have had to stay overnight as this would have been prohibitive due to the financial implications of finding suitable accommodation. Due to the scope and duration of doctoral level research, a low-cost strategy was preferred. Further, since I was planning to spend consecutive eight-hour days within the setting, anywhere beyond one or two hours travel by car each-way would have put a strain on my own physical wellbeing during this fieldwork phase. My preference was therefore to find a setting within one to two hours by car or public transport.

Ease of access was a second factor in terms of how often I would be allowed into the setting to gather data with the children. For instance, I was mindful from my own experience as a practitioner of whole afternoons that would be given over to external music and dances classes, in addition to regularly scheduled trips outside of the setting. Since I was interested in ordinary play encounters, my preference had been to select a setting where children’s engagement in these groups was at a minimum so that I could maximise my opportunities to gather data. My final criteria were the particular material affordances within the space that may have proved generative in line with my research aims which I would be able to witness during initial visits to each setting. This was based on my sociomaterial sensibilities around ‘tuning in’ (Stewart, 2010) to particular things that sparked my interest, or that I felt had an affect on me. This particular criteria might be read as antithetical to research objectivity in selecting an appropriate sample. However, as I have discussed in Chapter One ([see page 8](#)) and will examine further later on in this chapter ([see page 88](#)) the need to achieve objective truth is not a desired outcome of this study. Rooted within a positivist research paradigm,

feminist scholarship has long noted how claims to objectivity are rarely free from the values and intentions of the researcher (Harding, 2004). In this initial phase I received a total of nine responses from interested settings who were willing to find out more about this research project.

Since my *prima facie* assumption was that I would receive interest from indoor sites only, four expressions of interest came from fully outdoor settings, which I was aware were particularly popular in Scotland compared to the rest of the UK. However, because of the aforementioned location and transport costs, and as all of these sites were typically a lot further away and would have needed significant financial resources, I excluded outdoor environments from my list at this time. Of the remaining half, a further nursery was excluded on the basis of being a drop-in centre, which produced concerns about the size of the space and about regular attendance of the children. This left me with four settings to choose from during February and March 2020. I conducted preliminary visits to each of the four nurseries to gain a sense of the space and provide an opportunity for any questions or concerns from the staff teams to be answered. Though I had intended to visit all four settings, I stopped after visiting the third setting as the fourth was located two hours away and had much shorter opening hours than the rest.

Of the remaining three, one setting had fewer children present each day than the rest and had external activities on their busiest days, meaning that children would not be in their main nursery space, and I would have had to have gained further consent if I had wished to observe these external sessions. This would have presented a delay to my fieldwork that I would have preferred to avoid, therefore excluding this setting from my shortlist. Of the remaining two, both would have been appropriate settings for my research. On my visit to the setting I did not chose, it was apparent to me during the time that I spent within the room that I would have no issues with being witness to certain heteronormative and gendered practices. Some of the material displays, namely a large wall mural celebrating Valentine's Day in its most traditional (heteronormative) sense, caught my interest immediately, as did the children's choice of dress-up for World Book Day. However, it was the second setting, Chestnut nursery, that caught my interest most as it was larger in terms of physical space and hosted more children across each day. This setting also had a purpose-built climbing wall room adjacent to their main space that the children would access on a regular basis, which I believed based on the existing literature (Holland, 2003; Kilvington and Wood, 2016) may have been insightful in terms of displays of risk according to the gender of the children with this space.

4.2.3 *Coronavirus disruption*

As I wrote in the foreword to this thesis, it seems particularly apposite that something which so clearly demonstrates the fuzzy boundaries between animate and inanimate (gaseous) life (Villarreal, 2004; Chen, 2021), and also the affective nature of non-human animate and inanimate life (Fullagar and Pavlidis, 2020; Blackman, 2021), would significantly disrupt this study. In March 2020, after I had visited all three settings and come to a final decision, the process for gaining parent and carer consent was planned to begin with my key contact at Chestnut. A total of 53 parental and carer information sheets were distributed, however it was at this point which I experienced a significant delay in beginning my fieldwork.⁸ Initially, this had no impact on my studies, though as the virus arrived into Europe and then the UK it became increasingly apparent that I would not be able to continue with my fieldwork. Schools and nurseries were closed to all, with the exception of children whose parents and carers were key workers and children deemed ‘at risk’ (Scottish Government, 2020b). I was under instruction from my doctoral college to postpone any impending fieldwork until further notice. The nursery setting closed in line with government guidance and did not re-open until 10th August 2020. However, even when the setting did re-open only small groups of children and limited adults were permitted, with no external visits to the nursery. This, and the guidance around social distancing within indoor settings, presented a significant challenge to my original fieldwork plan.

I could have stayed with Chestnut nursery and held out until it was safe for me to return to the setting to begin fieldwork. However, because I would then be entering the third and final year of my PhD without any empirical data, as well as the university stipulations relating to how long it should take to complete this research project (three years in the UK), it was decided between myself and my supervisory team that an alternative option should be pursued. As others have noted, accessing a research site is not always a straightforward process and may require the researcher to amend their sampling strategy to overcome any challenges (Payne and Payne, 2004; Matthews and Ross, 2010). One advantageous aspect of the pandemic had been an increased focus on outdoor play, with a various articles and research papers published citing the many benefits of the spaces for young children during this period (Howe *et al.*, 2020; Quay *et al.*, 2020; Rowley, 2020;

⁸ Coronavirus, and more precisely Covid-19. is/was the name for a family of viruses, and a virus can be defined as a small infectious agent that can only replicate inside the cells of another organism, human and/or animal. Viruses are particularly interesting since among the scientific community it is thought that they can be situated inbetween the boundaries of living and non-living organisms. On their own, they cannot replicate, but once within the living cells of another organism they deeply affect the behaviour of their hosts (Villarreal, 2004). The virus therefore does well to challenge straightforward understandings of non-human animate and inanimate life

Alden, 2021). I therefore decided to revise the inclusion criteria as part of my sampling strategy to include outdoor settings following these justifications:

- Fully outdoor environments, because of Covid-19 had, and still have, taken on a greater significance as far as the obvious ventilation they provide means that these spaces are safer for children compared to primarily indoor settings.
- Outdoor nurseries are generally significantly larger in physical size. This means that I would be able to physically distance myself from the children, the staff and still gather good quality data at the same time.
- While outdoor nurseries had originally not been considered within the scope of this project, this was not because they were incompatible with my aims.
- I have an existing relationship with several settings who had expressed an initial interest in this study.

I approached all four outdoor settings who had initially expressed interest to explain the current situation and ask whether they would be open to the possibility of working with me for this research project. Two settings replied. I then visited both. However only one was deemed appropriate due to the size of the space and the number of children in attendance. Additionally, although I was keen to work with this remaining setting, Oak Tree nursery, uncertainty remained around my initial strategy to only focus on one setting in light of the coronavirus. This was primarily because individual settings were at risk of closing at any point due to local outbreaks and the fluctuating presence of restrictions that forced some areas to lockdown entirely, only allowing travel for essential reasons. This setting had also closed during the summer of 2020 and was still in the process of settling in new children and remapping their space. Henceforth, since at this point I had exhausted all expressions of interest through Early Years Scotland, I decided to broaden my recruitment strategy again to other settings that may be willing to take part in my research. I adopted a purposive sample strategy that involved deliberate selection of people associated with potential settings that could facilitate my research (Flick, 2018). While I had only moved to Scotland within the past two years, this was possible through the connections I made across various early childhood-related events during my time here. In her guidance on recruiting participants, Eide (in Given, 2008, pp. 743-744), notes the value of the researcher building good networks within their community which might then assist their research. I therefore reached out to two further settings that I believed may interested on the basis of an existing relationship with the gatekeepers, one of which replied and invited me to visit.

Wood Fire nursery, the setting I eventually came to choose, was advantageous for a number of reasons in line with my revised criteria. Firstly, it had remained open throughout the pandemic. This meant that I could visit the setting straight away to get a sense of the space and how it worked on a routine day. Secondly, while both this setting and the Oak Tree nursery were over an hour away, the location of Wood Fire meant that accommodation would be much easier to organise.⁹ Accommodation in the area surrounding Oak Tree setting was sparse. I would have had to have faced the prospect of long days travelling back and forth. Finally, conversations during my initial visits to Wood Fire led to me believe that I would be able to have a strong relationship with the setting manager who was fully aligned with the intentions of the project and keen to support with any further challenges that may arise. Creswell (2013) notes that a strong relationship between the researcher and the lead gatekeeper can be crucial in maintaining important ethical values of trust and integrity. However, on the basis of continual uncertainty with regard to lockdown legislation and nursery closures, the intention at this point was to agree to gather data from both settings. I would stay at Wood Fire for four weeks, before isolating according to government guidelines and then repeating the process with the Oak Tree nursery. An ethics amendment was submitted and accepted by the UWS Ethics Committee, and I was able to restart the process of gathering consent ahead of fieldwork towards the beginning of November 2020. This represented a delay to my fieldwork of roughly six months. In the end, my plan to use both settings did not materialise as Covid-19 again affected the duration of my fieldwork two weeks into my time at Wood Fire. Therefore, having reviewed the video and textual data that I had gathered, I made the decision to return to my original strategy of using a single setting.

As I will come to reflect upon in the subsequent chapter, entirely outdoor nursery settings remain relatively rare in Scotland despite the heavy emphasis on outdoor play within policy and guidance documents. Hence for reasons of anonymity it is not appropriate to provide in-depth detail of the wider community context. In fairly broad terms, however, it is an area marked by an older demographic population, a higher life expectancy compared to the rest of Scotland and paucity of racial diversity. Wood Fire itself is not within an area of relative deprivation, according to the most recent Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation statistics.¹⁰ However, not all children who attend the nursery reside within the data zone for this setting and the surrounding areas illustrate several disparities between each other in terms of outcomes for health, education, employment and housing.

⁹ In light of the pandemic, I received financial support from my university to be able revise my research project and widen the scope of potential settings.

¹⁰ Precise source is not revealed to maintain anonymity.

4.2.4 *Ethics*

Initial ethical approval for this study was granted in November 2019 by UWS Ethics Committee. In this section I discuss some of the challenges around the sensitivity of my research focus, the use of a video recorder, and my decision to apply a sticker system to map who I would be able to film.

As I moved through to the ethics application phase prior to negotiating access, and while my research focused was still oriented around heteronormativity, I was aware of the perceived nature of engaging with research on gender and sexuality in early childhood (Robinson, 2013). The discourse on young children's (physical and social) bodies, and the sociomaterial concept of heteronormativity entering in relation with video technologies seems to produce a kind of affective anxiety about what I might have been seeking to understand in this research thesis. This was unsurprising to me given what the existing literature documents about such issues being posited as risky and/or as threatening to the (hetero)normative order of things (Robinson, 2013). My ethics submission was also situated within a broader period where protests surrounding the question of whether to include LGBTQ+ inclusive education in primary schools were highly publicised across the media (Parveen, 2019a).¹¹ I therefore endeavoured to be as transparent as I could in my purpose and rationale for this project with potential participants. To this end, I created distinct parent/carer (see **Appendix 1**) and practitioner (see **Appendix 3**) information packs, as well as producing a child consent book (See **Appendix 5**). The parent/carer information packs were distributed physically to parents during pick up and drop-off times, whereas staff were forwarded an email with a Pdf. copy and an accompanying link to the consent form. The child consent book was particularly useful as a material resource because it allowed me to introduce myself in a friendly, welcoming manner (Te One, 2011). My plan was to introduce myself and the video recorder (see [page 90](#) for further discussion of video) during a circle or group time, and 'settle in' over a few days to allow myself time to get to know the space and gain a sense of the daily routine. I knew that the video recorder would draw children's attention as a new material thing, so spending time explaining the purpose of my presence and showing them how it looks was a plan that created an opening for a relationship to develop (Farrell, Kagan and Tisdall, 2016). There are a number of benefits to video recording. Though I was also aware that it may be perceived as obtrusive (Heath,

¹¹ Though, while I recognise the current broader context in which the PhD is situated, I continue to align myself with the existing scholarship in advocating for a refusal of the continued prescription of sexuality with risk as typically implied through ethical judgements surrounding sensitivity and embarrassment. As Robinson (2013, p. 80) puts it clearly: "Risks are constructed regulators; they are the potential consequences of the normalizing judgments, which are inherent in the societal gaze, and which discourage people from stepping outside the boundaries of socially-sanctioned values and practices".

Hindmarsh and Luff, 2010; Fler and Ridgway, 2014). I sought to address this within my ethics submission, writing:

I recognise that (the use of the video recorder) may be perceived as intrusive, however the fact that the video recording device is highly visible enables children to understand it clearly as an observational tool. I intend to draw techniques from others who have used video recordings to ensure my filming remains grounded in ethical practice (Fler and Ridgway, 2014; Heath, Hindmarsh and Luff, 2010). This will take the form of avoiding filming any situations when the children did not appear to have noticed my presence and responding to any situation when it is clear my presence is unwelcome or appears imposing. I would draw on my experience as a nursery practitioner to remain alert for such moments.

In addition to introducing the video recorder to children at the outset, allowing them to ask any questions, and avoiding whenever it was evident that my presence was not welcome, the child consent book also provided a means for children to signal their consent (Te One, 2011). I encouraged them to signal either a thumbs up or a thumbs down depending on whether I could record them during their play. It was impossible to know how many children I would have consent to gather data with, and different children attended Wood Fire on different days, so the ethics submission further provided an opportunity to carefully plan for any instances where I may need to be mindful of who I had consent to film. Initially I decided to opt for a sticker system to track who had given consent, and which may have also enabled the children to signal consent each day (Crowley and Callanan, 1998; Kyritsi, 2019). In the ethics submission I stated:

For children who I do not have consent to film, I will make every effort to ensure they are not recorded throughout my data. At the start of each fieldwork session. I intend to note which children are present within the nursery room including who I do and do not have consent to film. For those whom I have consent I intend to employ a sticker system to make them as clearly identifiable as possible. Those who consent will receive a sticker, all stickers will be identical to minimise any chance of conflict over colour preference. At the end of each fieldwork session, rather than at the end of all sessions, I will review all footage and remove any children filmed who I do not have consent for.

My initial decision to use stickers was not one I had reached easily; I was all too aware of the lure that stickers provide for children and their problematic relation with doing ‘good’ things (for example, through sticker charts) (Tobin, 1997; Bradbury, 2011). There was a tension in that the children whose parents and carers had given consent could be seen as being ‘rewarded’ over other children whose parents and carers had not consented to their participation (Tobin, 1997; Bradbury, 2011). The stickers, as material things, would potentially affect some bodies more than others. Nevertheless, they remained a useful option in supporting the practical matter of avoiding filming

children who had not provided consent and I hoped that over time the significance of the stickers would diminish. However, in the end all but one parent provided consent and this system was not necessary because the staff team supported me in ensuring that I avoided this single child.

The intention for the first part of this chapter has been to outline my research design in terms of the process of gaining access and coming to choose a single nursery setting. I have explained how the coronavirus provoked a shift toward a fully outdoor nursery environment and also outlined the ethics process for consent, video recording and, though not needed in the end, who I could and could not film. In the next section I assemble a sociomaterial inquiry through introducing and exploring the scholarship emergent through the ‘postqualitative turn’.

4.3 Producing a sociomaterial inquiry

4.3.1 Learning from the postqualitative turn

In recent years, a considerable amount of literature has emerged to consider how traditional qualitative inquiry might align with sociomaterial philosophies and attempts to better understand the relationality of non-human and human practices (Pierre, 2011; MacLure, 2013b; Lather and St. Pierre, 2013; St. Pierre, 2018; Koro-Ljungberg *et al.*, 2019). According to St. Pierre (2018), traditional qualitative methods have been treated as *doxa* within the social sciences for their ability to gain ‘deeper’ understandings of the social, as opposed to quantitative methods. Yet, it is this unwavering faith in qualitative research methods in the social sciences that makes it difficult to remember that, from the beginning, the idea of qualitative research itself is something that was ‘made up’, with distinctly humanist epistemological and ontological commitments (Lather and St. Pierre, 2013; Kuby, 2017; Koro-Ljungberg, Carlson and Montana, 2018). As Lather and St. Pierre (2013, p. 631) remind us, “the theory of representation used in humanist qualitative inquiry was not always thinkable ... so there is a precedent for thinking other theories”.

As is the case with most of the work I engage with in this thesis, there is difficulty in speaking of a coherent postqualitative turn.¹² Tracing the lineage of this scholarship is an equally complicated challenge, and it might reasonably be conceived that some scholars, especially in the arts, were already engaged with a number of the core tenets, namely a critique of humanism and the linguistic

¹² There is also little consensus on the correct spelling of this term. It is also widely referred to as post-qualitative, post qualitative, or (post)qualitative. While I am strongly tempted by the latter, this is only truly due to my taste for parentheses and unconventional things. Mayes (2019) uses (post)qualitative in recognition that this work still falls within the qualitative tradition, however I think it is necessary to go further and argue that this form of inquiry goes beyond, and can be understood as distinct from, traditional qualitative research, insofar as it aims to address things that are typically unintelligible in conventional accounts. My reason for the portmanteau is consistent with my usage of sociomaterialism, despite the hyphenated version being the most common.

turn, before it was first coined. This is inferred by St Pierre (2013), who is widely credited for coining this term. For her, the introduction of such a term is necessary in the context of increasing regulation around qualitative research methodologies. St Pierre (2013, p. 489) cites the case of the National Research Council in the United States, a congressional organisation who mandated “experimental research and, preferably, randomised controlled trials as the gold standard” during the early 2000s. For her, this has had significant implications insofar as qualitative research was essentially denigrated for a perceived lack of rigour in favour of positivist approaches. In the British contemporary context, such a claim resonates in light of the UK Government’s approach toward researching experiences of racism. As I note elsewhere (Tembo, 2021a), within the widely criticised government report published by the Commission on Race and Ethnic Disparities, (2021), there is an implicit preference for quantifiable data at the expense of individual experience. St Pierre’s (2013) contention is therefore that the increasing dismissal of qualitative research had corresponded with increasing discipline, regulation and standardisation of this line of inquiry. Against this, several potential avenues are explored regarding how it might be possible to reimagine research in social sciences, of which the concepts of Deleuze and Guattari (1987) feature. Ultimately, St. Pierre concludes on the position that any reader engaging with Deleuze and Guattari’s metaphysical approach would soon recognise a fundamental incompatibility with conventional (humanist) qualitative inquiry, hence the need for *post* qualitative inquiry informed by these philosophies.

Following the conception of this term just a decade ago, a number of scholars (Johansson, 2015; Taylor, 2016b; Rousell, 2019; Kuntz, 2020) including St Pierre herself (2017; 2018; 2019; 2020) and with others (Lather and St. Pierre, 2013; St. Pierre, Jackson and Mazzei, 2016; Taguchi and St. Pierre, 2017) have since come to clarify the overall tenets of this approach. In broad terms, beginning with an onto-epistemological commitment to inquiry, postqualitative inquiry seeks to rework traditional ideas of voice and data, as well as the binary distinctions between researchers and researched, and instead foreground a more relational analysis toward inquiry. Postqualitative inquiry is not merely a riff on traditional methodologies. Neither should it be understood as qualitative research stirred in with the additional concepts of assemblages or affect. The shift toward ‘inquiry’ as an alternative to methodology is significant because inquiry does not begin with a pre-existing research framework that one can follow step-by-step, like a cookbook, therefore producing ‘valid’ data. Cutting across binary logics of this kind works to refuse the implied linearity and systematic nature of the resulting empirical work. As an alternative, postqualitative inquiry is said to follow an entirely different path, with the potential to create new knowledges that may appear unintelligible in traditional frameworks of analysis (St. Pierre, 2019).

4.3.2 *Decentring voice in the assemblage*

An engagement with postqualitative inquiry further troubles an unproblematic privileging of the voice over materiality, and more precisely the longstanding notion that language can accurately represent the truth of consciousness and reality (MacLure, 2013b; Mazzei, 2016; Mazzei and Jackson, 2016). Recognising the insufficiency of voice within a more relational framework makes it impossible to conceive of the spoken word as the harbinger of truth and experience. Rather in the postqualitative mode, voice is distributed across, and emergent through, non-human and human bodies in the assemblage. As Maclure (2013b, p. 660) writes:

Language is deposed from its god-like centrality in the construction and regulation of worldly affairs, to become one element in a manifold of forces and intensities that are moving, connecting and diverging.

To be clear, this is not to dismiss the role of language entirely, but rather to resituate it to consider the relational materialist ontology within which both the social and material reside: it is a posthuman performativity (Barad, 2003). Voice might emerge through, for example, any number of things, spaces, affects, bodies, discourses, texts, and theory within an assemblage. In considering the size of certain assemblages for analysis, it is useful to remind ourselves of Deleuze and Guattari's (1987) assertion that the smallest unit is the always an assemblage rather than any individual person. Their claim is similar to that made by Barad (2007), who argues that attention must be paid to 'phenomena' as the basic ontological units that emerge through material-discursive relations. This decentring also works to reconceive the binary distinction between intelligible speech and silence (Maclure, 2009). The silence in-between words itself has something to say and can often be heard palpably but can sometimes be left out of the research findings or becomes synonymous with *not* knowing, especially in more positivist-oriented accounts with strict boundaries and definitions of validity. Instead, MacLure (2009, p. 97) puts forward a strategy for an inquiry into voice that would attend to emotions and features such as "laughter, mimicry, mockery, silence, stuttering, tears, slyness, shyness, shouts, jokes, lies, irrelevance, partiality, (and) inconsistency". Maclure's claim appears entirely justified in the early childhood context, where my own experience tells me that laughter, tears, shouts, and irrelevance all feature on a daily basis. Postqualitative-inspired inquiry might therefore be conceived as a productive approach within this research context. Also taking this position, Osgood and Robinson (2019, p. 27) write:

For early childhood researchers, this is not a radical departure from the form that many ethnographic studies in early childhood contexts take, where it is nearly impossible not to become entangled in the ebb and flow of daily life, routines and messy unpredictable

happenings that are bodily, affective and material. But working from a feminist new materialist framework requires that we immerse ourselves more fully in the intensities, flows, rhythms, affects and forces of children's entanglements with space, place and materiality.

Notably, what makes a productive synthesis between Maclure and Osgood and Robinson here is their reading of the *affective* nature of research practice. As I explained in the previous chapter, affect figures as a means to move away from back-end processes of signification, coding, and representation, toward a focus on what Simpson and Brigstocke, (2019, p. 2) describe as “the processes of transition one body goes through when encountering another and the implications such encounters have for a body's capacity to act”. An affective, relational reading of power relations within early childhood might therefore illustrate the ways that children's subjectivities surface beyond linguistic accounts of what children say and attend to processes of emergence.

4.3.3 *Troubling subjectivity and objectivity*

The call for objectivity within research inquiry is the principle that there should be a level of distance between the researcher and their object of inquiry, and that the researcher should aim to conduct the research free of personal prejudice, or any moral or cultural values (Payne and Payne, 2004; Williams, 2016). Yet what exactly this level of distance should be, and how the researcher might go about separating themselves from their research is a contested issue. Granted, most researchers today believe that true objectivity is impossible, where claims to this effect might be best understood through what Haraway (1991, p. 189) terms the illusory “god-trick” of seeing everything from nowhere. In the sociomaterialist and postqualitative scholarship, objectivity is something of a dirty word, not least for its adherence to humanist and colonial logics. For Braidotti (2013), while such claims to objectivity are intended to offer neutrality, this masks the fact that throughout much of Western history, supposedly ‘objective’ research methodologies have overwhelmingly acted in the interests of the white heterosexual cisgendered able-bodied man. In many ways, the figure of the white man is synonymous with the principle of the State philosophy that I discussed in Chapter Three. Ahmed (2014b) suggests that, when we talk of “white men”, a kind of institution is being described. For her, if it is recognised that the term institution can be described as “persistent structure or mechanism of social order governing the behaviour of a set of individuals within a given community” (Ahmed, 2014b, p. para 4), then speaking of white men *as* an institution names the mechanisms that have been set up to maintain that structure. Thus, I follow others in an affirmative rejection of objectivity and instead name that my own subjectivity leaks throughout this research process, from my research aims through to the proposed theoretical

approach and methods of gathering data. For, Mazzei (2013, p. 735), who is playing on a passage from Deleuze and Guattari (1987, p. 23):

There can no longer be a division between a field of reality (what we ask, what our participants tell us, and the places we inhabit), a field of representation (research narratives constructed after the interview), and a field of subjectivity (participants and researchers).

Acknowledging the need to challenge claims to objectivity, then, necessitates a mode of ethical accountability that refuses the principles of distance and flattens the binary separation between researcher and researched. It is this **research-assemblage** that produces the capacities for a doctoral research study where I am fully immersed in the processes of becoming. As an element in the research, I recognise myself as both affecting and affected by the research process. It therefore matters to note that I myself am not free from the constraints of identity that I am writing against within this thesis. My personal and professional history, the social categories of which I am part of and those to which I lay claim, as well as my values and beliefs, inform the construction of my subjectivity as a socially and materially mediated process (Braidotti, 2002). I am defined through the relations I form with others, which in-form the production of this thesis.

I come to this research as a Black cisgender heterosexual man from a working-class family within a predominantly white British community. I relate with some of these categories much more than others. For instance, insofar as I have long been heavily critical of the gender binary and actively try to disassociate myself from aspects of what I deem to be ‘hegemonic’ masculinity (Connell, 2005), the term ‘cisgender’ is one that I continually feel to be an arbitrary marker of my identity. I do not wish to be constrained by my gender, in the same way that I wish to think-otherwise of children beyond the many determinacies placed upon them. This is not to say that I am therefore gender-diverse, or non-binary, but rather to resist the categorisation of gender *per se*. Nor, of course, do I care for the violent representations of Black people that remain prevalent, where our proximity to death exists as normalised within a context where Black bodies are routinely dehumanised and over-regulated with racialised power.¹³ My naming of Black implies more than the violence accorded by way of phenotype and is a commitment to the liberatory politics that tie into skin colour (Harney and Moten, 2013; Andrews, 2018; Keeling, 2019). This is much more than simply a category of my identity. Both my decisions to centre my Blackness and refuse the

¹³ Clearly, my current and future academic roles as a lecturer within the university complicate a fixed conception of class, however it would be wrong that say that I am entirely insulated from racism. “Wealth and other forms of status do not “whiten”, which is to say that, while certain economic and social privileges beyond race may make life easier, these advantages do not prevent a person from experiencing the multiples forms of racism (Vila and Avery-Natale, 2020: :03)”.

gender binary are therefore heavily political and contribute toward the formation of this thesis. Furthermore, it matters to note that I have been involved in various aspects of early childhood education for the past decade, as a practitioner, a family support worker, an advocate for the profession, and now as a research student. I am attuned to the affective encounters presented here by virtue of my own experiences. Ultimately, this is an approach unconcerned with ‘getting things right’, ‘unmasking hidden agendas’, ‘truth-finding’ or ‘exposure’, and oriented more toward what might be termed as a ‘diffractive’ form of inquiry. Barad (2007, p. 94) explains that this approach:

Allows [the researcher] to examine in detail important philosophical issues such as the conditions for the possibility, or objectivity, the nature of measurement, the nature of meaning making, the conditions for intelligibility, the nature of causality and identity, and the relationship between discursive practices and the material worlds

A diffractive inquiry acknowledges that knowing is never done in isolation, is never objective, but is always affected by the coming together of different forces. It argues that we cannot know the world by studying it at a distance, we know because we are part of its very becoming.

4.4 Toward a multi-sensory inquiry

4.4.1 Video recording

Literally moving things - things that are in motion and that are defined by their capacity to affect and to be affected – these have to be mapped through different coexisting forms of compositions, habituation and event.

(Stewart, 2007, p. 04)

As I approached the fieldwork phase of this study, I continued to perceive text-based methods as valuable alongside visual modes of presentation. I intended to produce a detailed research diary to track what happens as I am in the field, with field notes written as ‘in the moment’ as possible. Though, ‘what happens’ will accommodate a focus on the emergent relations between social and material bodies, rather than any individual child or practitioner. At the same time, this sociomaterial framework guiding my study has compelled me to consider how else it might be possible to understand the ontogenetic nature of childhood subjectivities, and how else I can generate new knowledges into the ways that ‘literally moving things’, as Stewart (2007) puts it in the quotation above, assemble together to enable or constrain certain relations. For researchers aiming to attend to discursive and material relational elements, video methods are increasingly being deployed as a way to supplement linguistic interaction in the early childhood context to better understand how

bodies and things are set in motion, as well as to understand how particular events unfold within an always-already multisensorial environment (de Freitas, 2015; Magnusson, 2018; Holmes, 2020; MacRae and MacLure, 2021).

On a practical level, video technologies have become much more accessible in recent decades, parallel to the now ubiquitous nature of smartphones and media devices in contemporary capitalist societies that saturate and animate existence. Typically, the use of video methods in social constructionist research with young children has assumed a primary focus on the child as the sole unit of analysis; the material spaces are acknowledged, but since the focus tends to remain on the child's voice, they are rarely given the same ontological status as human bodies. A sociomaterial use of video differs by attending to the relational elements constructing an assemblage of human and non-human things (Staunæs and Kofoed, 2014). Moving beyond purely textual representations of data can provide a means to witness the affective social and material events that populate worlds. As Whatmore (2006, p. 606) argues:

There is an urgent need to supplement the familiar repertoire of humanist methods that rely on generating talk and text with experimental practices that amplify other sensory, bodily and affective registers and extend the company and modality of what constitutes a research subject.

The use of video therefore serves a useful role through their ability to go beyond words and recognise the non-human and more-than-human things that constitute processes of becoming in situ, *par le milieu*. Given that the aesthetics of spaces are not easily mapped through textual description and therefore tend to elude the analytic gaze, the visual affordances of video have the potential to highlight the ways in which materials themselves enable and constrain certain practices. Video can serve as a way of (re)witnessing various affective knowledges, skills, and embodied practices (Simpson and Brigstocke, 2019). Within this study, video might allow me to pause and search for the ways that things “hang together”, in Mol's (2002, p. 143) terms (as assemblages, in Deleuze and Guattari's (1987) terms), something that, while still possible with textual methods, is made much easier with video.

Renold and Mellor's (2013) research, which I discuss in the previous chapter ([see page 72](#)), is a useful illustration of how video can work to account for more than textual representation. Their findings from a research project exploring children's gendered relations use video technologies to illustrate affective encounters that foreground sound, body, and objects. Their analysis highlights the powerful forces at play that work to shape bodily capacities, pointing to how bodies are always ‘becoming’ in relation to other bodies and affecting how the body is permeable to the influence of

others. In their own words, their inquiry is an attempt to understand “an expanded epistemology of the social world – one that is open to the multiple events, actions and relations of bodies and objects as experienced through the oral and aural, sight, touch, taste and emotion” (Renold and Mellor, 2013, p. 37). Therefore, paying attention to discourses and materials in relation provides an opening to focus on the spatial nature of events and also to decentre an anthropocentric perspective toward the individual child.

Sociomaterial applications of video methods sit in contrast with early uses in a second way. Traditionally, video devices have been employed to ‘capture’ objective representations of natural behaviour and are often assumed to enact a form of distance, and therefore a binary separation, between the researcher and their data. This is because the video devices themselves are often seen as neutral objects that can record events objectively. However, as Waters and Waite (2016, p. 117) argue, the opposite is often true, visual methods “enact our intentions, moral choices, social position and cultural biases, and are bound in the time, place and context in which they are used, leaving impressions on participants and the environment long after research projects have finished”. Just as I situate myself within the broader research assemblage, my own physical body necessarily becomes part of the assemblage as I position myself as video-camera-researcher in the nursery assemblage. In any case, as I will discuss in the following chapters, my Black male body in the context of a predominantly white setting would hardly go unnoticed. This shift away from objectivity is illustrated well in Pink’s (2013, p. 35) definitions of visual ethnography:

Visual ethnography, as I interpret it, does not claim to produce an objective or truthful account of reality, but should aim to offer versions of ethnographers’ experience of reality that are as loyal as possible to the context, the embodied, sensory and affective experiences, and the negotiations and intersubjectivities through which the knowledge was produced.

On these terms, what gets produced from video cannot be seen as an innocent form of communication. I borrow Barad’s (2007) concept of the apparatus of observation to think through the video device not as a passive observing instrument but rather as a specific material-discursive practice that is in-formative of matter and meaning. Matter here can be understood in a double sense of ‘physical matter’ and ‘what comes to matter’ through what Barad (2007, p. 140) describes as ‘**agential cuts**’. Apparatuses such as video recorders enact agential cuts through their formation of what is included and excluded from meaning, or through what comes to matter. What *kind* of video recording device I use therefore also became significant in terms of the capacities of angle and movement that it would enable me to work through.

While I might have chosen to use a fixed camera to record data, my concern was that this alone would have restricted my movement (Knoblauch, Schnettler and Tuma, 2018). My preference was for a roving camera, such as an iPad or something similar, which would allow me to pay attention to the ways that bodies move through spaces and be responsive to fleeting moments, body movements and happenings that may occur. A higher quality video recording would also produce better still images. Mengis, Nicolini and Gorli (2016, p. 307) draw a similar conclusion in their overview of video recording practices. They point out that “aiming to further a processual or sociomaterial account of organizational practices (e.g., in strategy), the scholar will be better served by the Roving Point-of-View pointing to the continuous unfolding and relationality of activities, material artefacts, and human actors”.

The ability to move around the space also prompted me to look beyond specific sites within the nursery setting and embrace the uncertainty of not knowing where or when interesting encounters may occur between children and their material relations. I had no interest in making myself stay in one single place or focusing on any one particular area. Rather I saw myself as simply “hang(ing)-out” (Geertz, 1998) during ‘free-play’ times, where children are free to play where they choose in the nursery, and also being present at other times when more structured activities are taking place, for example circle time. Of course, I knew I would not be invisible in these situations, I intended to position myself as an ‘adult helper’ in the same way that a volunteer would be present in the setting. This meant that, for the most part, I engaged in play when children asked me to and would otherwise follow events as they happened. It could be argued here that this approach interferes with the objectivity of the research, however given my earlier discussion on this, this was not a concern. I extend on this point further in Chapter Five where I illustrate certain moments where I became caught up in the flows of children’s play during my fieldwork.

4.4.2 On speaking with practitioners

Though my primary aims were to understand how children come to develop their subjectivities within this outdoor nursery environment, the staff practitioner’s views mattered to me as an important element with this research-assemblage, the practitioners might have been able to provide valuable insight into the play encounters that I witnessed. Though, I was acutely aware of the pitfalls of conducting a traditional interview format, after my fieldwork stage, to gather their thoughts. I did not want the transcripts of an interview to be any more intelligible than the material and embodied context in which the interview itself took place, nor to distract from the primary intentions of this research. I expected conversations to simply emerge through my own physical presence so to conduct a formal interview outside of this environment felt too abstracted from the actual encounters. Instead, I therefore chose to use a technique described by Stiegler (2020) as

‘go-along interviews’ to speak with practitioners *in situ*, perhaps immediately after they have been part of a play assemblage that I was interested in. Rather than formally interviewing after the fact, go-along interviews would be to understand how they make sense of the event straight-away. Practically, this is also beneficial in terms of maximizing my time at the setting and avoiding the need to take staff away from their practice. There are some limitations to this approach in terms of noise levels, chances of interruption, and not wanting to take up too much of their time. Yet, I knew from my own experiences as a practitioner that there would be some opportunities to share thoughts on certain events as they occurred, real time. In my practitioner information sheet (**Appendix 4**, emphasis in original), I wrote:

Sometimes we will talk informally about my research within the nursery. If you make any comments that I feel may help my study, I may ask you if I can note our conversation down. You may say no, this will not affect your overall participation, and *unless I ask for your consent, what you say will not be recorded or form part of the study.*

Speaking with practitioners would therefore allow me to clarify how knowledges about children’s subjectivities were performed through their practice and consider how these knowledges emerged from wider social and material relations. I saw written notes as just as suitable as a tape-recorder, since I would be able to clarify any information that the participants gave consent to provide.

4.5 Attuning to artistic practice for research-creation

Creative digression and conceptual diversification has (sic) the potential to offer highly precarious journeys through the unctuous vapours and cloying mud of the normatively constructed and discursively inhibiting contours of the Positivist swamp.

(Gale, 2018, p. 148)

Perhaps one of the most liberating aspects of the postqualitative turn is the invitation to researchers to think-otherwise beyond conventional presentations of data and findings (Gale, 2018; de Freitas, 2016; Koro-Ljungberg, Löytönen and Tesar, 2017). Thus far I have retained the use of ‘data’ as it is commonly understood since, as with other terms, my definitional preference is to retain and expand their meaning. Here then, it is necessary to expand on ‘what counts’ as data within postqualitative-inspired research inquiry following the theoretical underpinning I have detailed in Chapter Three, where there is a shift toward considering how things are distributed through assemblages, and a focus on process (becomings) over stasis (being). What counts as data here, then, is the capacity of my sociomaterial proposal to adequately reconsider how subjectivities

are formed through my postqualitative and ethnographic approach into children's play encounters. In this section I consider the role of research-creation before turning to my presentation of the textual, still image and video data in the forthcoming two chapters.

4.5.1 What is research-creation?

Research-creation is said to play a crucial role with the scholarship on postqualitative inquiry as a way of expressing data on more creative terms (Manning, 2015; Springgay, 2018; Harris and Holman Jones, 2022). Central to those engaged in research-creation is a commitment to the arts and artistic practice. Grosz's (2008, p. 3) text on a Deleuzian interpretation of art provides an opening definition for the reader:

By arts, I am concerned here with all forms of creativity or production that generate intensity, sensation, or affect ... [I am interested] in exploring the peculiar relations that art establishes between the living body, the forces of the universe and the creation of the future, the most abstract of questions, which, if they are abstract enough, may provide us with a new way of understanding the concrete and the lived.

Significant here and throughout the rest of Grosz's text are the political implications of an engagement with artistic practice, insofar as the inducement of affect or haptic perception solicits the human body into sensations that they may not have felt before or may be unable to experience otherwise. Mimicking (unwittingly, perhaps) Clausewitz's famous aphorism, art (not war, of which this phrase is commonly understood in the context of) is conceived as 'politics by other means' (Grosz, 2008, p. 76). Grosz goes on to illustrate these claims via the sunflower-sensation distinct to Van Gogh's work and various other classical paintings that induce certain affects. A more contemporary illustration might be the artistic practice of UK Grime artist Stormzy when he became the first Black British performer to headline the Glastonbury Festival. Stormzy's set, as Hann's (2021) analysis draws attention to, foregrounds a creative sensation of Black culture within Britishness through the social and material elements on stage. By puncturing the cultural geographics of a predominantly white and middle-class event, by bringing "South London to a farm" (Routledge in Trendell, 2019), the assemblage that is Stormzy's performance elaborated new (Black) possibilities for the live audience present, including myself, and the television viewers. Returning to the purpose of this thesis, the motivation for engaging in artistic and experimental practice might therefore be understood as intended to elaborate new possibilities of more-than-human being and becoming against the dominant perspectives of humanism.

Colebrook (2002), however, suggests that one salient issue with how artistic practice might mobilise political concerns is the tendency for people unfamiliar with this mode of inquiry to

expect it to serve a functional purpose. For instance, it might be expected that the viewing of a particular image or video may make one a ‘better’ practitioner in terms of supporting children. This is plainly the intention for using image or video in some circumstances (Meager, 2019). However, for Colebrook, fundamentally with artistic practice the intention is to move beyond the forms of presentation as serving a precise function or strict use-value and instead elaborate other ways of knowing beyond what life is, toward that which it might be and become. In short, the purpose can be said to be *affective* rather than *effective*. Yet, insofar as this thesis has precise aims oriented toward articulating a sociomaterial metaphysics, my rationale for research-creation differs from Colebrook because it *is* intended to be effective, in meeting those aims, as much as it is intended to be affective, in elaborating subjectivities on more creative terms. For these reasons, in places I will refer to the affective and effective implications of my artistic practice.

Within the literature, post-qualitative engagements with artistic practice have occurred through photo-text entanglements (Nordstrom, 2013; Taguchi, 2013), and experimental writing techniques (Koro-Ljungberg, Löytönen and Tesar, 2017; Riddle, Bright and Honan, 2018). These may have been fruitful avenues for my own inquiry, yet the pull of more traditional forms of analysis weighed heavy as I wrestled with the conventional expectations of a doctoral research project and my own insecurities about engaging in artistic practice. Ultimately, as described in the following sections, while I do seek to queer presentation of imagery, my ethnography that will follow in Chapter Five remains with a traditional presentation format. Chapter Six where I re-present video data is perhaps more aligned with a postqualitative data presentation, however even here there are opportunities to further induce haptic perception that may form the basis for future inquiry. Hence, what follows may be more accurately termed post-qualitative-inspired in terms of my underlying theoretical intentions, yet still with one foot in the more conventional qualitative approach to data collection.

4.6 Writing ethnography: on textual data presentation

With regards to my presentation of the written field notes that detail my time at Wood Fire, it is initially noteworthy that many authors writing through postqualitative inquiry have eschewed thematic analysis and instead favoured vignettes as a means for providing insights into the social and the material things that can comprise an event (Gale, 2018; Masny, 2014; Jenkins, Ritchie and Quinn, 2020). While thematic analysis, through practices of coding, is commonplace in qualitative research, postqualitative scholars are critical of this approach insofar as it tends to presuppose a false level of objectivity within the researcher and elides the values of singular encounters (MacLure, 2013a). Vignettes, while certainly not restricted to postqualitative inquiry (Barter and Renold, 1999), have instead been favoured as part of the creation of an atmosphere perfectly suited for descriptive explanation (Gale, 2018). Others have spoken of vignettes in terms of enabling

‘ruptures’ into the research (Masny, 2014), or as a surface of a more widely distributed constellation of events (Rousell, 2019). As I approached the ‘writing up’ stage of the following chapter, vignettes weighed heavily on my mind as to whether they were the best means to present the data. Despite my best efforts to think-otherwise and the fact that I have a significant amount of experience working with young children, I had still naively begun my fieldwork with a preconception that I would witness clearly-spoken play encounters with the children that would last for extended periods of time. I would then present these as neat and tidy vignettes. This did happen sometimes, but all too often the creative and improvisational nature of their play, where often it became tricky to follow who said what and why, meant that trying to record every single word that was said felt inadequate. To understand children’s play experiences solely through their linguistic speech would be to present a partial slice of the encounters I witnessed. As I have made clear so far and shall detail further in the following chapter, there is *much more* to experience than that. This did however, serve as a reminder to me that ‘what was’ is indeed a powerful lure (Manning, 2016, p. 117) and that I would need to think hard to productively unlearn my own habits of thought.

A secondary concern with vignettes is that while they allow for extensive detail of an encounter, they are conventionally interpreted as reflective of a singular moment of judgement (Hemmings, 2005). I was just as interested in what Hemmings (2005) describes as ‘affective cycles’ and what I have written in previous chapters on the nature of habit. That is, the way in which social and cultural determinations feed-back into *multiple* play encounters across time and space in different moments. This relates to my decision in Chapter Three not to stress a clear distinction between affect and emotion: while I was affected in situ, my re-turning to the data has generated new thoughts and feelings about my time there. In the end, I have written in a style that I feel best captures the experiences that I witnessed at Wood Fire, choosing to present my time as an assemblage of encounters, a coming-together of things, of minor gestures and major tendencies. I digress in places, taking lines of flights toward the unexpected, letting myself get caught up in the flow of writing in the hope that the examples I share induce life into the concepts I am working through, with Massumi (2002, p. 19), “more or less violently”.

4.7 Visualising ethnography: on still-image presentation

While the still visual data I present in the following chapter are sociomaterial assemblages of the particular play events that took place, crucially they can and perhaps *should* also be read as a new layer of the relations, as re-presentations rather than an attempt to accurately mirror the truth. The purpose here is, with Vannini (2015, p. 15), to “enliven rather than report, to render rather than represent, to resonate rather than validate, to rupture and reimagine rather than to faithfully describe”. For this reason, the still images I share are re-presented through affective techniques

within artistic practice intended to induce haptic perception. For example, in De Freitas (2016) text on creative practice in still image and video footage, a software tool called Doodl is introduced to the reader. This is a web-based program where an online drawing robot writes over a given image at different speeds and with different intensities (see Figure 1). This affects the tonality of the image through the alteration of colour and, more importantly, disrupts conventional ways of perception:

In watching a Doodl video of colouring sensation, the eye is no longer the usual optic device, looking for resemblance, looking for the line, but becomes haptic. In other words, the eye touches the image, and the sense of sight behaves like the sense of touch.

(de Freitas, 2016, p. 328)

In blurring the contours of the image, then, research inquiry might challenge our relationship with the fixity of human subjectivity and induce haptic perception. This resonates with the broader monist metaphysics I introduced in Chapter Three which aims at bringing concepts to life and thinking of theory-as-practice. There are also close similarities with the writings of Tim Ingold (2010), who thinks-with a tree to question the external boundaries that are placed on subjects and objects and instead foregrounds the way that things *leak*, “forever discharging through the surfaces that form temporarily around them” (Ingold, 2010, p. 4). This matters because it highlights other ways of knowing about bodies and illustrates how subjectivities come to be in-formed in relation to our material environments. Regrettably, however, Doodl was built using Adobe Flash Player software, which was no longer supported from December 2020. Hence, the re-representation of still images in the forthcoming chapter makes use of editing software within Microsoft Word and Adobe Photoshop.

Figure 1 The author, re-presented through Doodl

Having said this, while the blurring of faces is already necessary to maintain anonymity, it raises a noteworthy ethical tension. When faces are blurred for ethical reasons, few questions are raised

around how this may mis-represent the child. Yet what if one chooses to queer representation for reasons other than anonymity? Such practices are cited by Russell (2020) in *Glitch Feminism*, a text on identity in the digital era, as contributory toward usefully problematising the body on the more-than-human terms. However, at times, I became mindful of not completely losing sight of the child. One might read this is indicative of a show of self-restraint where I remain tied to the rationality of humanism, yet ethically I believed this to be the most appropriate act. Having established a meaningful relationship with the children, this was my limit, my affective threshold beyond which I felt that to queer representation any further would pose a challenge to my ethical obligations.

My engagement with artistic practice raises questions about claims to truth. However, as I have argued throughout, what counts as ‘truth’ is always a value judgment and I am not interested in an account of experience that operates according to the value of the dominant order, of some kind of ‘neutral’ or ‘objective’ truth. As Manning (2020:112) makes clear:

Neutralized forms of knowing, generalised by systems of interpretation that renounce making the terms of engagement visible, do not silence only those who are neurodiverse. They silence all life that deviates from existing frames that organise and perpetuate how we are taught to know and see.

Rather than considering whether this is true or not, then, it is better to consider this as an extension of what is rarely interpreted through humanist perception, challenging claims to a singular truth. One might additionally read this as an attempt to overcome the binary logic of truth according to the Aristotelian principles of identity (where something *is* that thing) and the excluded middle (where something *is* either that thing *or not* that thing, such that there is no thing in between, in the middle). This has long been a central concern within the realm of artistic practice. For instance, Keane (2013) discusses the work of the artist Marcel Duchamp, whose installation *Door: 11, rue Larrey* is intended to produce the excluded middle against Aristotle’s principle. Given the identity of a door that must be either open or shut, Duchamp’s door is sited within a corner that opens one door at the same time as it closes another, it opens and shuts. This aesthetic and material unsettling of the excluded middle (a door either opens or closes) is essentially affective, such that the installation “dilates the suspension of judgement while amplifying attention and perception” (Keane, 2013, p. 49). Overall, producing affect and challenging the fixity of truth and identity aligns with the broader aim for this thesis of producing new knowledge and also of producing knowledge differently (St.Pierre, 2020; MacLure, 2013c).

4.8 Cinematizing ethnography: on video-image presentation

Figure 2 Adobe Premiere Pro

The video-data chapter that follows Chapter Five engages further in the process of research-creation through the production of a video montage. This video was created through Adobe Premiere Pro (see Figure 2), a video editing application with a number of built-in features that would enable me to play around with my footage and produce a video on postqualitative-esque terms. Initially, I again take my cue from De Freitas (2015; 2016) who, working with Deleuze's earlier cinema texts, asks that researchers move beyond the idea of movement within video data as only a literal sensory-motor image. Situating video research within the tradition of scientific cinema, across both of her texts, De Freitas (2015; 2016) draws attention to chronophotographic methods concerned with coding movements of the human body. These early attempts, aimed at capturing movement through frame-by-frame analysis, particularly those deemed unconscious or non-intentional, are worthy of criticism insofar as they facilitate a fascistic desire to interpret motor-activity as mechanical cause and effect. Instead, De Freitas proposes that inquiry should consider the opportunities inherent in a Deleuzian mode of empiricism that would enable the body to be understood in new, more-than-human, ways. Here it is experimental film practices, such as cross-dissolving, blurring, and montaging, that might better communicate and enliven the political questions and concerns that mobilise research inquiry. However, the very nature of experimental inquiry, in line with the broader postqualitative orientation toward research inquiry, necessitates that there are no formal guidelines on how haptic perception with video data might be achieved (St. Pierre, 2019).

The lack of guidelines is complicated by the knowledge that to claim something as ‘achieved’ in the first place assumes a logic of measurement which risks occluding qualitative capacity to affect, beyond measure. As Manning (2016) notes, it is a normative tendency of State philosophy to predetermine value according to accepted registers of change and the already-known. Indeed, the existing literature reveals a number of heterogeneous approaches toward inducing affect following De Freitas’ proposal (MacRae and MacLure, 2021; Silvis, 2019; Caton, 2019; Wolfe, 2016). MacRae and MacLure (2021), for instance, draw on video data from a project with two year-old children to play with *motion* as a means of generating haptic perception. For them, when video is slowed down in speed a different kind of focus emerges on “the dynamics of motion itself, and the shifting space between moving bodies as they respond to each other ... video has the potential to amplify moments of contact and change in events that usually pass unnoticed” (MacRae and MacLure, 2021, p. 7). In another paper seeking to unsettle haptic perception, Caton (2019) works with pixelation techniques to foreground light, colour, patterns and texture in a way that re-imagines human subjectivities on terms that align closely to my own sociomaterial proposal. By returning to the video data of my time at Wood Fire in a way that ‘ruptures and reimagines’ rather than ‘represents or reports’ (Vannini, 2015), my act of research-creation attempts to facilitate new modes of engagement into processes of affective sociomaterialisation.

4.9 Conclusion

The purpose of this chapter has been to work through the more theoretical aspects of sociomaterialism outlined in Chapter Three and draw these together with a postqualitative orientation toward research inquiry. The first part of this chapter concerned itself with the practicalities of gaining access to a research setting and the process of writing the ethics submissions for this research. The shift toward a fully outdoor nursery environment because of coronavirus was also explained before part two of this chapter. The second half moved on from research design toward producing a sociomaterial framework for inquiry. I have introduced and thought through the postqualitative turn, considering implications for the subsequent ethnographic account that follows. This has included the need to trouble subjectivity and objectivity, and the role of video. The final section of this chapter has addressed the presentation of my data in the forthcoming chapters, focusing specifically on the affordances offered by research-creation as a means of unsettling seemingly neutral ways of knowing about subjectivities. I have detailed my approach toward the ethnographic data textually, visually and cinematographically in relation to the video footage. Overall, this chapter has endeavoured to assemble a sociomaterial inquiry for exploring children’s identity in-formation, which will become the focus of the following two

5 Chapter Five: A sociomaterial ethnography at Wood Fire nursery

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter I present an ethnographic account from my time at Wood Fire nursery. I advance my inquiry into affective sociomaterialisation to explore children's identity in-formation. I open with an account of Wood Fire, where I consider in broad terms how this setting could be understood as an 'alter-childhood' space (Kraftl, 2014). I also outline differences from more conventional nurseries in terms of spatial features and daily routines, before detailing my processes of attuning into the space itself and settling in with the children. Here I note the affects and effects that my own Black male body had during my time there, before shifting my analysis toward the materials and spaces at Wood Fire. I then consider what happens when (it felt like) nothing happened, turning to occasions of experience where the children were free to dwell with muddy puddles and wooden planks as un-organised bodies (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987). Toward the end of this chapter, I centre the role of desire and examine how, during my fieldwork, I witnessed several encounters that seemed to striate subjective agency in children's play according to the broader cultural capital that certain materials generate. I explore how masculinity is produced sociomaterially, attending to one child and their bodied sense of self as they articulated their subjectivity into the world. Finally, I consider the nature of friendships at Wood Fire and close this chapter with an account of the value of (seeming) **non-sense**.

To briefly re-orient the reader, the ethnography that follows can be best understood as an assemblage of encounters, a coming-together of things, of minor gestures and major tendencies in an attempt to explicate how subjectivities are produced. This is a *sociomaterial* ethnography insofar as I treat agency as distributed and relational, rather than individualised in any one person. Practically, this means that at times I focus on non- and more-than-human things within encounters, not removing the human subject, the child, entirely but expanding the ambit of inquiry to affectively privilege the social *and* the material in relation. Some of the images I use in this chapter are therefore intended to challenge a conventional relationship with the fixity of human subjectivity and induce haptic perception (de Freitas, 2016). As I discussed toward the end of Chapter Five, they are not intended to be formal correspondences that accurately signify an objective truth but should rather be understood as an endeavour to induce sensation, or affect, into the imagery as a means of unsettling traditional representation (Grosz, 2008; Vannini, 2015). Elsewhere, I focus on the in-formational nature of experience itself and, finally, I pay close attention to matters of care. As with most efforts within the postqualitative turn aimed toward

producing new knowledge and producing knowledge differently (MacLure, 2013c; St.Pierre, 2020), this is a difficult balance to strike. Yet ultimately, this is an endeavour made in the hope that what follows will bring the concepts I have considered thus far *to life*.

5.2 Introducing Wood Fire

Figure 3 Wood Fire nursery

Wood Fire nursery (see Figure 3) is a fully outdoor environment for children from two years of age. It is set on grounds comprised of field, meadow, and woodland areas, with a small indoor space, known as a ‘Yurkie’, for the children which provides warmth and shelter if needed. Despite the generous amount of attention given to outdoor play in Scottish policy contexts (see Chapter Two) (Inspiring Scotland, 2018; Scottish Government, 2020a), fully outdoor settings represent less than 1% of all daycare provision in Scotland. It became clear to me on initial visits to the setting that I had not considered how unique fully outdoor early childhood settings are. For details explained in the previous chapter, my original research proposal was planned with a conventional nursery setting in mind. I therefore immediately felt as if I was forcing the concept of heteronormativity on to this setting, when during my short settling-in visits and sessions I simply had not seen the kinds of play practices that would illuminate the original focus of my research. This, as I will discuss in this chapter, does not mean that heteronormative practices did not occur at all, but my ethnographic gaze instead shifted toward an understanding of children’s identity information in a broader sense, to include wider questions around gender, masculinity, femininity

and the nature of friendship. The sociomaterial assemblage of things that comprise Wood Fire forced me to think differently. In many ways, this setting is somewhat exemplary of an 'alter-childhood' space. This is a term coined by Kraftl (2014, p. 219) to describe:

Explicit attempts to imagine, construct, talk about, and control the life worlds of children differently from a perceived mainstream ... not as a static category for naming particular discourses, against others (i.e., neoliberalism), but as a cipher for open and, hopefully, productive questioning.

Kraftl's label here is a useful entry point to begin to distinguish Wood Fire as not only distinct in terms of the nursery being fully outdoors, but also, as I will come to show, in terms of its broader pedagogical approach toward childhood, even among other outdoor nursery settings. The vast diversity of outdoor play provision is noted in Johnstone et al.'s (2021) systematic literature review that I examined in Chapter Two and was also something that I myself witnessed during my initial visits to other settings. Wood Fire differs from conventional mainstream provision insofar as the total area for children to play in is roughly 49,000ft² (4,559.66 m²), offering masses of space for the children and far more than a conventional indoor setting could ever provide. The spatial affordances are vast. Even on their busiest days with up to twenty children there are large parts of the environment that remain unused. Care inspectorate (2017) guidelines state that the minimum space standards per child is just under four square metres. At Wood Fire, each child could have well over ten times that and there would still be a significant amount of space remaining.

Secondly, there is no age-banding between the youngest and oldest children, meaning that they can all play together all the time. This again is rarely the case in conventional settings where children are often grouped together according to age and/or (perceived) ability. Logically, this is informed in curriculum guidance by the developmentalist belief that children need 'appropriate' resources for their age, which represents a neutral category of their development, a stage (Piaget, 1957). It is a way of producing social order according to chronological time. Yet in practice such a universalising gesture inevitably overlooks the differences between children of the same age and can produce an inequality for children who are seen as less mature or competent (Gallacher, 2005; Haynes and Murriss, 2016; Sundhall, 2017; Blaisdell, 2018). At Wood Fire, the lack of age-banding was perhaps a necessity given the practical impossibilities of dividing children within this space. However, it also allowed for an ethics of care to emerge in some instances (though, not always), where the children would develop relations un-limited from the arbitrary impositions of biological age.

Thirdly, there is little to no routine for the day. Children do not gather in the mornings for circle times and are not required to sit for any extended period of time. Apart from snack times (which are optional), lunchtimes, toileting provision and fire drills, children are allowed to play uninterrupted for extended periods. To their delight, there is also no requirement to tidy up any of the outdoor resources throughout their day. My own experience within practice reminds me that the often-tyrannical nature of routines can produce some children as ‘out-of-sync’. Having to conform to the temporalities of ‘welcome at 09:00’, ‘circle time’ at 09:15; ‘snack, toilets breaks and indoor play’ at 09:30; ‘tidy up indoors’ at 10:15; ‘outdoor play’ at 10:30; ‘tidy up and wash hands’ at 11:15; ‘lunch’ at 11:30; ‘sleep, or quiet play’ at 12:00, ‘home time’ at 13:00 (and repeat in the afternoon, every single day of the week) is a norm that perpetuates inequality against those children who are seen as untimely, unable to keep up, tidy up, or who are simply too invested in their own interests to follow a schedule (Bodén, 2015; Knight, 2019). In later conversations with Conor, the team leader at Wood Fire, he noted that:¹⁴

[We want] the least amount of transitions that you can possibly have in a day, because anytime you have a transition, you're pulling children out of deep play. So, we had tried to limit that as much as possible. And that's why with things like snack or rolling snack, the children can choose when they want to go, probably the only thing we have to do is lunches. We just manage that just to make sure that they happen because we have catered lunches and stuff like that. But, in my ideal world, the children have very little disruption of their day from us apart if they're coming, choosing to get us, but they know they're choosing when to eat and all those kinds of things, and we have to have the relationships with them.

This commitment to ‘the least amount of transitions’ as it translates into an open routine for the children is constitutive of an attempt to unsettle the habitual practices of time-keeping that would be normal in most nursery settings (Bodén, 2015; Knight, 2019). As such, this practice, facilitated as much by the material space as it is by the practitioner’s intentions, may be read as a minor opening-up of time released from conformist linearity.

Further, in line with my intentions to decentre the human, it also matters to note that this space is not one that is exclusively occupied by children or staff alone. During my time there, we searched together for traces of mice who would race through the setting from time to time; worms and slugs, too, were assigned a non-human personhood in many encounters (creatures became teachers), as well as the birds, steam trains, ambulances, real digger trucks (from the ongoing

¹⁴ All names in this chapter, except mine, are pseudonyms.

construction of a restaurant next door) who all populated the space and composed the affective texture Wood Fire as a whole. In Figure four below, for example, I follow the children as they become caught up in the frenzy of a group search for slugs (a). The atmosphere is lively as one child asks, “where’s the slug gone?” while another child shrieks uncontrollably “It’s slippery! Hahahahaha”. The screaming catches on as children nearby join in with the ludic gesture. In the midst of this, Rupert finds and gathers up a slug into his hands before walking over to me (b, c). “Shad, I’ve got something yucky!”. “Show me?”, I responded. “Slug.” Rupert replies plainly as he carefully opens his hand out to me, “it’s a good slug” he continues. He then turns away and raises his palm up to the other children while shouting “SLUG!” at the top of his voice (d). Human and non-human assemblages of this kind produced affects of excitement and care in the children. Many more unexpected moments akin to this occurred during my time at Wood Fire. These were thoroughly ordinary encounters that occurred outside conventional human-animal interactions insofar as notions of ownership and domestication were challenged (Ingold, 2000; Braidotti, 2013; Singh, 2018). To the children and staff, this environment belonged as much to the slugs and worms as it did to them.

Figure 4 Slug!

Wood Fire nursery is distinct even from other fully outdoor nursery settings. There is not a closet ban on plastic toys, and contra popular cultural imaginaries it is hardly ‘tucked away’ deep in a forest. Conor encouraged me to consider it as more of a junk yard-esque adventure playground than anything else. This felt apt. I recall that during my very first visit to this setting, on a notably

warm and sunny day, that I described it as a ‘mini Glastonbury festival’, an event which affectively structures my own perceptions of freedom, joy and escape. On mentioning this to Conor, he recollected their yearly picnic and sleepover that they would hold and explained the broader relation to the wider community that Wood Fire tried to produce through these events:

I've always said that the intention here was that well, and I always say to parents, they're not signing up for nursery, you're signing up for community. So, I think for me, it's the community coming together. The original intention of the picnic was to kind of celebrate the year we just had and acknowledge the children that are moving on.

Notably, these were intended not only for those currently attending, but for *all* children and families who had *ever* attended. Typically when children leave nursery provision there is little reason, besides a young sibling also then attending, for them to return. Yet as Massey (2004) has noted, the construction of local practices such as these events can work to situate and bring individuals together in tandem with material spaces, fostering relational networks of care and as productive of communities. Emotional feelings of celebration shared between bodies therefore might be said to organise not only the social but also the material space within this assemblage. A sociomaterial reading of community in this vein might be constitutive of what Eckenwiler (2021), drawing from Massey, refers to as the ‘inter-subjectivity’ of place.

Finally, all the children and staff at the setting used conventional ‘he’ or ‘she’ pronouns and identified as either a boy or a girl, so I will retain this language throughout the chapter. Some children felt the affective pull of their gender much more strongly than others. For example, I saw that some girls did wear clothes that were not obviously gender specific, by which I mean that they were not dressed in all pink clothing from head to toe, but no boys did. Nearly all of the children, bar one, were racially white, as was the entire staff team. Apart from the manager, a man, all the staff were women. All the children, staff and I were able-bodied. As I note above on their busiest days there were between fifteen to twenty children, however it is also worth mentioning that because of Covid-19 their staff to child ratios were much higher than usual. This meant that on some afternoons with fewer than ten children, there were still between four to six members of staff on site. I had parental consent to gather data with nearly all of the children bar one, meaning that an initially planned sticker-based system to decide who I could and could not film was not necessary. Ongoing consent from the children themselves then occurred on a routine basis, where I was attentive to moments where it was not appropriate for me to hang out with them (Flewitt, 2005; Warr *et al.*, 2016). Given the freedom in which children could roam, I became aware of my own body as a possible striating force that may have been affectively felt as a foreclosure of their

capacity to act, away from adult surveillance. This certainly happened, there were times where it felt clear that I should leave a child to do whatever they were doing without me or any others interfering. In these moments I moved away and left the children to it.

5.3 Tuning in to a sociomaterial sensibility

Figure 5 Surveying the landscape, tuning in.

The initial settling in period within the nursery was more stop-start than I would have liked. Due to institutional reasons relating to risk assessments and funding, I had four full days of simply settling in with the children and becoming accustomed to the space. This period provided me with time to simply observe the play happening throughout the day and understand how particular spaces were used by both practitioners and children. Given my sociomaterial approach, I was interested in not only how human bodies moved through space, but also how the spaces and materials themselves smoothed or striated certain forms of play. I was interested in understanding the particular milieus that children tended to inhabit within the space and the material relations that affected them yet may have typically gone unnoticed. Initially, given that this all felt rather unusual, I worked with certain techniques to guide me toward further experimentation and thought. Ahmed (2017, p. 22), for instance, talks about the role of *intensities* in feminist research:

Feminism often begins with intensity: you are aroused by what you come up against. You register something in the sharpness of an impression. Something can be sharp without it being clear what the point is. Over time, with experience, you sense that something is wrong or you have a feeling of being wronged. You sense an injustice.

Intensities were a useful opening for me because affect is itself intensive rather than extensive. As Colebrook (2002, p. 22) exemplifies, “I watch a scene in a film and my heart races, my eye flinches and I begin to perspire. Before I even think or conceptualise there is an element of response that is prior to any decision”. With this, I was prompted to follow things that somehow left an impression or caught my interest. This pre-cognitive immediacy is also illustrated by Massumi (2015, p. 93), who writes that:

In the heat of an encounter, we are immersed in eventful working-out of affective capacities. We have no luxury of a distance from the event from which we can observe and reflect upon it. But in that immediacy of feeling absorbed in the encounter, we already understand, in the very fibre of our being, what is at stake, and where things might be tending.

There are resonances between Ahmed and Massumi in their considerations of the ways in which we, as researchers, sense the (political) nature of what is at stake within such encounters. Elsewhere, I have sought to forge my own sensibilities by ‘feelingthinking’ through affective encounters with whiteness (Tembo, 2021a). Feelingthinking, informed by the scholarship on affect (Stewart, 2007; Manning, 2008; Massumi, 2008; Wolfe and Hook, 2019), troubles the primacy of cognitive thought and the normative brain-body hierarchal construction. It works as a heuristic technique to enable me as the researcher to write out my felt experience of particular examples and become entangled *in media res*, in the midst of the relations they generate. There are also similarities here to what Actor Network Theory theorists Fenwick and Edwards (2010, p. 149) propose when they ask:

What detail does one pick to start following? One ANT approach is to choose a site and just sit in it for a while or wander about in it, watching, listening, thinking, perhaps talking with people in the site, until something of interest emerges.

Intensities, then, presented themselves to me through the encounters I witnessed that caused me to think and consequently through the footage I decided to record in those present moments. Secondly, watching the video footage repeatedly attuned me to regularities, to habits of thought that had become sedimented through the repetition of particular practices. Being aware of intensities also shaped the way in which I produced my video-data, of which I will discuss in the following chapter.

5.3.1 *Who's researching who?*

As well as observing the children, I engaged in becoming-practitioner again as I endeavoured to build alliances with them and the staff team. I was able to refer to my experience within practice relatively easily, as my experience as a practitioner far exceeds that as a researcher. As there were few, if any, periods throughout the day when all of the children came together, I was initially accompanied around the space by a member of staff who introduced me to the children. I was introduced as an adult-helper who had come to visit Wood Fire because I was interested in finding out about their play and about the setting as a whole. The video recorder and my notepad were presented as a means to watch and record their play, similar to when the staff team use their cameras. Most of the children were happy to say hello, introduce themselves and let me join in with their play. In other moments, the video recorder itself flipped from a mere object to subject within the children's games. Figure 6 below exemplifies one of many moments where I quickly realised that it had become caught up in the flow of the children's fantasy play, where the encounter had taken over. Saoirse (on left), shouts and laughs in a high pitched tone: "Get the camera, get the camera!", while Tyler (on right) runs at the lens and me, waving a found stick as if to cast a magical spell.

Figure 6 "Get the camera!"

This encounter foregrounds the material significance of the video recorder within this research assemblage. Rather than a neutral device employed to represent experience, it can be said to have

been “actively implicated in the creation of a new layer of active material-discursive relations” (Myers, 2017, p. 195). In other moments, some children took their interest in me very seriously and became research assistants in this fieldwork assemblage. The video recorder and my willingness to demonstrate it to them resulted in many encounters where we were ‘doing-data’ together (Myers, 2017). At times, the questions put to me by the children troubled the neat distinctions between exactly *who was researching who*. Why did I have a video recorder? Why is this my job? Why do I need a job? Why is my hair so curly? Where is my mummy? These were tough questions that I could not always answer.

Figure 7 Who's researching who?

In other moments, children would follow me around as I observed the other children’s play, coming to sit with me and see what I could see through the video recorder lens (Figure 7, Figure 8). Sometimes they would narrate their peers play for me. I note these things not as an aside, but because they mattered as minor gestures that the children would engage in alongside their more visible modes of being in relation to my presence. I note all of this as part of my endeavour to map the minor moments that occurred during my fieldwork, relations that Manning (2020) describes as difficult to articulate but nonetheless *felt*.

Figure 8 "Can you see me?"

On a practical level, while I was primarily there to hang out, there were inevitably moments when it felt appropriate for me to support another member of staff who needed extra help. For instance, I supported asking children to wash their hands and offered them snack when necessary. I also occasionally supported the children with opening their squeezable yoghurts if they could not manage this for themselves. The children would sometimes come to me if they were upset. In these moments I would provide emotional support and, if necessary, signal for a member of staff to take over from me. With issues relating to tensions between the children in play, I would typically not get involved at all unless the children asked me to (if I felt that they were able to do so) or if I felt that it was necessary. I drew on my experience as a practitioner in these moments and would always feed back to the staff team as soon as I could. Finally, I made time to read through all of the safeguarding procedures in the case that any information relating to the children's welfare was disclosed to me. In total I spent nine full days at Wood Fire, or roughly sixty-three hours. I would arrive shortly after drop-off at 08:30am and be with the children up until 3:30pm. I loosely followed their lunch schedule, breaking away around 12:00 to eat and returning in time to greet the children who would arrive in the afternoons.

5.4 Entering fieldwork *in media res*, in the midst of things

Especially with qualitative research, it is generally understood that there is rarely a perfect time to begin fieldwork (Given, 2008; Denzin and Lincoln, 2017). When I returned to officially start gathering data with Wood Fire nursery it was late in the year. Dark afternoons, cold weather (even for Scotland), and regular bouts of rain all affected how I would spend my days (Figure 9). Such

seasonal affects stood in contrast to my earlier, warmer visits to the setting and mattered in terms of the numerous distinct sensory experiences that children would encounter. Weather continually textured my experience here. It is, as Rautio and Vladimirova (2016, p. 31) write, “is something we humans still have not figured out how to control and manipulate, yet we work with it endlessly – perhaps because of its own serendipitous agency”. This was an environment in process where weather was not represented to the children but actively experienced by them.

Figure 9 Elemental affects

Additionally, two children whose play I observed previously and felt would strongly exemplify many of my arguments had now left for Gaelic school, taking their highly audible ‘Hulk smash’ refrains that punctured the atmosphere with them. These sounds stayed with me and generated an affect that I felt was contributory toward the wider sonic geography (Kanngieser, 2012). It was supposed to be another child’s final week before a house move. She was interesting to me as she was the oldest child present which I felt affected the play of others around them. As it turned out, she was still present throughout my fieldwork because, in her own words, “moving house can *seem easy* but it’s *not actually easy, it can take a while*”. I state all of this to foreground the messy and imperfect nature of entering into this research-assemblage. My interest in hanging out and seeing what happens, rather than setting out with a clear expectation of what data I wanted to gather, is entirely genuine in this regard. I had a loose focus, however I really did not know what sort of data I would produce until I was there, until I had gained a feeling for and tuned into things. Of course, I wished both children were still present when I was there but this the way it went, landing *in media res*.

5.4.1 *Researching while Black*

Figure 10 (Failing at) Blending in.

It mattered that I was a Black man doing research within a profession dominated by white women (Scottish Government, 2017a) and in a geographic region that was primarily monocultural. I stood out. The popular cultural refrain, ‘doing x’ while Black’, where the ‘x’ stands in for nearly anything (for instance, driving, walking, existing, living, commuting, or teaching) served as a forceful reminder of the ways in which Black bodies intra-act with the ordinary affects of race (Tembo, 2020b). At Wood Fire, I was often the only non-white male visible to the children. Given children’s inquisitive tendencies, my afro hair was fiddled with and the darkness of my phenotype was commented upon. My body became racialised through these relations.

‘*Have you seen Dr Dolittle?*’ was a comment that a child greeted me with one morning. This is the title of a 1998 film featuring Eddie Murphy, a Black comedian who plays the role of a doctor who discovers that he can communicate with animals. While the film does well to avoid the racism of original book (Nel, 2017), it inevitably perpetuates the broader Hollywood family comedy genre of palatable Blackness for an idealised white middle class audience (Haggins, 2007). I had not been reminded of this film since my school days and it did not bring back happy memories, though I am no doubt that the child did not intend for this to have that kind of racial affect (Tembo, 2020b). This is unfortunately often how Black men are witnessed in popular culture and reminded me very early on of the ways in which social and cultural determinations limit our, including children’s, capacities to think-others beyond normative and reductive representations of non-white people

in popular media. To be clear, this is not a statement on intentionality, whether the child knowingly related me, a Black man, to another Black man they had seen on television in a consciously harmful way. Rather, it is more a comment on the *impersonality* of language (Riley, 2005). How my own history of facing racism in predominantly white spaces can mean that certain comments have an affect that go well beyond their official intentions (whether or not, as the child asked, I had actually seen Dr Doolittle). Knowing that I was often the only visible non-white person on site merely exacerbated these feelings, which may not even have registered with me in other spaces or at another time in a different assemblage. I share this as a moment of vulnerability. I *felt it mattered*.

5.4.2 *Researching while male*

It was not all like that. Sometimes my Black male bodily presence did force children to think otherwise from the ideas they had formed about social groups, to take a line of flight. Gwen, a four-year-old girl, and I had formed an interesting friendship during my fieldwork. She was an older child who I felt relied primarily on one other child to fully become themselves. When their friend was not present, I felt that this still had a contributory affect: I witnessed that Gwen either tagged along with another adult or played exclusively with other girls. In one encounter, Gwen asks me:

Gwen: *Are you my friend?*

Shaddai: *Do you want me to be your friend?*

Gwen: *Yesss! (shyly)*

Shaddai: *I'll be your friend, then.*

Gwen (several seconds later): *I do like boys with glasses on, have you got glasses on?*

Shaddai: *I've got glasses on, yeah.*

Gwen: *K.*

Shaddai: *that's lucky, isn't it?*

During my fieldwork, Gwen would join me as I hung out and watched the other children's play. We had several conversations, none of which I initiated myself verbally, about how 'she didn't like boys but only boys with glasses and my daddy' which was her way of articulating that, despite my sex/gender, I was acceptable as her friend. Put differently, despite the clear striation she felt in not wanting to be friends with boys, my very material male bodily presence appeared to produce a smoothing space in which she was able to think-otherwise beyond determinate ideas about gender and friendships.

In other encounters, it felt clear that Gwen's subjectivity was habitually formed in relation to conventional sociomaterial norms around femininity. She would often arrive clad in pink wellies, pink gloves, and pink waterproofs. Figure 11 illustrates a moment when Gwen would desire my approval for her new pink nails, running over to me and waving them in my face and asking that I record her hands. Overall through these occasions, 'long hair', 'pink nails', 'pink clothes' and 'not liking boys' are the habitual social and material things that appeared to affectively structure how Gwen made sense of herself as a girl (Coleman, 2009; Swindle, 2011).

However, the determinate nature of gender on children's subjectivity was not always this obvious. In my fieldnotes at the end of the day I reflected on a comment made by a member of staff to her which I couldn't immediately pinpoint, though it cast my mind back to Grace's best friend:

There was a comment from one member of staff regarding Grace's hair, she said 'your hairs going be longer than mine soon, it's growing so long!' – I felt that this was more a comment on feminine ideals than anything else and immediately thought of Melissa, Gwen's best friend, last week who felt so embarrassed about her short hair that Gwen had to tell me on her behalf and wear a hat all day to cover it. There is something here I can't place my finger on.

This comment from the staff member endured, it stayed with me. I recalled how, in a previous encounter, Melissa, Gwen and I were hanging out together outside on a climbing frame. This was not the first time we had spoken to each other, so a level of trust had been established between us. Melissa had wanted to tell me a 'secret', yet felt incapable of articulating it directly to me, nor was I able to guess. In the end, Melissa had to whisper this secret to Gwen who then told me. The

Figure 11 Gwen: Look, look, do you like my nails?!

secret was that she had had her hair cut to a short bob by her mum and felt embarrassed by her new look. “It’s too short!” Melissa responded upon the secret being revealed. She had been wearing a hat the whole time and continued to wear a hat throughout the duration of my fieldwork because of this. It might feasibly be suggested that Melissa was wearing a hat because she was cold. However, paying attention to the *confessional* nature of a secret here enlivens a Foucauldian lineage of thought. Foucault (1978), through tracing back to Catholic theology, examined the role of the confession as fundamental to the ways in which individuals come to express themselves. In articulating the confession, Foucault’s suggests that we become privy to the ‘internal ruse’ of power, hitherto mobilised as silence, or censorship. This is the difficult knowledge of traditional gender(ing). How the *felt* need to confess (through the secret) reveals how Melissa’s subjectivity is constituted by a previously unspoken (though expressed ontologically through the hat-hair relation) determinate standard that in-forms how she perceives herself and her identity. In other words, Melissa’s confession that her hair is too short reveals at the same time the unspoken knowledge that, as in the comment from the member of staff earlier, *a (correct) girl’s hair should not be that short*. Culturally, the relation between girls and women with short hair has come to symbolise being a transgression against traditional gender roles (Zipkin, 1999). This is a heavily heteronormative perception fuelled by the idea that women with long hair are more attractive than women with short hair. Mainstream children’s culture is not free from these gendered and sexist ideals, most obviously through the enduring cultural capital of Disney princesses (Cole and Sabik, 2009; Coyne *et al.*, 2016). In children’s literature, film, and toys, these characters continue to maintain heavily stereotypical ideals of what counts as ‘girl’ in contemporary society (Coleman, 2009; Swindle, 2011). Therefore, while Melissa’s confession is freeing, it is the affective nature of power as directive (in this case, toward becoming a certain kind of girl) that shapes her subjectivity in encounters to both be and become otherwise in the first place. Conceptually, this may be seen as an exemplification of affective sociomaterialisation.

5.5 Material matters

Figure 12 Vantage Points

The materials at Wood Fire had already changed from my visit six weeks previously and discussions with Conor and the staff team disclosed that, in a short time, things would look and feel different again. Trees would be replanted, and lesser-used structures would be recycled and remade. Few things were permanent. Things could be moved to suit. Few, if any, of the material resources were bought-as-new. Nearly everything had been reclaimed and/or re/upcycled in one way or another. Nothing went to waste, so that nearly-condemned things seemed to take on a second life at Wood Fire. These were care-full endeavours, surpassing maintenance toward an active engagement with *cultivation*. This may seem trivial. However, if the need to consider the ways in which material environments within nursery settings habitually contribute toward complicated, non-innocent, capitalist practices is taken seriously (Osgood and Mohandas, 2021), then Wood Fire's approach seems exemplary. This endeavour toward sustainability is an attunement toward different modalities of use-value away from the cultural obsession with the 'newest' and 'shiniest' things. Another minor gesture (Manning, 2016), constitutive of an ongoing concern with the processes of cultivation rather than a false desire for an end product. In a later discussion, Conor shares his thoughts about the compost bins that they use during mealtimes:

Shaddai: So, I really like what you're saying about sustainability and care and the way that's built into, you know, your practices with the children on a daily basis...

Conor: Yeah. And we've had three-year-olds challenge their families that they're not composting food at home, you know, and, and that to me is just amazing. Like talk about

grassroots, you know, three-year-olds just said: why aren't we composting that mom? [sic] And then she's like, crap. I don't know why, I guess we're going to have to start composting aren't we, you know?

Conor's comments here speak to the ways in which material practices of using compost bins shape broader sensibilities toward food waste within the children, producing relations of care in their behaviours. Again, temporally speaking, relational ecological practices make specific futures *knowable*, imbuing the present with an affective orientation towards care for non-human and human entanglements (Kraftl, 2014).

Turning the materials themselves, I arrived in the midst of a new structure being built: the 'tyre-hill' (see Figure 13). This had been created from a surplus of old car tyres and was held together by solely mud left by the builders in an adjacent site as they installed a new electricity pole. The combination of these two things gave form to a wide-based and multi-layered structure with a tube in the centre as a kind of focal point. This space drew my interest continually as it attracted the children to hang out here throughout the day. I understood it as exemplary of what Ahmed (2010) describes as a 'happy object'. The children often turned their bodies to these objects because the relation produces and commands happiness.

Figure 13 Tyre-hill assemblages

It was clear early on that these large climbing frames and the freedom with which the children could use them augmented their own sense of self and subsequent capacities. There were few orders to 'get down', to play 'properly', or to 'be careful' (and there were times when I had to stop

myself saying the latter). Such discursive statements of this kind are commonplace across educational settings (Cole, 2013). They can operate as habits of thoughts that, in their expression, striate bodily capacities. Deleuze and Guattari (1987, p. 107) make this point in relation to the affective nature of language. For them, ‘order-words’ are “little death sentence(s)” that designate the ways in which certain statements effect a power relation. Order is meant in both the sense of a command and in the sense of establishing order onto bodies, whereas death is related to differing modes of judgement and punishment dependent on the assemblage through which the language is used. Free of these order-words, then, the materials both produced and helped to shape how they could present themselves to me.

Many assemblages were produced with/in the tyre-hill, however the initial novelty of this structure in relation to the novelty of my video recorder provoked shouts of “take a pic, Shad!” from the children before they leapt off on to the ground. In moments like these, it can be said that they were not talking to me as a bounded individual in the Cartesian sense, or rather *the distinction between me and the video recorder was irrelevant* for them, my subjectivity was an assemblage of these things where my own body did not end at my skin (Haraway, 1987; Barad, 2003). Further, it would be easy to analyse the opportunities for physical development that a child was learning. However, that would fix in place and limit an understanding of what *else* is possible in terms of capacities during these encounters. At times there were so many bodies atop the tyre-hill that it became futile to focus on any single child. This enacted a group subjectivity: a hive-like sociomaterial assemblage of activity enabled in relation with the tyres, the mud, the wind, and the freedom to jump, leap, roll and wobble. To paraphrase Rautio and Jokinen (2015, p. 8) and their remarks on snow piles within these multiple encounters, “(The tyre-hill) can be thought of as generating life, as generating a “voice” which is always more and other than the sum of the individual (human) subjects. It is rather that the human subjects take part in one more-than-subject voice and become one clustered (tyre-hill) subject in the event of climbing and being with a (tyre-hill)”. In thinking through the capacities produced by the tyre-hill, it becomes possible to go beyond a focus on the development of any single child and instead consider the trans-individuality at the heart of experience: subjectivity, distributed. In other encounters, the children with becoming-with the tyre-hill as its indeterminate status shifted from volcano, a home, a volcano-home, an ice cream van, a hide-and-seek den, and a house for dumper trucks.

Figure 14 Clustered

Is the desirability of the tyre-hill all because it was ‘new’ to them? Perhaps, but the semi-permanent nature of all of the play spaces meant that no area was ever striated for an extended period. I witnessed constant deterritorialization at Wood Fire, in contrast to my previous experiences within ‘purpose built’ sites. I clearly remember the affective pressure of having to maintain such a space, with often unspoken rules implied by senior management on how frequently material things have to be ‘tidied up’, how and where to position my physical body in relation to the room, how to ensure that resources are played with ‘properly’, and how to ‘set up’ a room, often specifically for the purpose of a parent/carer show-around. Similar striating affects were experienced by Mohandas (2021) in their auto/ethnographical account of Montessorian early childhood practice. While always intended, to use the tired-out aphorism, with ‘the child at the heart’, these spaces and spatial practices are inevitably productive of particular subjectivities that determine the child’s capacity and potential. For example, I remember the implicit rule that in changing an environment around within a room, long open spaces where ‘children might be tempted to run’ were discouraged. The visibility of particular spaces was often seen as important, too, as a means to ‘control any bad behaviour’. Implicitly, as others have noted, this led to a panopticon-esque policing of boy’s play (MacNaughton, 2000; Lyttleton-Smith, 2017; Martin, 2011). The indeterminate nature of the material spaces that I witnessed at Wood Fire tended more-often-than-not toward smoothing spaces where such striations were not felt in the same way. They queered participation.

5.6 Spatial affordances

In her thesis on gender also from a posthuman, or sociomaterial, perspective, Lyttleton-Smith (2015) provides an extensive account of the conventionally demarcated spaces visible within early childhood settings. She considers how the ‘tidiness’ and ‘messiness’ of spaces can become imbricated in children’s enactments of gender, such that the surveillance of particular spaces enables and constrains particular forms of play. At Wood Fire, such a distinction did not arise, since as noted before there is no real requirement for children to tidy up. This led to queer kind of relation with certain toys that would disappear for a while and suddenly reappear again as children found them either on the floor or at the bottom of puddles (see Figure 15).

Figure 15: Lost, found, lost, and found again.

Children would often carry around things in their pockets and take things home such that I was rarely sure whether an object originally belonged to the nursery or not, nor did the staff feel the need to police any of the objects (Figure 16). I recognised this through my own felt anxiety of being greeted by different children with the same unusual objects and feeling the need to ask them “is that yours?”. In their paper on childhood objects, Jones *et al.* (2011, p. 54) express a similar feeling when they write about the affections that certain things produce both in practitioners (“anxiety if lost or stolen”) and parents (“annoyance and complaint”). My own experience with ‘toys from home’ policies that discourage children from bringing in items to the setting for fear of ‘negative behaviour’ reminds me that, while transitional objects are increasingly recognised as valuable for the child, such an approach is still not commonplace. In refusing to strictly police

ownership of resources, then, Wood Fire’s approach challenges dominant notions of property and the seeming necessity of individual ownership. In other words, this is minor contribution, or gesture, against possessive and individualist norms that are fundamental to broader normative ways of being rooted in colonial and individualistic logic (McClintock, 1995; Oyewumi, 1997; Jones and Okun, 2001; Osterweil, 2020).¹⁵

Figure 16 Pocket practices

The fact, too, that the environment during my time there was *ordinarily* muddy meant that I did not witness any child show an aversion to being dirty for any extended period of time, regardless of their gender. The children were also free to move and redistribute the mud, or the mud was free to move and distribute the children, wherever they liked. There were no coded discursive orders for the children to ‘keep it in a certain area’, as is often the case with more conventional ‘mud kitchens’. Aesthetically, none of the materials at Wood Fire were painted in what was described to me as ‘rainbow throw-up’ colours. In Figures 17 and 18, the mud and mud puddles that would appear following rainfall took on an agential force in contributing toward sociomaterial assemblage of the particular play encounters and the in-formation of subjectivities. Again, this is illustrative of the processual nature of the environment as contributory toward the capacities of children to act.

¹⁵ There is a long lineage of this thought, however Vicky Osterweil’s (2020:36) recent book makes the case clear in the contemporary moment through her chapter on the racial roots of property: “Not only is capitalist development completely reliant on racialized forms of power, but bourgeois legality itself, enshrining at its center[sic] the right to own property, fundamentally relies on racial structures of human nature to justify the right. Private property is a racial concept”.

Figure 17 Mud puddling

Figure 18 Mud-child-waterproof entanglements

Wood Fire still followed health and safety requirements, especially because of the ongoing coronavirus. Children were always required to wash their hands for meals. If they became muddy or wet to a point that it was uncomfortable for them then they would be encouraged (first, and then asked) to change their clothes (the younger children were given additional support here). The material resources were also cleaned on a rota basis. My point is that the materiality of the environment *elided the conformative (white) hygienic sublime* (Glabau, 2019). My broader locus of critique here is intended toward the increasing popularity of mud kitchens within the white middle-class

aesthetic re-determination of providing children with ‘natural’ experiences against what is perceived as the negative influence of digital technologies. The implications are twofold: this re-determination essentially re-fetishises the ‘natural environment’, therefore maintaining a position of human exceptionalism (Taylor, 2013). Secondly, it privileges a normative standard of white Eurocentric home life vis a vis the ‘domestic kitchen’. Wood Fire is not immune from this critique. I saw little digital play during my time there. This is not to say that the children were necessarily *lacking*, however I felt that more thought could have been done to consider how digital technologies might enhance their engagement with the environment rather than instigating a reductive either/or binary between the two. Put differently: while I sympathise with arguments that lament the increase in digital technologies for children, this does little to change the fact that, in the contemporary capitalist world, *we are already in posthuman times*, engendered by multiple and complicated advanced technological developments (Braidotti, 2019). Overall, it felt clear that Wood Fire’s refusal to demarcate ‘what goes where’ with the mud and not subscribe to often the tyrannous standards of ‘tidying up’ created a *smooth space* for the children to express their subjectivities-otherwise (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987). The intra-action of-mud-child-waterproofs through assemblages challenged determinate cultural and moral (and therefore thoroughly political) knowledges about cleanliness and messiness.

5.7 Becoming-with the world

Figure 19 *Becoming with the world*

What happens when nothing happens? I thought about this on many occasions where seemingly nothing in particular was going on, when children were simply hanging out or pausing for a moment, or when they were not doing anything that would typically merit an observation to document their ‘development’. I felt these temporalities to be incredibly generative for the children. Given what is known about the ways in which conventional nursery settings space time and time space, for instance through the conformist nature of the routine or through the rarely neutral arrangement of particular materials within an environment (Lyttleton-Smith, 2017; Knight, 2019), these moments of freedom from routines and the space that they had to simply wander about felt thoroughly life-enhancing. Far from doing nothing, a sociomaterial reading suggests that the children here were in fact *experiencing, attuning-to, and becoming-with the movement of the world* in all of its multisensory modes (Barad, 2007). The actual experience of being outdoors was significant with all its multisensory happenings: the feel of wind rushing by, the grassy and gritty surface textures, the noises of bird song. Hence, even when children do not speak, they still find ways to express themselves. This freedom from the tyranny of interruption that so often interrupts the times when we wish for our minds to wander, to let thought and the world flow through us, to move our bodies however we wish, is a rarity in early childhood spaces that remain heavily striated according to the fixity of spaces and times (Lyttleton-Smith, 2017; Knight, 2019).

Figure 20 Puddling

As an example of children-becoming-with-the-world, or the world-becoming with children, I turn to the puddle. As I briefly touched on above, the elemental affects at Wood Fire were both ordinary and remarkable. Rain and cold weather are far from unusual in Scotland, of course, yet they still produced marked affects with the children and the materiality of the space. The colloquial naming of the ‘sand-pit’ by the staff, for instance, was largely a ruse. I quickly discovered that there was no sand. Once made with an intention, it is now the plaything of the elements. On my visits, it became a large puddle-esque pool for children to play with, sometimes with more mud, sometimes with less. Always populated with various things: tin pots, buried toys, diggers.

Children desire splashing in puddles. This claim is nothing new. From a curriculum perspective, puddle splashing is conventionally determined to be beneficial for mobility and physical activity skills linked to better overall health, as well as being beneficial for an understanding of the scientific properties of water in a mathematical sense tilted toward future ‘life-skills’ (Education Scotland, 2020b). I do not contest any of this in a retrospective sense, but for the present child in the moment, in situ, the intention for jumping into puddles appears-otherwise. All too often, as I explored in Chapter Two, these developmentalist views maintain the presupposition that humans exist in a hierarchical relationship, above animals, plants, and things, as if the puddles were made *for* us, individuals. A sociomaterial attunement indicates that puddle jumping is an expression, but not solely of the child. Instead, child-puddle-rain-splash-wellies-mud-ripples-smile assemblages are an affective practice, produced in the intra-action of the encounter where conventional distinctions between subject and object lose traction. In the relation, puddles orient bodies, bodies orient

puddles. They induce movement, displacement, motility, and force. Puddles direct the flow of play and ‘produce this data as much as the video and the researcher’ (Somerville, 2017). Culturally, the relation to puddle splashing seems quintessential to childhood itself, as a joyous activity without any end goal. These intra-active practices that I witnessed oriented toward such joyful subjectivities.

Figure 21 experimental puddle-body subjectivities.

Nobody told the children how to splash in puddles, or to keep splashing in puddles, but they did it anyway often when no one was watching as an autotelic practice. That is, a practice that children, “repeatedly engage with for no external reward or motivation such as money or outside recognition” (Rautio, 2013, p. 394). Olsson (2009) makes a similar point when they examine a child

learning to walk, an activity that is fundamentally about the child increasing their capacities to move through joining their (human) body with other (non-human) bodies. This encounter transforms and softens the boundaries between the child and the puddle, creating experimental subjectivities, new modes of being and becoming that disconnect and reconfigure individuality.

Figure 22 'Contact zones'

A second material-thing exemplifies the argument I am putting forward here: the plank-walk. Figure 22 illustrates a long encounter one morning where I spent time with Zephanie, a three-year old child who would often hang-out on the plank walk as a vantage point to watch the other children run around. This is a material structure with little discursive contextualisation necessary, or perhaps possible, it is literally a plank adjoined to a wood climbing frame that bends and bounces according to the weight it holds at any one time. Zephanie would experiment with the affordances offered by this place as a 'contact zone' (Stewart, 2017) for experience, as a way of feeling herself into the world through her body in relation. It seemed to be one of the more popular play spaces, where I regularly saw both staff and children becoming-with and attuning-to the world around them as plank-child-wind-air assemblages. These moments of mattering mattered deeply to the children, eliding the developmental gaze as contact zones for emergent experience. In shifting

analysis away from the individual child alone, we become alert to the creative entanglements that compose experience. As I wrote in Chapter Three, this is what Deleuze and Guattari (1987) are referring to when they talk of a Body Without Organs (BwO), insofar as a body does not automatically designate a human body but is rather an assemblage of relations, of un-organised (human and non-human) bodies. The plank-child assemblages gained a ludic ontological status composed of heterogeneous elements that increased individual capacities to 'be'(come) (within)in and the world, differently.

5.8 Striating Subjectivities

My second research aim within this thesis is to examine the potential for outdoor early childhood environments to facilitate thinking otherwise beyond deterministic identity formations. During my fieldwork I become interested in understanding how what is known about social and cultural determinations may have played out in the absence of any specific gendering spaces. I was curious with regard to how, at times, free play become domesticated, or how the pull of the nuclear family retained familiarity. Although children were free to do as they pleased, I often felt and observed the restraints of conventional modalities of play during my time at Wood Fire. In Chapter Three I wrote that 'identity can be considered as an assemblage of social and material meanings and practices, rather than an overriding structural formation'. I take this up here as I think through how children continually re-constructed themselves to be and be-come otherwise in relation to cultural determinations and material things.

Figure 23 Dumper truck assemblages

There is a large body of research pertaining to the benefits of children’s fantasy play with toy vehicles, namely in terms of increased motor skills, increased opportunities for communication and as a means for schematic development (Santrock, 2014; Eisenberg *et al.*, 2017). Yet as affective objects, I became interested in what *else* they bring into relation. I focus here on ‘toy dumper trucks’ as affective things, as tendential “ideal inductions” into the striating cultural formation of gender for children, especially those who are sex-marked male (Hickey-Moody, 2019, p. 90). Within more conventional indoor nursery settings, toy dumper trucks are primarily housed within the ‘construction’ or ‘building’ area, a space primarily occupied by boys (Browne and France, 1986; Martin, 2011). Far from being pure or innocent childhood objects, the social and cultural capital of toy dumpers trucks fixes these objects in place as a striating formation in a much broader sense. Research has shown construction work to be culturally understood as a masculine activity (Iacuone, 2005; Stergiou-Kita *et al.*, 2015; Çınar, 2019). It is one of the most male-dominated professions and, for many young boys, produces an affective orientation toward notions of ‘hard (man’s) work’ and the profession being a ‘tough (man’s) job’, despite the soaring reports of poor mental health within the industry (Smith, 2016). Women within this field have also regularly reported their experiences of exclusion from the industry due to sexism (Williams, 2015). During

my fieldwork, I witnessed many dumper truck encounters. These were talismanic objects for the sex-marked male children in particular, directing their bodies as an assemblage of non-human and human things to produce them as boys. This occurred primarily through possession of the objects and a valorisation of them as the ‘best’ toy at Wood Fire. In literally moving bodies, the dumper trucks also enabled a different kind of proprioceptive spatiality to the children’s own human mobility. Agency in these encounters was not located in the children’s minds alone because this would be to discount the ontogenetic nature of these things and their affective force. Agency is distributed, relational in the vein of Barad’s (2003) posthuman performativity, and oriented in these encounters as a result of the broader cultural capital that dumper trucks feed-back. This account is not to say that the girls never played with the dumper truck, but the affective prestige never seemed to surface in the same way, there were no arguments over the dumper trucks in the way as I saw between the boys. Yet while my reading supports Hickey-Moody’s (2009) claim to these toy vehicles as tendential “ideal inductions” into a particular form of masculinity, in other encounters, other affects were produced.

Figure 24 Affective prestige

Figure 24, for instance, illustrates an encounter with Josh and Joseph, two boys, who I would often witness washing their dumper trucks in the sand pit. “We’re cleaning our dumper trucks”, Josh would say to me. In such relations, these objects were sticky with the feelings of pride and care. This is to say that while such objects were striating of their desires according to broader cultural

determinations around masculinity, paying attention to *what else* emerged can illuminate how practices of care are produced within such striations. On these terms, Manning's (2016) account of a minor gesture again appears percipient:

A minor (gesture) is always interlaced with major (gestures) — the minor works the major from within. What must be remembered is this: neither the minor nor the major is fixed in advance. The major is a structural tendency that organizes itself according to predetermined definitions of value. The minor is a force that courses through it, unmooring its structural integrity, problematizing its normative standards.

(Manning, 2016, p. 1)

In any case, to focus on the dumper truck toys as the *only* thing that oriented their desire would be to omit the literal aesthetic and sonic relation that Wood Fire had to a construction site directly adjacent to the setting. Returning to my fieldnotes, I wrote that this 'assemblage-next-door' figured as an outdoor cinema for the children at times, they would spend whole mornings watching the builders and building materials come and go. It was noisy, too, texturing the auditory atmosphere at times. One on occasion, I noted that Josh, in Figure 23 (also in Figure 25), spent the entire morning atop a large climbing frame surveying the landscape. From a sociomaterial view, the landscape can be said to have moved Josh. Its auditory and aesthetic affects further facilitated his aforementioned desire toward a particular cultural formation of gender, masculinity. With Gallagher (2016), treating sound in this way, as affective, enables knowledges to emerge around how the auditory atmosphere shapes Josh's subjectivity as he is becoming-with the construction site.

Figure 25 Aesthetic relations

5.8.1 Playing Masculinity

While watching the footage again and reading through my fieldnotes, my gaze frequently returned to one child in particular: Rupert, a three-year old boy. He was by all accounts a popular child among the staff team who would often recall funny stories about him to me. Watching him play, I immediately became interested in how Rupert expresses his desire in relation to his friendships, how he structures his subjectivity in relation to the material space and also in his own broader discursive ideas around what it means to affirmatively be, in his words, a “big boy”. Rupert was a talkative child and would often narrate his own play, pushing the dumper trucks along and shouting, “bigger and bigger and faster and faster”.

Figure 26 Affective Sociomaterialisation

Certain materials evidently augmented his capacities on occasion, materially shaping his performance as a boy (Hickey-Moody, 2019). Gendering always occurs in the relation. I would often see him atop of structures proclaiming, “I’m the king of the castle!”. His capacity in these moments was not only physical, as in he was literally taller than the others, but related closely to his felt and bodied sense of self as he articulated himself into the world. The image I share above, Figure 26, of Rupert is an interesting one, for he was habitually performing the bodily posture of what is culturally interpreted in the West as a ‘power pose’ (Carney, Cuddy and Yap, 2010). While popularised in a TED talk on YouTube by Amy Cuddy in 2012, the power pose is also historically recognised as a posture typically performed by Superman – a fictional character who has long propagated traditional masculine ideals (Marsh, 2000; Paechter, 2007). In the encounters that I witnessed, then, masculinity was produced sociomaterially in the assembled web of relations he entered into. This may again be exemplificatory of affective sociomaterialisation. Rupert individuates and enacts his subjectivity through the assemblage intra-action of discursive knowledges about what it means to be a ‘big boy’, the affective lure of male superheroes, bodily postures (the power pose), and the broader material architectural surrounds. All of these things shaped what Rupert felt he could do at times, producing him as a ‘big boy’ through these relations.

In my fieldnotes, I also noted that Rupert affected the relations of the play encounters he entered into in fairly significant ways through his ideas about how to relate with others. Friendships were a striding force throughout my time at Wood Fire. As they relate to subjectivities, children's peer cultures have been noted as an important factor in how individual children come to experience their individual sense of self (Corsaro, 2009). I became interested in the politics of attachment and what kinds of subjectivities emerged out of particular friendship encounters. The affective nature of attachment led, at times, to exclusions in the mode of determinate ways of being. For instance, Rupert's ideas about who was and who was not his 'best friend' had a stalling effect on another child, Eamon. As I wrote in my notes, Eamon was a child whom I felt 'sympathetic' toward in moments. Returning to the literature, Massumi (2017, p. 108) writes that sympathy is not a personal standpoint towards an individual person, but might be better understood as "the relational activity constitutive of the event", *par le milieu*. In other words, then, it is not merely that I felt sympathetic toward Eamon alone, but rather that the encounters I witnessed induced a sense of sympathy in me toward the ways in which Eamon was able to be and be-come otherwise. As I typed in my digital diary from my written fieldnotes at the end of this day:

As I have learned from the staff, Rupert and Alan were seen as "inseparable" and as "best friends"- this felt to me like a discursive habit of thought that has materialised in Alan not wishing to play with any other children whenever Rupert was present. This occurred most visibly one morning where I had witnessed Eamon and Alan play together just fine one morning, however with the introduction of Rupert in the afternoon, Eamon played by himself or trailed in the wake of Rupert and Alan's play. When he tried to join in on one occasion, Eamon was quickly rebuffed by Rupert, who I witnessed shout "Hey, you're not playing with us!". Eamon would try to talk to Alan, too, however he would rarely listen, much too interested in Rupert.

None of this is to blame Rupert, but rather to foreground the politics of how friendships become striated as a result of the affective prestige associated with having a 'best friend'. The discursive habits of thought that were placed upon this pair contributed toward the friendship, where Rupert and Alan were often referred to as an inseparable pair, more so than any other two children. Friendship is not always oppressive, but on the occasions that I witnessed it did produce exclusions in the relation. These are the tricky to articulate, yet nonetheless felt, micropolitical affects (Massumi, 2015). In another encounter, that on reflection felt hauntingly resonant with Renold and Mellor's (2013) study ([discussed on page 72](#)), I wrote:

Rupert is called over by an adult to be spoken to about a previous incident seconds earlier. Along with Alan and another child, they were 'hiding away' in a roofed play space that could only really accommodate

children's bodies. As Rupert reluctantly stands up and moves to leave the play space, he twists his body back and points his finger at Andy, 'You stay there, I'll come and get you'. Rupert does not return for a while yet Andy sits and waits, **his body literally fixed in place, striated.**

Figure 27 "You stay there"

Returning to the footage multiple times, I wondered how Alan felt about this. Given that he continued to sustain this 'friendship', I suspect that mostly he did not mind. There is always some comfort in conformity, as Deleuze and Guattari (1983; 1987) make clear. They note this in *A Thousand Plateaus* (1987) where they argue that complete smoothness would not be desirable as some kind of structure is always necessary in life.¹⁶ Yet this relation also raises wider questions around *how* and *in what ways* children form friendships with others under particular conditions. Here, this Rupert-Alan-friendship assemblage shapes how Alan sees himself as a result of the affects produced, which tended toward conforming with Rupert's desires more than the mutual desire of the pair. In many instances, this may be entirely productive as Andy feels his capacity is enhanced, however the *incapacity* that I felt at times for him to be and become-otherwise runs the risk of falling into habit, as a blockage of potential.

¹⁶ In a much more political sense in *Anti-Oedipus* (1983, p. 38) they lament the perverse nature of social repression in the face of fascism: "Why do men fight for their servitude as if it was their salvation? How can people possibly reach the point of shouting "More taxes! Less bread!?" ... the masses were not innocent dupes; at a certain point, under a certain set of conditions, they *wanted* fascism, and it is this perversion of the desire of the masses that needs to be accounted for".

5.9 Yurkie encounters

As I mentioned at the outset of this chapter, while children predominantly spent their days outside regardless of the conditions, the weather would occasionally fight back (Rautio and Vladimirova, 2016). The Yurkie was then the environment where children would be able to play and hang-out until they were able to return outside. This was not a large room, though it rarely felt busy given its high ceilings. It featured a wood burner to one side that was always on as it provided hot water for the whole site. This created a stark atmospheric contrast of warmth compared to the outdoor environment. Along the other sides were a large, benched table that children could sit at, as well as an adult sofa and shelving units which held story books, wooden blocks, mark-making resources and puzzles for the children to use.

The centre of the Yurkie was an open space. It gave the children just a slice of the freedom to move their bodies that they were so used to in the seemingly boundless outdoor environment discussed previously. However, it also cast light on the children who literally ‘took up space’ more than others. At times, certain bodies moved freely throughout this space, whereas others demonstrated resistance and tended to remain at the edges. This did occasionally happen outdoors, where the older children would often roam around with much greater freedom and the younger children tended to stay closer to the centre of the space, but it rarely materialised into an inequality because of the sheer size of the environment.

Figure 28 Yurkie Encounters

To focus on a single moment of interest, Figure 29 materialises an encounter where Andy, Rupert and Daisy are holding hands with each other, dancing to music and falling to the floor every few seconds in fits of laughter. It was unclear whether Rupert, as he thought, was in charge, or whether, as in much contemporary dance, the music took over their bodies (Manning, 2012). As with the auditory expression from the construction, in this encounter the music affects bodies in particular ways and textures the atmosphere in which subjects are produced (Gallagher, 2016).

Figure 29 Juxtapositions

In many ways, their movements seemed to echo those seen within a Ceilidh, a traditional Scottish social gathering where people come together and dance in groups. They seemed, too, to echo the movement of the popular children’s song ‘Ring-a-ring-a-rosies’. Either way, I did not know for certain. No one told them to do this. It just happened. Rewatching the footage and reading my fieldnote, this event stayed with me for several reasons. Firstly, it happened toward the end of the day with few children remaining, an odd temporality saturated with the knowledge that parental pick-up was imminent. I felt that this encounter was thoroughly life-enhancing, recalling the event I am filled with joy and returned to the laughter of the children. Yet, I also noted a sense of irony as the other staff members had their attention fixated on another child, to the right of the image, building with the blocks, doing ‘serious, focused’ play. As Pacini-Ketchabaw, Kind and Kocher (2017) note, blocks and block play has always been saturated with expectation. Blocks are expected to foster children’s creativity and imagination and are productive of often unspoken regulations, as they observed in their research:

No one, teachers included, said anything about how blocks could or should be used, but it quickly became evident that block-building “rules” did exist. The rules emerged in interaction: blocks are for building and making things; once you build something, no one

else can take it apart; once something is constructed, it stays there ... we notice right away how static and stable blocks can appear

(Pacini-Ketchabaw, Kind and Kocher, 2017, p. 89)

I was struck by the encounter because while my attention had drifted toward what might crudely be considered as the ‘non-sensical’, given that a few children dancing at the end of the day to some music would rarely merit too much attention, the practitioner’s gaze was instead directed toward a much more obvious mode of learning. ‘Received wisdom’ would have it that the child playing with the blocks would be ‘learning more’, that they are playing with the blocks in a correct and appropriate way toward their physical and motor development, whereas the children dancing were merely having fun with little ‘actual’ learning involved. Yet, as I have explored throughout this chapter, little is learnt through such a dichotomy. I argue here that there is something to be gained by re-valuing the role of non-sense outside of its developmental value. “But is this not just children being silly? Surely this carries no value?”, one may retort. Perhaps, but maybe this is the point. As Massumi (2014, p. 86) writes in his chapter on play:

Invented styles of taking flight, improvised ways of surpassing the given in (play), experimental orbits of escape from the known situations and their generic themes, might suggest, by analogy, creative lines of flight out of other situations where a heavy dependence on the already-expressed imposes itself with a life-crushing weight of the imperative to conform.

As the heart of this thesis as a whole has been the recognition that the in-formation of children’s subjectivities in early childhood spaces is not distinct from the broader social and cultural determinations in Western society. The determinations themselves are clearly not free from the affective pull of capital and operate as a mode of mnemonic control, where normative sociomaterial practices habitually feed back an affective resonance toward particular modes of being. Foregrounding the non-sensical aspects of children’s play, then, and privileging moments of creativity as minor processes where ludic invention and improvisation are recognised, might just signal toward resistance against what Massumi identifies as the ‘life-crushing weight of the imperative to conform’.

5.10 Concluding remarks

Philosophy begins in wonder. And, at the end, when philosophic thought has done its best, the wonder remains. (Whitehead, 1968:168)

Figure 30 Wonder

This chapter has sought to provide an ethnographic account from my time at Wood Fire nursery, exploring childhood subjectivities from a perspective of affective sociomaterialisation. By working in a more creative spirit to bring concepts to life and account for times and spaces that often elide the developmental gaze, I have sought to map the affective occasions of experiences that I witnessed at Wood Fire during my time there. This has been an entirely situated account. By recognising the nature of experience as produced in the relations of this research-assemblage, I am accountable for the knowledge produced as an endeavour towards research creation.

As I have attempted to demonstrate, the affective pull of cultural determinations around gender and the politics of friendship mean that striating practices still occur. Despite the potential inherent in working with affect, there remains a need to map the parameters of what bodies can do, how they can be and become. For instance, the ways that ‘long hair’, ‘pink nails’, ‘pink clothes’ and ‘not liking boys’ were the social and material things that affectively structured how Gwen made sense of herself as a girl, and also how Rupert’s subjectivity was structured through discursive knowledges about what it means to be a ‘big boy’, the affective lure of male superheroes, bodily postures and the broader material architectural surrounds. Yet, there were many opportunities for children to become otherwise from these things, too. I have exemplified this in relation to the

ways that Wood Fire challenged determinate knowledges about gender as it relates to discursivities of tidiness and messiness, and also through the moments where children were simply allowed to dwell: to do nothing and still do something. I have also endeavoured to map minor gestures, moments where I as the researcher had challenges children's ideas about Black men, moments where the distinction between who was researching who blurred, and moments of non-sense. This chapter closed with an account from my time within the Yurkie at Wood Fire. I considered the value of non-sense in children's play as it relates to the broader discussion on what gets valued in early childhood environments, outside of developmentalism. Valuing these ludic moments of improvisation and experimentation in children's play, I argue, is a minor gesture toward the possibility for childhoods-otherwise.

6 Chapter Six: Engaging in research-creation with video data from Wood Fire nursery

6.1 Introduction

In this chapter I introduce the video data from which the still images in Chapter Five are drawn. As both an exposition and in response to De Freitas' (2015; 2016) proposal for more experimental modes of research inquiry, I detail the 'techniques' that I have used to produce this video. While, feasibly, one might consider these to be 'methods', the connotations of standardisation and proceduralism that tend to accompany this term have led me to favour the language of technique. Granted, in the same way as method, to use a technique involves the repetition of a particular action. However, as Manning (2016) notes, it also leaves more space for play and modification. Thus, on the basis of the literature I have drawn from toward the end of Chapter Four, others may infer other techniques for research-creation, or they may repeat the techniques that I have developed with their own variation.

The ethical role of the researcher as deeply implicated within the re-presentation of this data is once again salient to note in explicating this entanglement of video editing software in relation to my video (Barad, 2007; 2012b). However, this is not to position myself as the (human, agential) 'expert' responsible for forming the inert video materials. It would be more accurate to acknowledge co-creation insofar as the materiality of the video data has had an agential force that, intra-acting in relation with myself, produces this event of research-creation. While the clips featured loosely follow the same order as the images in Chapter Five for the sake of clarity, some additional footage is interspersed throughout. As such, this chapter is intended to demonstrate the value of such a line of inquiry for postqualitative-inspired research relating to my own research aims. **The full video, of which the reader is now encouraged to watch, is available here.**

6.2 Presenting the video data

In the previous chapter, I noted how paying attention to intensities during my fieldwork enabled me to become attuned to moments of interest. Rewatching all of the video footage back, I became again attuned to intensities as part of my broader sociomaterial sensibility in deciding on the data to include that might best illustrate the materiality of Wood Fire and the in-formation of children's subjectivities. From here, my attention turned toward how best to re-present this video data and engage in research-creation. It would be amiss to lay claim to any articulable plan or predefined set of criteria for how I intended this video to be, hence my preference to speak in terms of technique rather than method. Based on the literature and the research of others who had engaged with this work, I cultivated a further sensibility toward broad aspects that I felt would serve as fruitful

avenues of inquiry. The first aspect was that of ‘lines’ informed through Ingold’s (2015; 2011; 2006) writing. Although Ingold does not participate in research-creation *per se*, his claims to the aesthetics of lines as they populate everyday worlds served as an initial source of insight, affectively as much as cognitively, for the re-presentation of this video footage. This led to me to play with motion, informed through the literature discussed toward the end of Chapter 4, and also a way to further illustrate some of my writing in Chapter Five around becoming-with the world and the slowed sense of time at Wood Fire. Playing both lines and motion brought to the fore the role of colour as the third broad aspect, before I finally turned my attention to the auditory experience. There were other techniques that I considered through experimentation, such as intense blurring and distortion, however I ultimately felt these to be less affective, and therefore less effective, than those that I finally drew on. In the following sections, I will discuss these aspects in further detail.

6.3 Experimenting with lines

Across his oeuvre, Ingold (2015; 2011; 2006) explores the way in which attending to the ontogenetic animacy of the world and the aesthetics of the lines that run through it refuses a binary division between the human and the non-human environment. It is *through* lines that beings are brought into the world and life itself is continually made legible through processes of becoming. I made the decision to initially focus on the lines as they initially caught my attention while re-watching the video footage and had the effect of immediately queering the image in a way that playing with colour or motion might not have. I first utilised the ‘find edges’ tool which brought attention to the boundaries in-between bodies and materials and created something of a sketch aesthetic on the surface of the screen (see Figure 31).

Figure 31 Finding edges

With the materials and spaces at Wood Fire, this effect had the impression of flattening the textural quality of the environment and disorienting habitual witnessing where the automatic tendency toward identification is slowed. For Manning and Massumi (2014) in conventional everyday witnessing, the experience of viewing an individualised subject can be said to be habitual such that the experiential immediacy of something-happening is often short-circuited in favour reflection after the fact. Deleuze (1986), too, presents a similar argument on the role of clichés in perception. Aesthetic images, for him, are not external or separate to the human, but rather “penetrate each one of us and constitute (our) internal world, so that everyone possesses only psychic clichés by which (they) think and feel” (*ibid*, p. 208). Affective response toward human recognition is therefore said to be habitual, or perhaps axiomatic, in everyday witnessing. In the video, however, the near automatic process of recognition stutters as attention shifts from the human body in the centre of the screen toward the materiality of the environmental itself in which subjectivity emerges through. Further, the ability to modulate the strength of this tool enabled me to play with moments where the original footage fades in and out, affectively re- and disorientating human common sense perception (see Figure 32). This was intended, in line with my research aims, to demonstrate how an attendant focus on materiality, as much as the children, themselves might enable a different way of understanding how children come to form their sense of selves. Ontologically, this distributes an understanding of being on more relational terms and, as I have discussed in the previous chapter, might concurrently illustrate the ways in which children may always-already be experiencing, attuning-to, and becoming-with the movement of the world in all of its multisensory modes (Barad, 2007). Put differently, the video enables an understanding of both how a sociomaterial metaphysical framework enables a different way of knowing about the child, and also how the children themselves may already experiencing be the world insofar as their subjectivities remain more open to indetermination than us as adults. This is not to speak *for* the child, but rather to re-articulate subjectivity in a way that remains open to alternative ways of knowing about how children ‘speak’ to us, adults, and express their sense of self through the world on more relational terms.

Figure 32 Dis- and re-orientation

As well as drawing attention to the environment, the find edges tool also unsettled routine witnessing of human subjectivities. The find edges tool indiscriminately produced lines within the footage across the human and non-human bodies. While lines can imply boundaries, here I felt that they effectively unsettled the eye's tendency to foreground human bodies as a kind of threshold heuristic by tuning into the texture of the material environment. The lines animated surfaces through a textural flattering whereby a routine distinction between subjects and objects is affectively unsettled, if only momentarily. This technique also drew attention to the shadows present within the footage on the sunnier days at Wood Fire. Variations of light and shade, in relation to the textural flattening, again complicate a clean distinction between the composition of human bodies and the material surroundings. This is consequential of the playfully deceptive nature of shadows that, as inhuman things, effect all bodies indiscriminately. In Figure 33, the shadows take on an ontogenetic presence that extends a conventional aesthetic presentation of subjectivity to one distributed through the spatial environment. Neither the human body nor the shadows presuppose each other, but rather emerge through the environmental surrounds as a form of Barad's (2003) posthuman performativity. This situates 'knowing' about the human body as a felt and material practice, as a "specific engagement of the world where part of the world becomes

differentially intelligible to another part of the world in its differential accountability to or for that of which it is a part” (Barad, 2007, p. 342). By bringing variation of light and shade to the fore in this video data, this technique offers an opportunity to consider where human bodies end and the extent to which subjectivities are composed through phenomena of light.

Figure 33 Play with shadows

A further implication of the find edges tool was the way in which the children’s faces become defamiliarised through the aesthetic smoothing of facial features. As I noted toward the end of Chapter 4 there was an ethical tension in this process where I felt a limit to the extent that I could do this. The deliberate misrepresentation of faces gestures toward invisibility, yet the same time has the affect of making them more visible through the disruption of habitual witnessing. This is a paradoxical kind of visible-invisibility, whereby ‘who this child is’ is not given, not necessarily determined, and not definitively prefigured. In one of their more esoteric passages, Deleuze and Guattari (1987) provides an analysis of faces in relation to systems of signification and subjectification. There is a relationality to the recognition of faces that, they write, “define zones of frequency or probability, delimit a field that neutralizes in advance any expressions or connections unamenable to the appropriate significations.” (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987, p. 168). Against this, artistically dismantling the face might be understood as a political gesture, a “becoming-clandestine” (*ibid*, p. 188) against humanist processes of subjectification. In Figure 34, the find edges effect therefore complicates automatic recognition and again foregrounds a more sensational process of coming-to witness how bodies are formed-otherwise in relation to their environment.

Figure 34 Defamiliarisation

6.4 Experimenting with motion

In addition to the find edges tool, the video plays around with motion as a means to intensify movements. Sobchak (2004), in her text on moving image culture, explores the implications of queering temporality for subjectivity. For her, the creative use of temporal practices makes time heterogeneous, presenting bodies as discontinuous from, yet still simultaneous with, linear time. This has the effect of ‘thickening’ the present moment as bodies, human or not, come into being through motion. Playing with slow and fast motion in this video enabled me to draw the viewer’s conscious attention to particular moments that, in real time, might not have registered or had an affect.

Figure 4 exemplifies the queering of motion with the video data. It is drawn from a momentary encounter of a child engaging with the material space where they are performing a near 360-degree twist jump off of a wooden platform for the video recorder, as much as for me. Here, the child’s movement is speeding *up* as they prepare to perform the twist jump, yet I slow this movement *down* to enable the viewer to become more attentive to the minutiae of motion within experience itself. In a later paper, Sobchak (2006) specifically focuses on the role of slow motion in cinematic practices, as it can serve to distil kinetic movement down to its essence. Her claim that playing with motion can produce an ‘extended sense of time’ echoes my own intentions here and, in this sense, is akin to Macrae and Maclure’s (2021) paper, discussed in the previous chapter.

Figure 35 Play with motion

In other sections of the video data, I slow down the events of splashing into a puddle and hanging out on a plank-walk to exaggerate ordinary encounters and generate intensities in the way that they affected me during my time at Wood Fire. Playing with motion here also animates how the material features at Wood Fire contribute toward how children came to express themselves on a routine basis. Slowing down in this way, as within image x from the footage below, animates the way in which surroundings “invite, provoke, and entice persons to perform actions” (Gins and Arakawa, 2002, p. 03). It is also intended to re-present my own experiences of witnessing play encounters, where the quality slowness was atmospheric and mattered in relation to my experiences within conventional nursery spaces. The video effectively enlivens my discussion of children becoming-with the world in Chapter Five and demonstrates the value of motion in providing alternative ways of knowing in-formation of children’s subjectivities.

Figure 36 Animating experimental puddle-body subjectivities

6.5 Experimenting with colour

Having experiments with lines and motion, my attention then shifted toward colour, since the find edges tools had the effect of washing away the hue to achromatic black and white shades. This enabled me to pause for thought and consider the significance of colour theory as it intersects with affect. Deleuze (2003, p. 52), in his book on the painter Francis Bacon, writes that “the color [sic] system itself is a system of direct action on the nervous system”, a claim that resonates closely with his writings on colour in his later *Cinema* (1986; 1989) texts. Scholars writing on contemporary colour theory support Deleuze’s claim by noting that viewers will affectively respond to colour prior to conscious sense or recognition of an image or of footage (Bleicher, 2011; Pavlidis, 2021). For Deleuze (2003), however, the use of colour has the capacity to un-organise bodies away from formal representation insofar as the queering of colour can release the habitual adherence between the eye and human figuration, pointing again toward the harmony between human and non-human bodies aligned with a sociomaterial way of knowing. Attention is also given to colour by Massumi (2002, p. 163), who proposes that any one-to-one correspondence between material stimuli and the perceptions that they produce is not possible. Massumi is opposed to the classical Newtonian theory of colour which sought to offer a standardised attempt of colour according to light. Through an optical prism experiment on the refraction of light rays, Newton advanced the theory that all the visible colours of the spectrum were contained within white light, which was best expressed through a colour wheel (Bleicher, 2011). Yet for Massumi (2002) and others (Sullivan,

2014; Sepper, 1998; Miller, 2014), such an approach establishes a false assumption of comparison across contexts, due to the parsing of the experience of life itself (what Massumi terms ‘the absolute’) into disassociated parts for analysis. The systematicity of colour alone, uncontextualised, is not in fact a universal phenomenon, for instance within the Hanunoo language, indigenous to the Philippines, colour is spoken of in relation to texture and taste. A more readily identifiable example in the West would be names given to paint colours (such as ‘pebble silk’ or ‘lemon pie yellow’). Massumi’s overall point is that recognising the conflux between colour and wider contextual elements has a number of implications, namely:

If artists (avoid) "rigidly ruling out" whole domains of confounding but absolutely real visual and synesthetic experience, then their treatment of form is significantly altered. Color is no longer separable from form, ... (it) can no longer be discounted (or celebrated) as subjective or whimsical ("decorative... It is experienced as being as fundamental as form. Color, illumination, form, three-dimensional space, and linear time all emerge, and emerge together, reciprocally, differently each time, from a many-more dimensioned, self-varying confound.

(Massumi, 2002, p. 173)

While Massumi does acknowledge the German poet Johann Wolfgang von Goethe, his analysis may have been strengthened by drawing out the distinctions between Newton and Goethe in further depth. This is salient to note since within the literature on colour theory, the distinction between Newton and Goethe have been subject to considerable discussion (Miller, 2014; Sullivan, 2014; Sepper, 1998; Gleick, 2008; Platts, 2006). As Sepper (1998) explains, Goethe was heavily critical of Newton’s colour theory for an overemphasis on objective qualities of light at the expense of the human ‘eye’ which he believed could not be separated from the actual act of seeing. Sullivan (2014) has come to characterise Goethe’s position as ecological since he effectively overcomes the

subject-object binary which aligns closely with an ontology that assumes no separation between the human and non-human, elemental, realm.

Figure 37 Play with colour

The implications of this knowledge for my own engagement in artistic practice are that the colours used within the video serve a significant function in contributing toward re-presenting the overall, or absolute, experience of my time at Wood Fire and the overall in-formation of human and non-human bodies. Further, far from an objective understanding of colour-alone, it would be fruitful to consider how other senses infuse with colour to contribute the broader atmospheric production of experience. In this video, while the black and white gradation did unsettle conventional perception to some extent through the find edges tool, it also created a sense of blandness, lacking a quality of vibrancy. As much as this video is intended to examine the potential for outdoor early childhood environments to facilitate thinking otherwise beyond deterministic identity formations, my wish was for it do so in a way that was colour-full. I therefore returned to, and enhanced through saturation techniques, the original colours in the footage to produce this video (see Figure 37). This is most visible in the slow transitions within particular clips between the ‘actual’ footage and the footage I have re-presented. Elsewhere, I make use of bright white to penetrate the footage as bodies slowly dissipate into the background. In figure 38 below, for instance, dissolving techniques are used in relation to colour to play with conventional perceptions of foreground and background, as both eventually give way to singular light. This coming-to of whiteness, the colour, speaks to an increase in intensity as the encounter plays out and again induces haptic perception through challenging conventional aesthetics of subjectivities within video footage.

Figure 38 Dissolution

6.6 Experimenting with sound

In *Hush: Media and Sonic Self Control*, Hagood (2019) develops an analysis of ‘orphyic’ media practices within contemporary society. Intuited through the character of Orpheus within Greek mythology, whose sounds had the ability to influence and shape the people he encountered, the term orphyic media relates to the ways in which the auditory capacity of all media can “can channel affective desires and modulate our sensory and attentional engagement with our environment and one another” (Hagood, 2019, p. 23). Hagood’s conceptualisation of orphyic media echoes the broader scholarship on the affective nature of sounds (Kanngieser, 2012; Gallagher, 2016; Doughty and Drozdowski, 2022), and underpins an understanding of the significance of this medium toward the effectiveness of this video as a whole. Given the experimental nature of the video produced thus far, and on the basis that I had recorded good quality audio of my time at Wood Fire, I made the decision to leave this aspect unedited and include original sounds, aside from moments where the audio is slowed to match any changes in motion. The noises that accompany the video feature the human and non-human sounds of bird sounds; the sounds of pen hitting paper; rain patter; puddle splashing; walkie talkies; human speech including jokes, laughter, shrieks; and noises from the adjacent construction site. These are all palpable and relational to the visual aesthetics of the video data.

Of further note is that, while I was keen to draw the viewers the materiality of the space and how children came to form their subjectivities within the environment, I felt that intersecting moments of social humour would personalise the footage, thus making it more affective and effective in terms of maintaining the viewers' attention. Humour is a felt feeling, where the naming of something as humorous denotes a change in one's affective state through the relation with that thing. It points toward the affective nature of language beyond mere communication of information (Riley, 2005).

Examples of humour in the video come in firstly at around 35 seconds, where silence gives way to the ambient sounds of the environment, before the calmness is punctuated by Sophie turning directly to the camera and directly acknowledging me, the viewer. Breaking the 'fourth wall' is a comedic media device that offers a break in the scene and draws attention to the viewer as a witness, directly implicated in the video (in truth, had Sophie not said my name, it may have been more effective to a general audience, but one should be reminded that these are thoroughly ordinary encounters in which these moments happened without prompt). Elsewhere, there is the humour of Zephaniah at around 4 minutes and 20 seconds as they giggle to themselves "Hehe, be careful!", and the slow build up toward the splashing of the video recorder in the subsequent clip "I'm going to splash you: one, two, three!". The video ends with a joyous moment of Ellis speaking directly to the camera, affectively anchoring my act research-creation affirmatively back to the 'child' in the closing act, "That was me up there... *That was me...*". Yet this is the child on more-than-human terms, distributed through play with lines and colour in relation to their material environment. The viewer is left with these words as Ellis turns and walk away from the camera, the aesthetics of the scene again shift, and the transition fades to black.

6.7 Revelling in uncertainty

If there is no standardised approach for where to begin with artistic practice, then knowing when to demonstrate constraint and mark work as finished is an equally testing challenge. Further, there is the question of how such a video might be received by the intended audience. On one side, it may be conceived I have gone *too far* in obscuring the child and have negatively disorientated the reader. Perhaps my presentation techniques have unnecessarily troubled received recognition and produced a feeling of confusion rather than clarity. Conversely, it may reasonably be argued that I have *not gone far enough*, that I have not completely let go of representationalism in my act of research-creation that remains inflected with a humanist orientation. In many ways, it is this precise tension that mobilises this thesis as a whole. As Manning (2020, p. 177) observes in relation to her

own artistic practice, “to practice new modes of encounter, to invent in the cracks of existence where individuality schizzes, is necessarily to be without bearings. And where there are no bearings, the first temptation is to presume to know.” While I recognise that the affective desire to *judge* this video remains strong, even within myself, there is also a need to revel affirmatively in the space of not knowing and enable a space away from the realm of critique. It has been the intention of this video data to elaborate new possibilities for understanding subjectivity and engage in artistic practice as ‘politics by other means’ (Grosz, 2008, p. 76).

In another way, this chapter has been an endeavour to overcome what MacLure *et al.* (2010) refer to as ‘video fear’, where researchers fail to articulate possibilities beyond what is already known. Following the broader aims of this research, to advance a metaphysical framework of sociomaterialism for understanding children’s identity formation, aesthetically presenting the social and the material in this way has offered an alternative expression of how subjectivities may be known on more affective terms. This aesthetic act of knowing through the video data sheds light on my sociomaterial metaphysical framework and serves as an affirmative act of research-creation that deliberately problematises received everyday witnessing. It also serves to disrupt ‘what counts’ as data and provoke further thought about how children might come to form their subjectivities through entirely outdoor environments. For instance, in Chapter Three, I discussed some of the limitations of conventional theoretical frameworks for understanding subjectivity that have remained primarily at the level of the discursive. My critique was not that they are too abstract, but rather, with Deleuze and Guattari (1987), that they are not abstract enough. Further, I argued that sociomaterialism might more clearly encompass a diversity of ways of knowing about the world through an explicit account of ontogenesis. Engaging in research-creation to bring to life my sociomaterial framework in this way has been my response insofar as I have sought to foreground aesthetic presentation to illustrate material and relational worlds, as much as the social. This challenges the logic of representation and strives toward effectively meeting my research aims by demonstrating how such a framework can offer new ways of knowing about subjectivity. Fundamentally, art is made not through content but through its affective style, hence the reason that cinematic practice remains so ubiquitous in contemporary society (Colebrook, 2002). This demonstrates, as Colebrook (2002), further notes, a human desire toward affective means of knowing and the re-presentation of knowledge on alternative terms.

6.8 Conclusion

The purpose of this chapter has been to trace my process of coming to engage in artistic practices as a means of challenging haptic perception. In relation to my research aims, I have sought to

participate in an act of research-creation through the production of this video data and detail my techniques in terms of lines, motion, colour and sound. As I have endeavoured to emphasise throughout, this chapter has been about producing a video that challenges the limits of thought through the affective and effective capacity of cinematic practice.

7 Chapter Seven: Conclusion

7.1 Introduction

In this chapter I aim to recap and trace the journey that this thesis has taken. I bring each chapter in line with each other to illustrate the relation between the arguments that I have put forth thus far. I return to the original research aims of this study in light of my fieldwork to examine the extent to which these have been met. I also provide a section on the implications of this study for practice and research inquiry, as well as on constraints. This conclusion closes with a final passage on the themes that this thesis has touched on and provides a discussion regarding what my argument may mean for future practice and research within this area of inquiry.

7.2 A recap

This thesis has set out to examine the role of outdoor early childhood provision in Scotland, foregrounding a framework of affective sociomaterialisation to understand how children's subjectivities are in-formed within such spaces. Following my introductory chapter, the early parts of this thesis were intended to provide contextual analysis regarding the policy context in which this research project is situated. I examined the role of the Scottish Government's CfE (Education Scotland, 2019b) and considered the influence of neoliberalism as it has become entangled with the logic of 'development' in educational contexts. I argued that mechanisms of testing, regulatory inspection, monitoring, audit, and measurement have all come to create a developmentalist mode of understanding subjectivity. In examining how one might challenge curriculum logics, the following section explored the primary theoretical frameworks that were concerned with understanding children's subjectivity: social constructionism (Foucault, 1978; 1980a; 1980b), performativity theory (Butler, 2004), and developmental psychology (Piaget, 1957). While I maintained that there remains utility across each approach, my analysis also revealed limitations across all three perspectives insofar as they naturalise an individualist metaphysical basis rooted in Cartesian logic (Gatens, 2009; Mignolo, 2012). In light of this, I have turned to the increasing scholarship on materiality to explore how else the in-formation of childhood subjectivities might be understood (Fox and Alldred, 2017; Dolphijn and Tuin, 2012; Barad, 2007; Braidotti, 2013). As contributory toward the second research aim of this thesis, I argued that, especially regarding entirely outdoor environments, the use of the dominant theoretical frameworks for further understanding subjectivities in the Scottish context might perpetuate a human-centric perspective of the world (Hultman and Taguchi, 2010). My argument was thus that greater attention toward

ontological and ontogenetic matters may prove generative in developing new knowledges on how subjectivities are formed that unsettle humanist logics.

Chapter Three was produced with my initial research aim in mind, of advancing a sociomaterial metaphysics toward understanding children's identity in-formation. I employed a method of 'conceptual pickpocketing' (Braidotti, 2002) to produce a sociomaterial framework for understanding subjectivities. As an alternative to staying faithful to any particular theorist, the aim was to bring together multiple aspects of this heterogeneous body of scholarship and assemble my proposal for understanding identity in-formation. I began by introducing a Spinozist (2002) metaphysics to overcome some of the limitations of Cartesian logics, instead positing the body as simultaneous with the mind and blurring the distinctions between theory and practice, and nature and culture. This was a salient theoretical move as it enabled me to reconsider the role of agency with regard to how the world is experienced between humans and non-humans in relation (Barad, 2003). I also introduced two further key terms: assemblages and affect. The former might be understood as a heuristic to bring together the Spinozist metaphysics and sociomaterial performativity that I had outlined previously. However, I also recognise that we cannot fully understand assemblages, in a truly political sense as they relate to subjectivities, without a clear knowledge of the role of affect. My interpretation of affect was intended to highlight its utility in reconceiving power as processual and produced through certain assemblages, rather than as *a priori*, and to foreground the nature of experience as felt, perceptively, as much as it is conventionally considered to be predominantly cognitive (or visible through narrowing processes of quantification that seek to metricise life (Parisi and Goodman, 2011; Massumi, 2015)).

Overall, my argument in Chapter Three was that sociomaterialism enables a shift from understanding the child's subjectivity as lack, as I examined within the previous chapter. Rather, through the assemblage, subjectivity is produced only through one's assemblage of experiences according to whatever habitually affects them. Children lack nothing until the conformist notions of 'ages and stages', 'developmental goals' and 'experiences and outcomes' come to striate their desire. On the basis of what is known about the creative nature of childhood, which I discussed in Chapter One, insofar as children's knowledges about who they should be and become are still largely undetermined, my contention here was that a sociomaterial framework is entirely appropriate for considering how children's subjectivity is in-formed within early childhood provision. This chapter also examined some implications for how space and time might alternatively be interpreted, where I was keen to emphasise that paying attention to the *emergent* conditions of capture, through affect, is crucial if we, researchers, are to better understand the

sociomaterial relations that assemble to consequently striate and produce particular modes of subjectivity (Coleman, 2009; Swindle, 2011; Hickey-Moody, 2019).

In Chapter Four, I was concerned with how I might mobilise these knowledges in practice and bring my research aims around advancing a sociomaterial proposal in relation to the scholarship on the postqualitative turn. This chapter considered the opportunities that a shift from more conventional research methods could offer for my study. Here, I was interested in decentring the role of language and, more precisely, pushing back against the position that only discursivity can accurately represent experience and reality. My argument was that decentring the spoken word and recognising how communication (in the broadest sense of the term) occurs through the *relation* between things, spaces, and bodies might better allow us to understand how children in-form their identities outside of the dominant humanist frameworks of knowing and being (Mazzei, 2016; St. Pierre, 2020). In the middle part of Chapter Four, I outlined my proposal for producing a multi-sensory inquiry for understanding children's identity in-formation. Since I wished to produce an account of subjectivity that did not privilege the individual, video methods were the most appropriate format (Whatmore, 2006; Staunæs and Kofoed, 2014). This would allow me to go beyond, though not dismiss, solely textual representations of data as a means to witness the affective social and material events that populate early childhood environments. The final part of this chapter centred around the presentation of the data to come. I examined the roles of artistic practice and research-creation in presenting an account of subjectivities at Wood Fire on visual and cinematic, as well as textual, terms. Experimenting in this way, I argued, might induce an affective response in the reader insofar as my presentation is intended to challenge conventional knowledges about subjectivity, and also effectively respond to my research aims.

Chapter Five was my attempt at bringing my sociomaterial proposal to life and enabled me to directly respond to many aspects of my research aims. I provided an ethnographic account of my time at Wood Fire nursery, paying close attention to the various materials that populate this environment and how the space itself was utilised in certain moments by certain children. Drawing insight from the literature on affect (Fenwick and Edwards, 2010; Massumi, 2015; Ahmed, 2017), I detailed my processes of tuning in with the children, paying attention to intensities and moments where I became-with the children and the flows of their always-ongoing assemblages of play. I noted the tensions in entering in the midst of things and considered how I, as a Black man in a predominately white location, stood out. Throughout the rest of this chapter, I examined the presence of certain materials on site at Wood Fire, considering the additional freedom with which the children were able to present themselves. This was helped by the messy reality of researching with young children, where focusing on any single child was a futile endeavour at times. Group

subjectivities emerged in assemblages of intense activity in, around, and through certain material structures (Rautio and Jokinen, 2015).

Within Chapter Five I also asked what happened, when seemingly nothing happened. In the times where children were simply hanging out, my sociomaterial attunement led me to witness child-puddle-rain-splash-wellies-mud-ripples-smile assemblages as affective practices. These were experimental subjectivities, *in media res*. Elsewhere, my focus was on whether the social and cultural norms that we typically expect to witness within more conventional indoor settings, continued to occur within this environment. For the boys, the affective prestige of ‘dumper trucks’ remained a strong lure (Hickey-Moody, 2019). However, in the absence of any demarcated construction area, or rules about how to play with these resources, an elevated level of *care* also emerged. Wood Fire’s approach toward resources, where nothing had to be ‘tidied up’ at the end of the day or put into a specific place, meant that the boys seemed to inhabit a feeling of responsibility that elevated the significance of the relation beyond merely desiring the ‘biggest’ or ‘fastest’ truck. They did desire this at times, and their desire toward these particular toys was perhaps elevated by the materiality of the adjacent construction site that affected the aesthetic and sonic atmosphere at Wood Fire. However, through a sociomaterial perspective it became possible to witness the more minor moments that emerged in the background as contributory aspects of the boys’ play. I closed this chapter with an account from my time within the Yurkie at Wood Fire. I considered the value of non-sense in children’s play as it relates to the broader discussion on what gets valued in early childhood environments, outside of the shackles of developmentalism. Valuing these ludic moments of improvisation and experimentation in children’s play, I argue, is a gesture toward the possibility for childhoods-otherwise.

Finally, in Chapter Six I introduced the video-data from which the still images were drawn and sought to re-present these through artistic practice in a further act of research-creation. My exposition examined how I would respond to De Freitas’ (2015; 2016) call for more experimental modes of research inquiry. The emphasis placed upon cinematic presentation and the aesthetics of moving images was an endeavour to induce haptic perception and foreground the materiality of Wood Fire on terms that would slow habitual forms of witnessing. This section closed with a discussion of how the viewer may respond to the video, where the very uncertainty in problematising conventional ways of knowing was posited as a central driving force in the video-data. Yet the desire to judge remained strong, even within myself. I concluded with the claim that there is ultimately a need to revel affirmatively in the space of not knowing away from the realm of critique.

7.3 Revisiting my aims

I now examine the original research aims of this project and consider the extent to which these have been met.

1. *To advance a sociomaterial metaphysics toward understanding children's identity in-formation*

My use of sociomaterialism within this thesis has enabled a number of opportunities for me to unsettle conventional knowledges around how children come to form their identities. Rather than beginning with a representationalist figure of the individual knowing child, I have used sociomaterialism as a heuristic to develop new knowledges on the processual and relational nature of how such representations come to be in-formed in practice. The relationality at play here is crucial in overcoming the Cartesian parsing of mind and matter and foregrounding a way of knowing that unsettles a conventional notion of agency. I have sought to extend the logics of individualism and consider the wider role of all kinds of materiality and things as they come to affect how identities are in-formed. This has been more expansive reading in which subjectivity is never given in advance. It has been the assemblages themselves that I have endeavoured to situate as my units of analysis, in the same vein as Deleuze himself argued in an interview with Claire Parnet (2007, p. 51): “The minimum real unit is not the word, the idea, the concept or the signifier, but the assemblage. It is always an assemblage which produces utterances. The utterance is the product of an assemblage which is always collective.” Deleuze’s use of utterances in this quote resonates with my own exposition of a more-than-human form of performativity. I have attempted to demonstrate how a sociomaterial metaphysics can be put to use in practice within Chapter Five, detailing mud-child-waterproofs assemblages, plank-child-wind-air assemblages, and dumper truck-boy assemblages. In each, children became un-organised bodies, affectively intra-acting with their environment to produce their subjectivities. My use of sociomaterialism has therefore enabled me to figure these in-formations beyond the constraints of the Cartesian subject and therefore provide an alternative means of understanding the ways in which environments can shape bodily capacities.

The aesthetic and cinematic presentation of my data also serves a salient purpose in responding to this initial aim because my engagement with artistic practice has enabled me to experiment with conventional data presentation on more creative terms. By seeking to induce haptic perception through the still images and the video data, the sensations produced in the viewer were intended to elaborate new possibilities of more-than-human being and becoming against the dominant metaphysics of humanism. An example of this is in Chapter Six, where I played with techniques

of lines and colour to affectively and effectively re- and disorient human common sense perception, and situate knowing as a felt and material practice (Barad, 2007). I recognise, however, that the act of research-creation through artistic practice may be interpreted as a risk. How art is judged follows a different set of criteria to that placed upon conventional research inquiry. The question of ‘what it is’ is backgrounded in favour ‘what it does’, and the kind of experimental practice I have produced may “create new forms of knowledge that may have no means of evaluation within current disciplinary models” (Manning, 2016). On evaluation, this has been a necessary risk worth taking toward affectively and effectively illuminating a sociomaterial metaphysics, and attending to materiality, on alternative political terms (Grosz, 2008).

Partially through postqualitative inquiry, then, the metaphysical framework I have utilised also pushes back against anthropocentric narratives by reconfiguring traditional conceptions of agency. Rather than the child being the sole actor within a passive environment, my analysis has demonstrated how *experience itself produces subjectivities*. For instance, with the toy dumper-truck encounters ([see page 131-134](#)), where the dumper-truck became a talismanic object for the sex-marked male children in particular, directing their bodies as an assemblage of non-human and human things to produce them as boys. The sonic geography was also significant in shaping agency in this regard. The sounds produced from the adjacent construction site can be said to have moved Josh and facilitated his desire toward a particular cultural formation of gender, masculinity. I explained that treating sound in this way, as affective, enables knowledges to emerge around how the auditory atmosphere shapes subjectivity where, in this particular encounter, Josh is becoming-with the construction site. I have therefore unsettled the hegemony of an *a priori* knowing self, pointing to how we, humans, are always-already composed in more-than-human ways.

Elsewhere, the focus on spatiality, the movement of bodies, and the affective nature of language accorded through a sociomaterial metaphysics has also enabled me to demonstrate how friendships might be conceptualised in an alternative way. The account shared with Rupert and Eamon through an understanding of smooth and striated spaces (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987) offers insight into how desires are shaped between children in ways that can augment or diminish their capacity to act according to the affective prestige associated with having a ‘best friend’. To this end, this thesis has contributed toward mobilising sociomaterialism in research inquiry as a generative metaphysical framework. This approach has enabled a novel and more expansive contribution toward how childhood subjectivities are affectively and sociomaterially produced in relation to entirely outdoor and alter-childhood nursery environments. As I have sought to bring to life through the video-data, my ethnographic account foregrounds the agency of events and

things in which children are constituted with respect to non-human things that compose subjectivity.

2. *To examine the potential for outdoor early childhood environments to facilitate thinking otherwise beyond determinising identity formations.*

In Chapter Five I described Wood Fire as an alter-childhood space (Kraftl, 2014). The endeavours of the whole staff team to produce an environment in distinct contradiction to a conventional nursery setting (or, perhaps, the capacities of the environment itself: the trees, the sheer physical space, the birds and the mice) in enabling the staff team to think-otherwise really mattered. Ways of doing things differently in terms of routine and an attitude toward the environment that refused the logics of mastery enabled play spaces for children to in-form their identities in non-conventional, care-full ways (Bellacasa, 2017). The material space facilitated tendencies in the children to become-with the material structures and spaces and develop what might be understood as a ‘slow sensitivity’ with the world. The children were becoming-with Wood Fire. This is to say that in moments when where they were simply hanging out and it appeared like nothing happened, more-than-human things still happened. These moments mattered deeply to the children, eliding the developmental gaze as ‘contact zones’ (Stewart, 2017) for emergent experience.

Yet, despite the novelty of the environment, it became clear that social and cultural determinacies still had a habit of affectively orientating children’s desires where the past and the future came to shape the present. For example, how pink wellies, pink gloves, and pink waterproofs still came to structure the ways that some of the children sex-marked female were sociomaterially produced as ‘girls’ (Coleman, 2009; Swindle, 2011). Or how, in the same way, received knowledges about what it means to be a ‘big boy’ and the affective lure of male superheroes came to produce conventional masculinities in-formation. This was the case with my account of Rupert, where a sociomaterial metaphysics enabled me to demonstrate how he individuates and enacts his subjectivity through the assemblage of discursive knowledges about what it means to be a ‘big boy’, the affective lure of male superheroes, bodily postures (the power pose), and the broader material architectural surrounds. Against the human-centric focus on how children form their sense of selves in outdoor environments that I explored in Chapter Two, where there is a lack of recognition with regard to how these spaces enable or constrain subjective capacities, my analysis has illustrated how these spaces remain inflected with determinising tendencies. In doing so, I have made clear that outdoor learning environments are not discrete bubbles distinct from the ‘real’ world and the affective pull of broader normative social and cultural determinations did not get left at the nursery gates. Processually, the in-formations of children’s subjectivity that I witnessed at Wood Fire were

subject to constant flux, caught up between the hold of the already-known (specifically, in terms of normative knowledges about gender) and at the same time open to the unknown (of the non-sensical). Deleuze and Guattari make a similar claim when they write that “smooth space is constantly being translated, transversed into a striated space (and) striated space is constantly being reversed, returned to a smooth space” (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987:474). Therefore, I am wary of elevating Wood Fire as an exemplary setting to which every child should attend. I recognise that smooth spaces alone, that allow for experimentation, will not entirely mitigate the weight of conformity according to wider social, cultural and curricula normativities. Yet, they may well enable the production of new capacities, more affirmative ways of knowing, untethered from the conceits of individualism and beyond the artificial parsing of mind/body and nature/culture. Overall, the data produced with Wood Fire does enable a novel contribution toward the broader field of scholarship concerned with alter-childhood spaces that actively seek to challenge the tenets of mainstream provision. It shows how the novelty of material structures that would not normally be present in conventional settings enable diverse ways for children to relate with their environments, and how these environments can facilitate particular sensitivities of being with/in the world.

3. *To evaluate how a sociomaterial metaphysics toward understanding children’s identity formation can assist future learning and teaching.*

Throughout this thesis, my intention has been to problematise conventional understandings of early childhood development and invokes new knowledges about how practices are assembled to produce determinate subjectivities. The produced data does have implications for future learning and teaching, insofar as it will resonate closely with those concerned with social justice in early childhood to approach questions of subjectivity from a different metaphysical position. This is not to say that affective sociomaterialisation is better than other frameworks, though it does carry distinct implications for how the production of power relations within early childhood can be approached and challenged. For instance, by privileging the assemblage I have enabled an understanding of experience that avoids the cumbersome logics of the child as an omnipresent force and instead situates agency as both distributed and relational. The example of the tyre-hill in Chapter Five is salient here, which became productive of subjectivities on more-than-human terms, increasing capacities to act outside of any predefined developmentalist purpose. This allows for an expanded perception of how we, humans, are produced as individuals in certain encounters prior to established classifications of the self. Further, moments where children could dwell, free from temporal constrictions, were affective practices where conventional distinctions between subject and object began to lose traction. I detailed this latter point specifically in in the section on ‘becoming-with the world’ ([see page 127](#)), where the actual experience of being outdoors with all

its multisensory happenings: the feel of wind rushing by, the grassy and gritty surface textures, the noises of bird song, was significant in enabling expressions of the self that would not usually have been possible in more conventional early childhood provision. Rather than a sole focus on the individual child, then, a sociomaterial metaphysics demonstrates new knowledges about how non-human material and elemental forces affectively shape desires and contribute toward creative ways of being and becoming.

Such a blurring of the boundaries of the self might conceivably be read as a loss of identity, echoing my initial anxieties and those of Olsson (2009) that I discuss in Chapter Three. This would, firstly, be a misinterpretation, and one must also question what it is precisely about the established logics of identity that are worth holding on to. I am not naïve to the fact that I am writing against the central tenets of identity at a time where, for many people, the loss of identity may feel like itself an act of exclusion for those who continue to struggle for identity-based rights today (Manning, 2020). However, my metaphysical approach is intended as an enrichment, an opening up of how subjectivity is known, rather than the opposite. It is an alternative conception that, against the dominant theoretical perspectives of social constructionism, performativity theory, and Piagetian developmental psychology, usefully problematises habitual understandings of subjectivity that inevitably perpetuate the exclusionary logics of individualist and anthropocentric thought. This enables us, adults, to question how bodies are always-already becoming in distinct ways and therefore provides a more diverse perspective for practitioners in understanding the processual nature of experience and how children may come to form their sense of self, materially as much as socially.

More radically, it might be said, based on the data I have presented, that this thesis has been as much about what childhood experience can teach us, as adults, as much it has been about ways that adults can support children. Given the creativity and indeterminacy inherent in how they come to experience the world in ways that challenge conventional norms and produce minor gestures in the face of major tendencies, the perception that we, adults, have something to teach them feels at best naïve. Instead, turning to the relationality inherent in childhood experiences casts a dark shadow on the individualistic and humanist nature of our own adult lives. This is a mode of being that, as I noted in Chapter Two, continues to be actively desired. Revealing, then, how children play at the boundaries of their identities in-formation, how they are always-already becoming-with the world in more-than-human ways, how they are already meeting the universe halfway (Barad, 2007), enables a light of flight toward envisaging how we all might live together in this world, differently.

7.4 Implications of this study

The theoretical proposal and subsequent data that has been produced through this thesis offers several implications for future research inquiry and practice that, while I have broadly drawn attention to in response to my aims, will be outlined in detail here. However, it is first worth acknowledging the concerns of Gallacher and Gallagher (2008, p. 504), who suggest the anxiety to ‘know’ about children and produce practical, policy-relevant implications regarding subjectivities and identity is perhaps intimately related to adult anxieties about:

How to improve them, make them more employable, more productive and healthier; how to encourage and regulate their moral conduct and to participate in democratic politics. That is, it is concerned with the production of ideal future citizens.

Their claim is convincing as it relates closely to my discussion in Chapter Two of the neoliberal tendencies of curriculum in Scotland to privilege teleological outcomes that prefigure children as future workers. Hence, while I am deeply concerned toward justice within a world saturated by inequality, my implications here are not intended to respond to the ways practitioners might ‘improve’ children, but are rather about considering how we, adults, can improve our own **response-ability** toward a less exclusionary way of knowing about subjectivities. To that end, the first clear implication from this study is that it provides practitioners and researchers with an enhanced *conception* of subjectivity through the metaphysical framework produced. As I noted within the introduction, questions of identity are rarely explicit within curriculum guidance. Where they are visible, they remain appended to developmentalist logics that privilege the child ‘as an individual’ and the cognitive at the expense of the relational and the perceptive. This was exemplified within my analysis toward the end of Chapter Two, from which Chapter Three examined a metaphysics where no primacy is given to the mind over affective ways of knowing. The need to speak at the level of metaphysics, while perhaps at a level of abstraction I acknowledge might be unfamiliar to many practitioners, remains necessary in addressing the root of experience from which subjectivities are then formed.

Additional to an enhanced conception of identity, the visuality of my findings, re-presented on more creative terms, is intended to support practitioners in developing a greater *perception* of how materiality shapes subjectivities. In many ways, the majority of the still and moving image data were intended to, affectively and effectively, disrupt the boundaries of individual identity and articulate something of the excluded middle, where it becomes possible to understand how subjectivity may be perceived on terms relational with the wider non-human environment. In

Chapter Six, for instance, I did this by experimenting with motion in the video data to produce an extended sense of time and draw the viewer's conscious attention to particular moments that, in real time, might not have registered or had an affect. Both conceptual and perceptual insights into processes of affective sociomaterialisation may be especially insightful for children who come to experience the world in ways-otherwise from the standardising expectations placed on them. For instance, my focus on the overall pedagogic approach at Wood Fire that unsettled the habitual practices of time-keeping, that would be normal in most nursery settings (Bodén, 2015; Knight, 2019), speaks to a minor temporal gesture toward children who are too often seen as out-of-sync.

I am not naïve to the fact that both the nature of doctoral research and the length of this thesis itself can mean that those who are engaged at the level of practice may not have the time, nor the desire, to read a PhD in its entirety. To mitigate against this and ensure that my research is accessible to a wider audience, I am committed to the presentation of my research findings in a much shorter length of time than it would take to read this thesis, and in a more distilled way. I had already presented at one academic conference in June 2019 on the theoretical nature of my, then proposed, research project and had begun to share my knowledge and understanding on heteronormativity and identity in early childhood to a practice-based audience. Conversations have already taken place with Early Years Scotland, whom this PhD was originally designed in partnership with, to share my research following the Viva stage. I also have experiencing of writing shorter articles to a general audience in early years media and will be able to filter the findings and implications of this thesis through this format to demonstrate further accessibility. Finally, I anticipate that in the future a focus on the significance of paying attention to subjectivities as they relate to broader questions of identity will form a focus of my own independent training and delivery through Critical Early Years.

This thesis has further implications for the role of alternative outdoor environments in Scotland, where future inquiry might further engage in a purposive approach toward examining provision where there is clear novelty in the material space. This may be determined on the basis of the findings at Wood Fire that are detailed in Chapter Five where, for instance, the nature of creatures becoming teachers signals toward the value of non-human elements that compose the space and produce an ethics of care away from notions of ownership and domestication (Ingold, 2000; Braidotti, 2013; Singh, 2018). My ethnographic account at Wood Fire also calls attention to the role of certain practices that are cultivated with an ethics of care and therefore affectively shapes sensibilities in children. For instance, where I detailed my discussion with Conor on the compost bins that are used during mealtimes, or the way in which structures were continually remade and renewed rather than wasted. There is a sense in which such matters are trivial. However, I argue

that conversely such practices are significant in problematising non-innocent, capitalist practices of consumption in early childhood environments.

Hence, the implications I have outlined thus far should be interpreted as a shift toward knowing-otherwise. Or perhaps, paradoxically, it may be argued that they require an affirmative commitment to *not* knowing. That is, the purpose of education as not claiming to know in advance the capacities of the child, not tethering their abilities to arbitrary ages and stages, and not valuing developmentalism over the use-less. As Grosz (1999b) writes in her text on the potential of not knowing, if this feels destabilising, that is because it is. Uncertainly wobbles the determinate, producing errant, experimental futures outside of signification. This is, affirmatively, to position not knowing outside of a framework of lack, as if to present a linear temporality where the goal is subsequently to know, and instead place indeterminacy as *excessive*, as productive of difference in a generative way. On a more practical level, what ‘not knowing’ might translate to within curriculum pedagogy is a challenging question to answer. What is clear is that any commitment to indeterminacy would directly contradict the neoliberal demands of the Scottish curriculum to prepare children to become ‘successful’ learners; ‘confident’ individuals; ‘responsible’ citizens; and ‘effective’ contributors (Education Scotland, 2017). Herein perhaps lies the value of ‘alter-childhood’ spaces (Kraftl, 2014) that may be more open to subverting epistemological foreclosures of potential and the habituation of particular modes of being (and becoming) through standards of ‘normal’ development. Given the increase of entirely outdoor settings in Scotland, there is potential here for these environments to advance a more radical, more-than-human, pedagogy that truly recognises the value of materiality and the non-sensical in producing not-yet-known ways of being with and in this world.

For research inquiry, my contribution to knowledge offers several avenues for further inquiry. My thesis is situated within the disciplines of childhood studies and philosophy. It offers a contemporary critique of theoretical frameworks as well as a level of originality in my application of sociomaterialism to my chosen nursery site. Especially in the Scottish context within which this thesis is written, I have drawn attention to taken-for-granted ways of knowing about the child and usefully problematised issues of agency and the relation the human and non-human world. Further, the usage of ‘affective sociomaterialisation’ is intended to provide an epistemic resonance with the language of ‘socialisation’, albeit with clear ontological and ontogenetic distinctions. Future research may benefit from the application of this term in other research contexts, for other avenues of inquiry. For example, as was the original aim of this study prior to the Covid-19 pandemic, to examine heteronormative practices with conventional early childhood provision. This study has not considered the production of racial identity, besides how I myself become racialised, although

I have utilised my learning on affect in relation to this elsewhere (Tembo, 2020b), and as such this may be an insightful future line of inquiry along with other social classifications of identity that come to form in childhood spaces.

My contribution to knowledge also has methodological implications for those uncertain about the threshold between research-creation and artistic practice, where I have affirmatively sought to trouble representationalism and engage in politics by other means (Grosz, 2008). It may also enable researchers to overcome, as I discussed toward the end of Chapter Six, 'video fear' (MacLure *et al.*, 2010), where researchers fail to articulate possibilities beyond what is already known. While my background is not within artistic practice, and as such this foray into research-creation has been fraught with a number of both conceptual and technical challenges to presentation, my intention remains that others may come to learn and develop their own approach toward the queering of visual presentation. They may continue to articulate the inherent relation between postqualitative-inspired inquiry and artistic practice in further depth.

Naming such tensions in my foray toward artistic-practices feeds into my broader ethical position in terms of affirmatively articulating the multiple and messy ways in which I, the lead researcher, am implicated in the production of this thesis. For instance, in Chapter Five where I discuss the role of researching while Black and while male. Rather than a position of distance, I have sought to become more ethically responsible for the research that I produce. The extent to which I have detailed my becoming-sociomaterial, inclusive of the messiness of such a foray, has been a real strength of this thesis. It is anticipated that future researchers may draw on my expositions and develop their own techniques for troubling the often binary separation between the researcher and their research.

On more general terms, outlining and seeking to respond to the problematic nature of how identity is currently understood, and as something that many of us, including myself, remain in tension with, signals a need to shift toward a more relational ethics. Indeed, the imperative to move beyond individualism that I have explored in this thesis is a thread that I have begun to follow in other avenues of inquiry. In a forthcoming paper (Tembo and Bateson, 2022), I engage in writing-as-inquiry through co-authorship to decentre individualism favouring a more relational ethics. I directly apply the knowledges that I have developed within this thesis to think through what the relationality of children's subjectivities might have to offer processes of collaborative inquiry, specifically in terms of racial identities. We privilege indeterminacy, unsettle the anteriority of identity and practice new modes of encounter beyond Cartesian logics.

7.5 Study limitations

In this section, I discuss and respond to some of the critiques that may be levelled against this thesis in terms of the quality of data in the light of the challenges with Covid-19, the truthfulness of my findings, and the literature that I have engaged with.

As I discussed in the foreword for this thesis, Covid-19 had a significant effect on my ability to complete this project, which has become otherwise from what it was. I nevertheless managed to get my studies back on track and have been able to directly respond to my intended aims on the basis of two detailed multisensory findings chapters. However, I remain frustrated that I could not spend any more time at Wood Fire than I did. My actual experience of doing sociomaterial ethnography, on top of the challenges of Covid-19 and the shift in my overall research focus, was compounded by a felt anxiety to record and gather data on everything that was going on and not any one (human or not) thing (or things) in particular. This was especially the case in the early days of fieldwork where, having spent the summer months locked down at home with my partner, the physical experience of spending days outside in the rain and mud, the emotional strain of developing new friendships with the children and staff, the pressure to quickly familiarise myself with doing distinctly unfamiliar sociomaterial research and the looming knowledge that Covid-19 could cut short my stay at any point was difficult, to say the least. Yet overall, while I recognise that more time in the setting may have been fruitful in documenting a sociomaterial framework in even further depth, since my original plan had been to hang out within the nursery for a few months rather than weeks, I remain confident that the data produced across the two chapters responds to my aims in an appropriate way.

While I have been clear in my approach against objectivity at various points throughout this thesis, questions will likely still be posed about the truthfulness of the data produced. As Gullion (2018, p. 44) remarks, “we tend to believe that when a research practices objectivity, the truth will be revealed”. Yet her argument continues that objectivity does not necessarily denote truth, nor conversely does subjectivity denote falseness. Hence, in naming my subjective position and the way that it has shaped this research at various points, I maintain the position that the findings produced in Chapters Five and Six are no less true than had I written under the guise of objectivity. Ultimately, I take the position that this is an ethically more productive way of engaging in research inquiry that, as I noted above with regards to the implications of this study, may support future researchers to develop their own techniques for problematising claims to objectivity and truthfulness.

As I explain in Chapter Four, my intention for choosing the fieldwork site was to study an example that carries value in own its right (Massumi, 2002; Gale, 2018, pp. 168-169). Hence, any critique of the lack of generalisability of these findings would not be appropriate as this was not my original intention. Yet these findings should produce feelings of relatability. Especially for those who have worked directly within early childhood as practitioners and are familiar with the weariness of trying to think differently about questions of identity in educational spaces. No doubt, this clique will probably be small, but that is not to say that to hold an interest of this kind is in any way insignificant. We may consider the broader trend toward new materialist scholarship as indicative of the shift away from human-centric research inquiry with young children. My thesis sits as a contribution toward other ways of sense-making in the face of the hegemony of developmentalist and individualist approaches toward education.

As I have noted throughout, coming to terms with the vast body of scholarship that might reasonably fit within a sociomaterial metaphysics has been a conceptual challenge. My decision to engage a strategy of conceptual pickpocketing to inform my sociomaterial inquiry was made in response to the extensive scope of literature that may feasibly be considered relevant to a sociomaterial framework. This has been a necessary strategy to consolidate various strands and demonstrates novelty in my overall approach. Even so, there are more generative avenues of thought, and possibly more generative concepts, that I also realise I simply have not been able to cover with the level of depth I would have liked. These areas may be explored further in future studies. For instance, as much as there are some limitations to many aspects of psychoanalytic thought, I am aware that there are some resonances between the writings of Stern (1985) and Winnicott (1971) that could prove insightful in future works. Similarly, future research may consider French theorist Gilbert Simondon's (2020) early texts on individuation, who is recognised as a major source of inspiration for Deleuze. Had this English translation been published sooner than two years into my thesis, it would certainly have been given more analysis as part of the literature. I suspect, too, that any systematic analysis of this field of inquiry would reveal the writings of Bergson (1944; 1946; 2001) and Whitehead (1968; 1971; 1997) to operate as a kind of theoretical glue across this whole body of scholarship. Their writings seem fundamental to an understanding of this metaphysical framework, but on reflection beyond the scope of what I had initially set out to explore. Ultimately, I come from an academic background within the early childhood studies field where the kinds of knowledges about subjectivity that I have learnt in the past few years were simply not part of the curriculum during my previous studies. This has been a steep learning curve where I have tried to think-otherwise. As my learning has evolved from social

constructionist thought toward sociomaterialism, those who come from a similar educational background will relate closely to this journey over the past few years.

Finally, there remains an avenue for further inquiry into the *histories* of particular materials present at Wood Fire that was not explored within this thesis. While I endeavoured to map the materiality of the space as it contributed in-the-moment to the formation of identities, staying with my analysis of objects (the tyres, the wooden structures) for even longer might have offered another form of insight into Wood Fire as itself a partially sedimented, yet partially fluid, assemblage of things, human and non-human. As part of the broader scholarship on alter-childhood spaces, it is hoped that this may form the basis for future research.

7.6 Final remarks

As I noted in the introduction, I am drawn to the production of a world where notions of value are stripped from their capitalist and neoliberal relations, where subjectivity can truly be considered otherwise away from humanism, a by-product of colonialism. A synergy is visible here between my own commitments and those of Deleuze and Guattari who were deeply critical of colonial thought. In their famous text, *Anti-Oedipus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia* (1983), which laid out an argument against the prevailing Freudian logic of psychoanalysis at the time, they write that: “Oedipus is always colonization pursued by other means, it is the interior colony, and we shall see that even here at home, where we Europeans are concerned, it is our intimate colonial education (Deleuze and Guattari, 1983:170). One may retort that their critique of Oedipus is precise to the field of psychoanalysis. However, on the basis of the literature I have identified (Wynter, 2003; Braidotti, 2013), it is clear that oedipalizing logics remain at play through the broader capitalist axiomatics that have come to shape how childhood is understood today. I made this point in Chapter Two, initially with my examination of the ways that education has become tied to economic market logics and secondly with my argument toward the implicit logic of developmentalism in the Scottish curriculum as a result of the enduring legacy of Descartes’ (1985a) humanist mode of being. Read sideways, this is another form of State philosophy through typological thought processes that foreclose children’s capacities of being and becoming to the realm of the already-known. Humanism perpetuates a logic of mastery and maintains the binary between the mind and the body, thus privileging a rationalist way of knowing the child as primarily cognitive at the expense of an understanding of experience as felt. Yet through affect, I have argued that experiences produce us as subjects as much as we consciously believe the opposite to be true. By foregrounding sociomaterialism then, I have sought to make us more capable of responding to the ways in which subjectivities in childhood can be produced otherwise from the historically-present tenets of colonialism. Again, I have endeavoured to do this through my use of affect,

where in Chapters Five and Six I played with forms of haptic perception in the presentation of my data as a means of unsettling the boundaries that we place on subjects and objects. The resultant knowledge has demonstrated the utility of a sociomaterial metaphysics in presenting a form of subjectivity on more distributed terms. By unsettling strict representation and questioning a singular notion of truth as always-already a value judgement, I have sought to produce new knowledge and produce knowledge differently (MacLure, 2013c; St.Pierre, 2020). As I have noted throughout, this was far from easy for me. I constantly grappled with the tensions around how to refigure the child without dissolving their subjectivities completely. This is partially why I chose to conceptual pick-pocket aspects from Deleuze's oeuvre rather than stay entirely faithful. Following Lapoujade (2017) I suspect a purely Deleuzian approach would tend toward *absolute deterritorialisation*, a point whereby:

We no longer conceive bodies based on our representations nor on our lived experience of them; we produce them based on the percepts and affects of which we become capable.

(Lapoujade, 2017, p. 307, original emphasis)

This Spinoza-inflected maxim that Lapoujade identifies as crucial to the overall philosophy of Deleuze gestures toward a temporality prior to representationalism and beyond the limitations of what we believe that any body can do. Therefore, it is possible to understand Deleuze's philosophy as an-archic, against structural thinking toward a world in continual flux against the hegemony of State apparatus. Yet I wonder, given the constraints of capitalism on present ways of knowing and being, if a world where bodies are no longer based on representations will ever be possible. Perhaps I remain political depressed (Fisher, 2009; Cvetkovich, 2012). Yet, again, I turn to Manning (2020, p. 52), who proposes that "a critique of identity politics must coincide with the creation of new modes of existence that do not privilege our preconstituted position but engage deeply with the will to art that opens the world to minor gestures". Privileging material spaces that continually enable children to experiment with their subjectivities in more-than-human ways then is a gesture toward indeterminate futures. Massumi, in the foreword to Deleuze and Guattari's (1987, p. xv) second tome, writes of their work that "the question is not: is it true? But: does it work? What new thoughts does it make it possible to think? What new emotions does it make it possible to feel? What new sensations and perceptions does it open in the body". In the end, this is the spirit in which this thesis should be received.

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Glossary of key conceptual terms

Affect

Affect refers to one's felt capacity to act in any encounter (Anderson, 2006; Stewart, 2007; Massumi, 2015; Simpson and Brigstocke, 2019). It is an ontogenetic (see **Ontogenesis**) force that mobilises **subjectivities** in composition with elements of an **assemblage**. Affect unsettles a notion of subjectivity as produced throughout conscious perception, in the mind, and instead facilitates an understanding of the human body's visceral, or felt, sensibility, through sensations that occur at a pre- or just- conscious level. There is some debate within the literature about the relationship between affect and emotion. For the purposes of this study, emotions are understood as subsequent to affect, "as affect plus an aware of awareness of that affect" (Manning, 2006, p. xxi). However, it is notable that in everyday reality there is a great deal of slippage between these terms such that a distinction is not always necessary (Ahmed, 2014a).

Affective sociomaterialisation

This is an original term used within this thesis. It is intended to describe the process through which **subjectivity** is produced on the basis of the **sociomaterial** framework that I advance. Affective sociomaterialisation denotes a more expansive way of understanding subjectivity, compared to conventional theoretical frameworks, insofar as it incorporates **ontogenetic** as well as **epistemological** knowledges. *Cf. Affect.*

Alter-childhood

This is a term originally coined by Kraftl (2014, p.219) and deployed within this thesis to describe "explicit attempts to imagine, construct, talk about, and control the life worlds of children differently from a perceived mainstream ... not as a static category for naming particular discourses, against others (i.e., **neoliberalism**), but as a cipher for open and, hopefully, productive questioning".

Agency

Agency is the capacity of human **beings** to express themselves, understood as occurring through conscious thought (Oxford English Dictionary, 2021a). *Cf. Performativity, posthuman performativity.*

Agential cuts

A Baradian (2003) term used to refer to the ways that particular apparatus are productive of particular practices of knowledge, in contrast to the position that such apparatus serve a neutral

role or lack agency. Agential cuts thus challenge the Cartesian metaphysical presupposition between subject and object.

Anthropocene

The term Anthropocene denotes a geographical epoch, or a period in time, in which humankind has significantly shaped the global environment (Crutzen, 2002). It is derived from the Greek ‘anthrōpos’ which refers to human being. Relatedly, Anthropocentrism is a perspective that gives primacy to humans and human **agency** above the **non-human** world. It is derived from the term The exact period in which this epoch originated remains subject to debate. However, it is worth noting that the majority of accounts fail to acknowledge the effects of the Western **colonial** project in shaping this era (Yusoff, 2018).

Assemblage

The term assemblage was introduced by Deleuze and Guattari (1987) to conceptualise the way in which heterogeneous elements come together in a non-homogenous groupings as the “minimum real unit” of experience (Deleuze and Parnet, 2007, p. 51). Assemblages challenge the logic that there is a pre-existing world that sits anterior to events where individual components subsequently interact with each other. Rather assemblages produce and are constitutive *of* worlds through the very coming together of heterogeneous, human and **non-human**, elements. For the purposes of research analysis in this thesis, assemblages shift the scope of inquiry beyond the individual human alone, toward the human and non-human relationality of certain events that may enable or constrain certain capacities or affects. For instance, in an early childhood context, any number of elements (building blocks, toy cars, home corners, superhero outfits, children) may come together as an assemblage to crystallise certain **gender** identities.

Attunement

The process of acclimatising oneself, or ‘tuning in’, with something. In the literature, Stewart (2010, p. 4) describes an atmospheric attunement as an “alerted sense that something is happening and an attachment to sensing out whatever it is”. Others in a similar vein have considered the value of attunement for research inquiry as a means of recognising certain **affective** forces between human and **non-human** bodies (Blackman, 2012; Brigstocke and Noorani, 2016; Hohti *et al.*, 2021; Hann, 2021). Elsewhere, I have used this term in relation to whiteness as an affective formation of power (Tembo, 2021a)..

Becoming

A significant, and perhaps central, concept used by Deleuze (1986; 1989; 1994; 2007) and Deleuze and Guattari (1986; 1987) to unsettle the fixity of **being** and undermine **identity** in experience.

Becoming does not imply a movement between two states of being because this presupposes being as the *a priori* state. Rather, it is more accurate to say that there is nothing other than becoming and that being is simply “a contraction of the flow of becoming” (Colebrook, 2002, p. 126). In this sense, the actual experience of life itself is dislodged from a **humanist** metaphysics and has no fixed destination or final state of being outside itself. *Cf.* **Ontogenesis, process philosophy.**

Being

This term is used widely in philosophical literature and conventionally refers to states of existence, or presence (Oxford English Dictionary, 2021b). Critiques of being have centred around an omission of the nature of movement and process, such that ‘to be’ typically refers to a fixed form of identity or subject position (i.e. to be a man or a woman) (Braidotti, 2002; Massumi, 2002; Nail, 2019). This is not to dismiss the value of being, but rather to acknowledge it as limited to a particular mode of existence (Massumi, 2002, p. 7). An inclusion of these concepts necessitates a shift in terminology toward **becoming**. *Cf.* **Ontology.**

Body without Organs (BwO)

For Deleuze and Guattari (1987) BwO does mean a human body removed of its biological organs, but a body that has become un-organised through assemblages. In their own words, “the body without organs is not a dead body but a living body all the more alive and teeming once it has blown apart the organism and its organization ... [it] is a body populated by multiplicities” (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987, p. 30).

Capitalism

An economic system centred on the accumulation of capital, or wealth, resulting in profit through free-market exchange (Jahan and Mahmud, 2015; Carr *et al.*, 2018, p. 14). For Massumi (2018), capitalism transforms the qualitative nature of life itself into quantitative measure through financial systems.

Colonialism

This term relates to the practice of political and economic domination and subjugation over other countries, lands and peoples. Used here to refer to Western colonialism as it emerged from around the fifteenth century and remains in places today, namely through **humanism** and the hegemony of Enlightenment philosophies (Oyewumi, 1997; Wynter, 2003; Lugones, 2007; Ahuja, 2017).

Desire

An attraction toward something, mobilised through **affect**. Deleuze (1992c; 1997) and Deleuze and Guattari (1987) give ontological priority to desire over **power** as it emerges through **assemblages**.

Developmentalism

In an educational context, this term refers to a normative way of understanding the child according to linear and predetermined goals and standards of development (usually split into physical, social, emotional, cognitive, and communicative development) (Riggs, 2006; Renold, 2005, pp. 24-25; Burman, 2016). Developmentalism is problematic because it positions all children as lacking, prejudices those who fall short of these standards, and forecloses alternative explanations about how children make sense of their worlds (Pires, 2014; Manning, 2016).

Developmental psychology

A theoretical approach concerned with psychological aspects of development (see **developmentalism**) (Qvortrup, Corsaro and Honig, 2009; Burman, 2016; Shaffer *et al.*, 2020). While a heterogeneous field of scholarship, within early childhood research developmental psychology scholars have tended to uphold the principles of developmentalism and **individualism**. Proponents of developmental psychology also tend to give primacy to cognitive development (Watson and Coulter, 2008).

Diffraction

Within **sociomaterial** thought, diffraction is a generative concept that involves “reading insights through one another in attending to and responding to the details and specificities of relations of difference and how they matter” (Barad, 2007, p.71). Diffraction is distinct from reflection, and thus **representationalism**, and instead argues that we cannot know the world by studying it at a distance, we know because we are always-already part of its **becoming**. In methodological terms, a diffractive approach is essentially an alternative method to critical reflection that is open to immanent and subjective truth(es) in the moment of the encounter. As Barad (2007, p.94) further notes, a diffractive methodology “allows [the researcher] to examine in detail important philosophical issues such as the conditions for the possibility, or objectivity, the nature of measurement, the nature of meaning making, the conditions for intelligibility, the nature of causality and identity, and the relationship between discursive practices and the material worlds”

Discourse

A Foucauldian (1978; 1980c; 1990; 2002) term describing bodies of knowledge, including language, thoughts, and actions, that produce, and are constitutive, of social worlds. Viewing the social world as constantly disciplined through discourse, also referred to as discursive practices, allows for an

understanding of the power mechanisms within such practices. Foucault made clear that the most powerful discourses were rooted within institutional structures and tended toward processes of identification (see **identity**). One example of a discourse would be that of **gender**, which is productive of gendered identities.

Epistemology

Epistemology is a philosophical term concerned with knowledge, beliefs, evidence and ways of knowing about the world (Williams, 2016, pp. 36-41; Denzin and Lincoln, 2017). In short, it can be understood as the study of knowledge including the ways that we know about things.

Gender

Gender refers to the social, cultural, and material expressions of biological sex, visible through a combination of behaviours, roles, and expectations, and most commonly measured on a scale of masculinity and femininity. While it is understood to be fluid, rather than fixed, and vary according to social, cultural and individual preference, research has shown that there is a strong tendency for gender to be experienced as determinate of one's **identity** in binary terms (Oyewumi, 1997; Nokizaru, 2015; Hines, 2018).

Haptic perception

Haptic perception relates to a felt sense of tactility through vision (de Freitas, 2016).

Heteronormativity

Heteronormativity connotes a body of norms which hold that people are determined according to distinct and complementary sexualities and **genders**. These categories are then assumed to be natural and fixed constructions. Biological sex, sexuality, gender identity and expression and normative gender roles are aligned in such a way that heterosexuality is privileged, normalised and naturalised, and non-heterosexual relationships are rendered deviant, abnormal and unnatural (Rich, 1993; Warner, 1993; Katz, 1995).

Humanism

Humanism is a metaphysical stance that asserts the inherent, individualistic (see **individualism**) value of human thoughts, beliefs and actions (Braidotti, 2013). The formation of the human individual subject is most clearly attributed to the philosophical position outlined by Descartes (1985b; 1985a), an Enlightenment era philosopher.

Identity

Related to the legible characterisation of a subject according to particular classifications, personalities or social representations within a given society. Identity is often considered to be a

stable feature of the subject, however in this thesis it is understood through **sociomaterialism** on more relational terms (Manning, 2012).

Immanence

Immanence is a metaphysical position relating to a singular account of experience in which there is nothing outside of, or *a priori* to that experience. Deleuze (1994; 2001) and Deleuze and Guattari's (1994; 1987) interpretation of immanence is informed directly by the inherent relationality of Spinoza's **monism**. *Cf.* **Transcendence**.

Individualism

Similar to **humanism**, this term relates to a position that asserts the value of the individual human **being** (Oxford English Dictionary, 2019).

In-formation

The process of coming to form without prior grounds (Manning, 2012). *cf.* **ontogenesis**.

Intra-action

Intra-action is a term first coined by Karen Barad (1996) to grasp the mutual constitution of **non-human** and human elements that emerge through, rather than precede, their intra-action. Whereas interaction is based on the metaphysics of anterior experience that privileges pre-constituted subjects and objects, intra-action is instead informed on the premise of the ontogenetic inseparability through which objects and subjects then emerge. *Cf.* **in-formation**, **ontogenesis**.

Materiality

The quality or aspect of relating to the material, which itself relates to matter and the physical (Oxford English Dictionary, 2020). In this thesis, I refer to the materiality of my fieldwork setting to include the toys, built frames, and the composition of the environment itself.

Metaphysics

Metaphysics is a philosophical term that relates to the basic nature of experience itself, inclusive of **epistemology**, **ontogenesis** and **ontology** (Williams, 2016, p. 6). Western philosophical thought has traditionally upheld Descartes' (1985a) metaphysics, however alternative frameworks exist within and outside of this context (Spinoza, 2002; Mignolo, 2012).

Monism

Monism is etymologically derived from the Greek term *monos* meaning 'single' and is used to describe Spinoza's (2002) **metaphysical** framework as one that interprets the nature of reality as inherently relational. Monism contests the dualism of Descartes' metaphysics and is used in this

thesis to overcome **anthropocentrism** and redistribute **agency** on **more-than-human** terms. *Cf.* **Humanism**.

More-than-human

This is a term with roots in both human geography, anthropology and new materialist thought processes which aims to trouble the binary separation of the **non-human** and human (and by extension, **humanism**) (Whatmore, 2002; Fox and Alldred, 2017). More-than draws attention to the entanglements that emerge through both non-human and human relations and signifies a move away from individualistic humanist conceptions of agency as located in the corporeal body, toward an understanding of agency as distributed across given relations (see entry on **assemblages**). This term is often used interchangeably with **'posthuman'** ([see page 11](#) of the main thesis).

Nomad thought

Nomad thought, or nomadism, is the name given by Deleuze and Guattari (1987) to a mode of knowing rooted in process philosophy intended to emphasise the ontogenetic nature of knowledge against the logics of **State philosophy**.

Non-human

All materials and the natural world which are not human corporeal bodies (Oxford English Dictionary, 2021c).

Neoliberalism

Neoliberalism is used to describe a set of practices rooted in the early modernisation and free-market ideology period of the 1960s and 1970s that, in more and less explicit ways, uphold a belief in personhood as 'human capital' (McCafferty, 2010; Giroux, 2014; Ball, 2015; Roberts-Holmes and Lee, 2019; Roberts-Holmes and Moss, 2021). This is most clearly illustrated in educational contexts through the **epistemological** belief implied with curricular models that people can be seen in relation to their labour market value, thus shaping individual **subjectivities** according to predetermined goals and standards that prefigure children as future workers. *Cf.* **Capitalism**.

Neurotypical

A pervasive belief that "there is an independence of thought and being attributable above all to the human, a better- than- ness accorded to our neurology" (Manning, 2016, p. 3). Put differently, neurotypicality can be understood "akin to structural racism—as the infusion of white supremacy in the governing definition of what counts as human" (Manning, 2020, p. 2).

Non-sense

A Deleuzian term referring to that which is deemed irrational or outside of reason, often through humour, irony, or paradox. It is intended as a means of unsettling linguistics outside the domain of propositional logic and representation (Colebrook, 2002; Young, Genosko and Watson, 2013; Deleuze, 2015). Deleuze drew heavily on the literary works of Lewis Carroll in *Alice's Adventures in Wonderland* to illustrate how non-sensical expressions and events can be productive of new forms of sense.

Ontogenesis

A term popularised by Massumi (2002, p. 8) to provide a distinction from **ontology** and situate being (onto-) as equal to emergence from which there is no anterior ground. Ontogenetic is the adjectival term.

Ontology

Ontology is a philosophical term concerned with the natures of, usually human, being and existence (Williams, 2016, pp. 154-159).

Performativity

Theorised by Judith Butler (1993, p. 2) to refer to “the reiterative and citational practice by which discourse produces the effects that it names”, whereby performances of the self are bounded discursive practices that are consistently repeated primarily through speech acts, rather than being a universal condition of one’s identity. Performativity enables a further understanding of **agency** in relation to discursive practices and in this these I use performativity theory as a broad term to relate to scholarship informed by Butler’s conception. *Cf.* **Posthuman performativity, discourse.**

Posthuman performativity

A phrase coined by Karen Barad (2003) to resituate the classic conception of **performativity** on terms that do not grant significance to human performance over **materiality**. Drawing from insights in the field of quantum physics, Barad restates a case for matter and meaning without giving *a priori* primacy to either. She proposed that “all bodies, not merely ‘human’ bodies, come to matter through the world’s iterative intra-activity - its performativity” (Barad 2003, p. 823). **Agency** is distributed, relational, and contributes toward a conception of the self as **more-than-human**. For research inquiry this enlarges the ambit beyond the individual, beyond **humanism**, toward a **monist** metaphysics which allows for a consideration of the **non-human** things that compose (us, humans) in experience (Spinoza, 2002).

Postqualitative

This term refers to a form of inquiry in which researchers seek to rework traditional ideas of voice and data in conventional qualitative scholarship, trouble a binary distinction between researcher and researched, and foreground a more relational, **sociomaterial**, analysis (Pierre, 2011; Lather and St. Pierre, 2013; MacLure, 2013b; St. Pierre, 2018; Koro-Ljungberg *et al.*, 2019).

Posthuman

This term is usually attributed to Haraway (1991) within the field of Science and Technology Studies. In contemporary usage it is usually understood as shorthand for the ‘posthumanities’ as a field of scholarship, or as synonymous with **more-than-human**.

Process philosophy

Process philosophy is **metaphysics** that advances a conception of the world as an ongoing process in continual transformation (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987; Grosz, 1999a; Dolphijn and Tuin, 2013). As it relates to **subjectivity**, process philosophy enables a recognition of **becoming** as much as **being**, such that to ‘be’ in the first place is always-already a processual move within the ongoing middling of life itself. Hence why **ontogenesis** is preferred to **ontology** (Massumi, 2002; Manning, 2006).

Power

The capacity to influence others, interpreted as consequential from **desire** (Deleuze and Guattari, 1987; Deleuze, 1992c; 1997).

Representationalism

For Barad (2003, p. 804), this term refers to “the belief in the ontological distinction between representations and that which they purport to represent; in particular, that which is represented is held to be independent of all practices of representing”. For her, as with Deleuze (1994), this belief is typically reliant on the assumption that there is a world separate to our interpretation of it, and that proponents of representationalism tend to foreground language at the expense of the **ontological** nature of things themselves.

Research-assemblage

Refers to the heterogeneous human and **non-human** elements that come together to produce research and data (Fox and Alldred, 2015). *Cf.* **Assemblage**.

Research-creation

This term was originally coined within the journal *Inflexions* (2008) and has come to refer to the practice of producing new knowledge through artistic practice within research (Manning, 2015).

Response-ability

The capacity to respond to others, human or not. Distinct from responsibility which refers to an external obligation or sense of accountability (Haraway and Kenney, 2015, p. 256).

Social constructionism

A theoretical framework often attributed to Michel Foucault (1978; 1980c; 1980a; 1980b; 1986) in which human beings are understood as constructed by **power** in the form of **discourse**.

Sociomaterialism

Sociomaterialism refers to the overarching metaphysical framework that brings together Spinozist (2002) **monism** and insights from **process philosophy** (Massumi, 2002) in relation to Deleuze and Guattari's (1987) concepts of the **assemblage** and **affect**. With these, sociomaterialism articulates an alternative understanding of how children might come to form their **subjectivities**, in contrast to dominant theoretical perspectives.

Sonic geography

Relating to the **affective** capacity of sound with a particular place (Gallagher, 2011; Kanngieser, 2012; Gallagher, 2016; Doughty and Drozdowski, 2022)

Smooth and striated space

Deleuze and Guattari (1987) introduce the concepts of 'smooth' and 'striated' spaces to further understand the relation that humans and non-humans have with the spatial world. They draw on the board games Go and chess to exemplify these terms. Whereas the rules of Go facilitate an infinite variety of movements across the board, making it a *smooth* space, the internal rules accorded to chess pieces make movements much more restricted, or *striated*. Smooth spaces are understood as nomadic, unpredictable and allow for the production of new knowledges, whereas striated spaces are generally more coded according to particular demarcations of territory.

Space

In this thesis, space is understood not as fixed in place, but rather as produced through **intra-actions** (Barad, 1996; Massey, 2005). These can augment or diminish certain capacities and therefore are productive of **subjectivities**.

State philosophy

A term used by Massumi in the translators forward to Deleuze and Guattari's (1987) *A Thousand Plateaus* to refer to the author's exposition of the relation between the State and modes of philosophical inquiry that align with the striating and typological logics of **representationalism**. As Roy (2003, p. 114) usefully explains of Deleuze and Guattari's concept, "what state philosophy

tries to do is to bring under control the unmanageable existence, but in the process of doing so, it reifies the reference points, thus reducing existence to a grid". *Cf. Nomad thought.*

Subjectivity

Relates to the condition of being and becoming a subject. In this thesis I examine subjectivity through the perspectives of Descartes' **humanism** and through **sociomaterialism**.

Transcendence

A transcendent metaphysics is the position that there is a world and then a representation of that world, usually represented by the reasoning human subject. This, however, implies that the thinking subject is anterior to that world thus acting as the overseer and the sole determiner of that world (Haraway, 1988; Colebrook, 2002). *Cf. Immanence.*

List of Appendices

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Appendix 1: parent/carer information sheet

<p style="text-align: right;"><small>UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND</small> UWS</p> <h3>Parent/Carer Information Sheet</h3> <p><i>UWS Doctoral Research Project (ethical approval no. 8838), September 2020. Lead Researcher: Shaddai Tembo; [REDACTED]</i></p> <p>Who am I?</p> <p>My name is Shaddai, I am a PhD Student at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). I am a former early years practitioner and have experience in a variety of nurseries and children's centres. Your child is invited to take part in this study following your nursery's membership status with Early Years Scotland, a third-sector organisation who are supporting my research. The UWS Ethics Committee have approved this study.</p> <p>Purpose of the Project</p> <p>Children's play provides an important site for them to develop ideas about their own gender identity in relation to others. This project focuses on how boys and girls play in different spaces within the nursery, and how their play is influenced by certain spaces and materials.</p> <p>What does the research involve?</p> <p>The research involves me spending time in your child's setting focusing on free play times within the nursery routine where I will be making observations using field-notes, photographs, and video recordings. Specifically, I will be exploring play across different spaces (for example, a climbing frame area or a mud kitchen area) and looking at how different materials (for example, a dress, or building blocks) enable or constrain certain forms of play.</p> <p>In relation the video recording, I intend to use an iPad or similar device to record footage of certain play events. This will be similar to existing practice within your setting. Video footage allows me to attend to more than simply the child's or practitioner's voice and focus on the whole nursery environment. Using video data allows me to illustrate how particular events unfold and understand the multisensory elements constraining certain forms of play.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">1</p>	<p style="text-align: right;"><small>UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND</small> UWS</p> <p>I recognise this may be seen as intrusive, however because the video recording device is highly visible children will be able to understand I am filming them. I will avoid filming any situations when the children did not appear to have noticed my presence and I will respond to any situation when it is clear my presence is not welcome. I intend to follow your child's nursery safeguarding procedure at any time.</p> <p>Will my child be recognisable and who will have access to the data?</p> <p>I intend to use pseudonyms rather than your child's real name and will avoid any information that would easily identify your child. I intend to blur and cover the faces of children using software which will mimic "natural" blurs. This means that children will not be recognizable. I shall store all data on a password-protected computer accessed only by myself. This will be shared with my supervisory team solely for the purposes of data analysis. The recorded media and photographs will be deleted from my recording device immediately following download; and transcribed only by myself.</p> <p>What will my child have to do?</p> <p>There are no specific requirements or instructions for this study, I am focusing on how routine, ordinary, everyday play events create certain affects, rather than "testing" anything out specifically.</p> <p>Does my child have to take part?</p> <p>No, your child does not have to take part. If you do choose to take part, you may withdraw your child's consent at any time during the fieldwork phase.</p> <p>What are the possible disadvantages and benefits of taking part?</p> <p>There are no known disadvantages or risks to this study. I hope this study will have implications for practice which I look forward to sharing with the nursery staff team.</p> <p>Further Information</p> <p>If you have any questions, or for more information on this study, please feel free to get in touch with me directly at [REDACTED] or you may contact my supervisor, Dr Conny Gollek at [REDACTED]</p> <p style="text-align: center;">2</p> <div style="border: 1px solid red; padding: 2px; display: inline-block; color: red;">Personal details withheld.</div>
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Appendix 2: parent/carer consent form

Parent/Carer Consent Form

UWS Doctoral Research Project (ethical approval no. 8838), September 2020. Lead Researcher: Shaddal Tembo, [REDACTED]. If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the ESS Ethics Committee by email at: [REDACTED]. Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Education and Social Science, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

*Required

Personal details withheld.

1. Child's name *

2. Parent/Carer name *

3. Please enter today's date below. *

Example: 7 January 2019

4. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

5. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

6. I consent to the processing of my personal information for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation. *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

7. I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any publication resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me. *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

8. I understand my child, or the child for whom I hold responsibility, may be video recorded as part of this study. *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

9. I freely agree for my child to participate in this study. *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

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Google Forms

Appendix 3: Practitioner information sheet

Practitioner Information Sheet

UWS Doctoral Research Project (ethical approval no. 8838), September 2020. Lead Researcher: Shaddai Tembo;

Personal details withheld.

Who am I?

My name is Shaddai (Shad is fine), I am a PhD Student at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). I am a former early years practitioner and have experience in a variety of nurseries and children's centres. You are invited to take part in this study following your nursery's membership status with Early Years Scotland. The UWS Ethics Committee have approved this study.

Purpose of the Project

Children's play provides an important site for them to develop ideas about their own gender identity in relation to others. This project focuses on how boys and girls play in different spaces within the nursery, and how their play is influenced by certain spaces and materials.

What does the research involve?

The research involves me spending time in your setting focusing on free play times within your nursery routine where I will be making observations using: field-notes, photographs, and video recordings. Specifically, I will be exploring play across different spaces (for example, a climbing frame area or a mud kitchen area) and looking at how different materials (for example, a dress, or a building blocks) enable or constrain certain forms of play.

In relation to the video recording, I intend to use an iPad to record footage of certain play events. Video footage allows me to attend to more than simply the child's or practitioner's voice and focus on the whole nursery environment. Using video data allows me to recognise how particular events unfold and understand the resources and materials constraining certain forms of play.

1

I recognise this may be perceived as intrusive, however because the video recording device is highly visible children will be able to understand it clearly as an observational tool. I will avoid filming any situations when the children did not appear to have noticed my presence and I will respond to any situation when it is clear my presence is not welcome. I intend to follow your nursery setting's safeguarding procedure and to read this policy ahead of my time in the nursery to ensure that I understand how to proceed.

Will you be recording everything I say and do?

I will not be recording continuously. I intend to carry my device at all times and record only when I see play events of interest. These events may be as short as 30 seconds and will likely be no more than several minutes each time. The focus will be on play events, of which you may or may not be part of. It should be obvious when I am filming and you will be able to signal me to stop recording at any time

Sometimes we will talk informally about my research within the nursery. If you make any comments that I feel may help my study, I may ask you if I can note our conversation down. You may say no, this will not affect your overall participation, and unless I ask for your consent, what you say will not be recorded or form part of the study.

The exact duration and dates for the study are still to be negotiated with your setting, though you will have this information as soon as possible.

What will I have to do?

There are no specific requirements or instructions for this study. I will not ask you to do anything other than what you would typically do in your normal role. This is because I am focusing on how routine, ordinary, everyday play events create certain affects, rather than "testing" anything out specifically. This project is not designed to 'test' your ability as a practitioner, observe your capabilities or make judgements on your practice in any way.

2

Will I have to option to share my thoughts?

Yes, following the fieldwork phase, I intend offer you the opportunity to debrief and reflect on the video footage I will have recorded. This may be audio recorded, depending on your consent, and may form part of my data collection and findings.

Do I have to take part?

No, you do not have to take part. If you do choose to take part, you may withdraw your consent at any time during the fieldwork phase.

Will I be recognisable and who will have access to the data?

I intend to use pseudonyms rather than practitioner's and children's real names and will avoid the use of information that would easily identify a specific participant or nursery. I intend to blur and cover the faces of practitioners and children using post-processing software which will mimic "natural" blurs caused by camera dynamics. This means that children will not be recognizable.

Who will have access to the data collected during the study and how will you keep it confidential?

I shall store all data on a password-protected computer accessed only by myself. This will be shared with my supervisory team solely for the purposes of data analysis. The recorded media and photographs will be deleted from my recording device immediately following download; and transcribed only by myself.

What are the possible disadvantages and benefits of taking part?

There are no known disadvantages or risks to this study. There are no financial benefits to taking part in this study. However, I do anticipate this study will have implications for practice which I look forward to sharing with you.

What happens when the project is finished?

Following the conclusion of this project, I look forward to sharing my findings and analysis with your setting. You would be welcome to read my full thesis, and I intend to provide other, shorter, versions of my work. This may take the form of a poster, a

leaflet, or I may create an event for participants to attend where I would present my research and allow sufficient time for questions and discussion.

Further Information

For more information on this study, please feel free to get in touch with me directly at [REDACTED] or you may contact my supervisor, Dr Conny Gollek

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 4 Practitioner consent form

Personal details withheld.

Practitioner Consent Form

UWS Doctoral Research Project (ethical approval no. 8838), September 2020. Lead Researcher: Shaddai Tembo, [REDACTED]

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the ESS Ethics Committee by email at: [REDACTED] Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Education and Social Science, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

***Required**

1. Your name *

2. Job Title *

3. Please enter today's date below. *

Example: 7 January 2019

4. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

5. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

6. I consent to the processing of my personal information for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation. *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

7. I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any publication resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me. *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

8. I understand I may be video recorded as part of this study. *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

9. I freely agree for my child to participate in this study. *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

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Google Forms

Appendix 5: child consent book

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Shad's Research Book

1

Hello 😊

My name is Shad.

I work at a university, where grown-ups learn about children and nursery.

Here is a picture of my university in Ayr.

2

It is a very **big** building. We do lots of things at university.

Sometimes we teach people in lectures.

3

We have a **library** 📖 like you do at
(*name of centre*).
It is very quiet (shh!)

We also have a nice **canteen** to eat our
lunch. 🍴🍰

4

We have lots of work to do at University,
and I would like your help with my
Research Project.

A Research Project is a big story about
you, your parents or carers, and your
helpers.

In my Research Project, I would like to
find out about how you play with your
friends.

5

I will do this by watching you play,
playing with you and with the other
children and adults.

I will also be using our play to help me
at university.

6

I will always ask you if I can play with you first.

You can say **yes** or **no**. It is up to you whether I can play or watch you play.

Thank you for taking the time to listen to my Research Story.

Shad.

This leaflet was made using photographs from University of the West of Scotland and Pixabay (CCO approved; free for commercial use; no attribution required – www.pixabay.com)

7

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8

Appendix 6: Ethical approval letters*

*The two ethical approval letters represent initial approval and approval based on amendments made in light of Covid-19.

Appendix 7: Link to Video data

The video that accompanies this thesis can be downloaded from **here**.

Note that permission is necessary to view this video for confidentiality purposes.

Alternatively, you may copy and paste the following link into your browser:

https://studentmailuwsac-my.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/personal/shaddai_tembo_uws_ac_uk/Documents/Tembo%20S%20Affective%20Sociomaterialisation%20Thesis%200422?csf=1&web=1&e=paobla

Notes

Please note that you should *download* the video, rather than view it in OneDrive for better quality.

The video is available to those granted access only.